

**Human integration issues during post mergers and acquisitions:
A mix methodology approach in the study of successful mergers of humans**

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Abstract

The study of mergers and acquisitions is a broad interdisciplinary research field. In the corporate world, mergers and acquisitions are ever present, and have become an increasingly important part of corporate strategies in present. However, the failure rate is alarming and therefore in-depth analysis required incorporating multidisciplinary areas to unearth the reasons behind higher M&A's failure rate which is between 70 and 90 percent (Kenny, 2020). During the process, the biggest threat for organisations is unsuccessful attempt of the merger, focus primarily on transition of the two organisations leaving behind the factors affecting human beings (employees) associated with both organisations. Research have been conducted on this phenomenon investigating human factors causing the failure of M&As and empirical evidence available which is insufficient to provide an in-depth analysis of human related factors due to confidentiality and privacy issues and underlying human factors during M&As are underexplored. There are several studies who have worked on the human issues during M&As however, to my knowledge all studies are dispersed, and therefore, need for a comprehensive study who have inculcated these combined factors and conducted a comprehensive analysis of factors affecting humans during M&As. This study fulfilling this gap by incorporating multi-disciplinary M&A integration issues of humans between two firms divided into 7 broad categories of culture, leadership, communication, emotions, IT/IS, management of change and HRM issues such as employees' satisfactions, turnover of key people, post-merger performance drops, and morale problems. This study not only provide the rich understanding and in-depth analysis on human factors surrounding change process of M&As but also provide key contributions to the literature and practice by identifying key factors which are very important to consider during the integration process of M&As. Mix methodology approach was used to address these factors affecting humans at work, the results of this study show that dealing with the above elements individually and collectively and incorporating them in the M&As policy will result in successful M&As integration which can reduce failure rates. Emerging from these findings, Conceptual Integrative Framework developed which can be followed by M&A partners to avoid human issues affecting M&As.

Key Words: merger and acquisition, post-merger integration, culture, culture integration, leadership, leadership integration, change management, change, organisational change, innovation, communication, process integration, systems integration, information technology, information systems, IT/IS integration, human resource management, HR integration, employees' emotions, employees' satisfactions, job satisfaction, human integration, compensations, employee's turnover, post-merger performance drops, and morale.

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List of Abbreviations

M&A - Mergers and Acquisitions

CFA - Confirmatory Factor Analysis

EFA - Exploratory Factor Analysis

PCA - Principal Component Analysis

ERP - Enterprise Resource Planning

TQM - Total quality management

SPSS - Statistical Package for Social Sciences

HRD - Human Resource Development

HRM - Human Resource Management

IT – Information Technology

IS – Information Systems

IT System - Information Technology and Information System

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CHAPTER 1- Introduction

1.1 Background

Firms constantly looking out for growth in terms of their sales, capacity, and profits either in organic way where firms hire additional salespeople and invest in developing new products or in non-organic way where firms developed through mergers and acquisitions (M&A). Analysing from the history, mergers and acquisitions have evolved in 5 phases, each of which is discussed here as outlined from previous incidents, economic factors cause mergers & acquisitions. The macroeconomic environment, which includes GDP growth, interest rates and monetary policies, plays a key role in the process of mergers or acquisitions between firms. Since end of the 19th century, there had been five M&A waves which provide evidence to the increasing prevalence of M&A for firms to grow and gain new capabilities (Cartwright and Schoenberg, 2006). Each mergers and acquisitions wave had different and complex characteristics and was generated by various events which combinations were driven by external and internal factors. It is very important to understand the dynamics of mergers and acquisitions wave and its patterns as they can provide a valuable insight to the emergence of current wave of M&A.

1.1.1 First wave (1893-1910)

The first wave of mergers and acquisitions in US initiated around in 1893 and lasted till 1910. This wave was driven by the development of the transcontinental railway network system that potentially linked cities across the different continents among US states and created an integrated national market in the US which turned the local firms in US to grow in their size and become national companies. During this wave, companies were merged through both vertical and horizontal integration and some of the famous brands such as Coca-Cola and General Electric emerged through the horizontal integration of leading producers. This wave was represented by horizontal type of mergers, in which firms seek to acquire and merge with other firms within the industry. This could also aim at merging or acquiring the competitor within the same industry which can potentially increase the competition due to having less firms offering the same products or services in the market. This is often brought about by larger corporations that aim to achieve more productive economies of scale, as the firms that band together sell the same products or

services. Therefore, it became the standard to form trusts. This was particularly appealing to corporations seeking to create monopolies and market dominance, as the combinations resulted in greater combined market shares. Just before the beginning of the First World War, big giants' corporations in manufacturing and transportation sectors in the United States, particularly in the steel, oil, mining, and railroad industries feel the taste of rise and managed to turn themselves into massive organisations. Finally, horizontal mergers have also strengthened the telecommunications market during first merger and acquisition wave.

1.1.2 Second wave (1919-1929/30)

The second wave of mergers and acquisitions was driven by the expansion of automobiles from the 1920s to the early 1930s. The availability and affordability of automobiles allowed the company to effectively utilize the sales force. It stimulated corporate development, especially in food and Food processing industry. Again, it is characterized by a high degree of vertical and horizontal integration between the secondary producers in heavy industry and the financial sector. The main impact of this wave of mergers and acquisitions is that oligopoly has replaced monopoly. Companies that cannot obtain a share of shares during the first wave must merge with other companies or purchase other companies to maintain their competitiveness with the larger participants generated during the first wave. That wave ended during the Great Depression of 1929. Automakers were the main players, while Ford and Fiat were far ahead. In addition, in the second wave, the oil and gas industry has adjusted, as Standard Oil has shown by expanding its business to refining, retail and marketing by moving from horizontal to vertical integration.

1.1.3 Third wave (1955-1970)

The third wave of mergers and acquisitions in the United States introduced legislation that made it difficult for companies to integrate horizontally or vertically. As a result, because the acquirer encounters difficulties in managing new acquisitions, mergers and acquisitions with other unrelated companies can cause management problems and failures. When the third wave came, expansion and diversification became the main driving force for business decisions. When neither horizontal nor vertical integration can provide the solutions sought by these large companies, they turned their attention to corporate mergers and acquisitions. The desire of American companies to enter new markets and diversify their sources of income triggered this wave. Therefore, the holding

company and the corporate group met around. However, this situation did not last long, as the oil crisis intensified in the early 1970s and the fall in stock prices led to the end of the third wave.

1.1.3 Fourth Wave (1974-1989)

The US and UK governments have relaxed merger laws, which encouraged large-scale horizontal mergers and led to a significant reduction in competition among different industries, including petroleum and chemical production. During this period, underperforming companies were acquired due to low interest rates, which made acquisition financing relatively available. Despite the fact of friendly mergers, there have been more hostile acquisitions during this period than any previous wave of mergers. The fourth wave witnessed the arrival of corporate predators and became a common place for hostile acquisitions and similar mergers. During this period, investment banks played a more active role, and they were willing to spend a lot of cash to support their customers (corporate intruders) in active takeovers. This has also seen the emergence of new markets, one of which is the "junk" bond market. Here, bonds are issued to companies with weaker or lower credit quality. The end of the fourth wave was in 1989, when banks ended too many loans, too many times (high inflation also means that borrowing costs are too high, which is of no avail), and they cannot maintain their lending structure. capital. This situation was further exacerbated by the stock market crash in 1987, when many companies were forced to close their doors.

1.1.4 Fifth Wave (1993-2000)

This wave is characterized by the rapid growth of new technologies and new media including computers and the Internet. Despite the slow market growth, mergers and acquisitions enable companies to grow in these slow markets. During this period, hostile takeover activity has declined significantly, but at the same time, the company is also facing global competition due to the increasing pressure of prices, supply, and changes, creating an environment conducive to mergers and acquisitions. This wave is like the first wave of the railway network, because this wave is the result of a new technology that opened the national commodity market. This wave did not last long. It caused a huge sensation, but it was also bound by scandals related to the bankruptcy filings of big names such as WorldCom and Enron. The Internet bubble also burst, and a deal was reached.

The research of Alexandridis, Mavrovitis and Travlos (2012) shows that lower financing interest rates, higher cash items and the fact that the acquirer is undervalued relative to the 2004-2007

target make financing more obvious. Market competition was weaker, and managers were less optimistic. Compared with the latest wave of mergers and acquisitions, the premium involved in the offer has been greatly reduced, which undermines shareholder value and reduces returns.

1.1.5 Sixth Wave (From 2002 to onward)

From the burst of dotcom bubble, M&A activity increased to the level of \$3.4 trillion annually by 2006. (Nolan, Zhang and Liu, 2007). This boost in M&A activity was mainly because of factors such as globalization, rise in commodity prices, lower interest rates and shareholder activism. M&As through hedge fund, private equity funds such as leveraged buyouts (LBOs) were also among these factors which helped to reach higher M&As activity. This wave came to end because of banking crisis and recession of the US economy in 2008. Merger of AOL and Time Warner was one of the most popular mergers valued at US\$164 billion started before recession of 2008 although it reported \$100 billion losses one year after merger. Cash deals has significantly increased during this period which largely contributed to the economy crash. This was mainly because of target shareholders learned the lesson from dot-com bubble and followed “cash is king” philosophy to avoid being paid in overvalued stock (Buehlmaier and Zechner, 2012). AOL and Time Warner merger failure known as the “biggest mistake in corporate merger history”. Since the financial crises of 2008, it took about ten years for M&As deals to bounce back to pre-financial crisis position on average although deal value never seen quite recovered from this shock due to trade tensions between US and China. This time recovery in M&As activities was mainly due to the cooperation of BRICS (Brazil, Russia, India, China, and South Africa) countries. At the same time, the negative impact on M&A activities due to trade war and intense relationship between China and US which was challenging for the companies particularly larger deals, EY group leaders recorded that the larger deals announced at its lowest level since 2013 (Shames, 2019).

Following Britain’s exit from the EU, there has been some uncertainty on the conduct of merger control proceedings within European Commission under the EU Merger Regulation which would likely to end the concept of the one-stop-shop for merger control, increasing compliance costs and procedural times with UK's Competition and Markets Authority (CMA). According to some researchers, Brexit had very little impact on M&A deals as market bounced back within few weeks after some currency fluctuations. This could be because of M&A activities were slower prior to the EU referendum so its impact on M&As activates already factored in before referendum. Soon

after the Brexit, deal makers were following “wait and see” strategy due to uncertainty in market mentioned in survey conducted by Deloitte. Brexit has diverted the focus of UK and EU investors to look out for other markets such as US and China although they are more cautious than before (Macmillan, 2017) which has compensated the slower pace market due to Brexit.

COVID-19 has impacted the world’s economy significantly that forced businesses of all different sizes to shut down. Uncertainty in the market caused M&As deal activities to drop up to 30% because of COVID-19 concerns. However, there are active low-valued deals progressing which shows optimism which causing market to bounce back at a very slower pace (McLennan 2020). History suggests, we will still see trends and patterns that originally arose during the earlier waves soon Covid-19 crisis ends and M&As activities will start to flourish (Salsberg 2020). Governments and regulators are likely to be much more tolerant of M&As activities in many industries as their focus is on increased business activities which will boost economy and reduce unemployment rates. Among all other factors, there is consensus among analyst and investor that soon uncertainty dissipates, M&A activities tends to recover quickly.

1.2. Mergers & Acquisitions (M&A)

This section deals with the basic background details of M&A. It involves defining concepts, past market growth and current trends, as well as the overall transaction phase. In addition, a description of the reasons for transaction decisions will be illustrated, and the assessment of progress will be discussed in this study. Mergers and acquisitions (M&A) are transactions in which the ownership of firms or business organisations, or their operating units are transferred or combined so that they can grow by enlarging geographically, shrink, and change the nature of their business or competitive position. The main difference between a merger, acquisition or takeover lies in the way in which the combination of the two companies is brought about. The global compacting pushes businesses to grow exponentially, operate efficiently and effectively, be profitable and establish a competitively dominant position in the world. Consequently, mergers and acquisitions are inevitable for companies to pursue to restructure a more competitive growth business.

Figure 1.1 Types of Mergers & Acquisitions

1.2.1 Mergers

Merger is a broad term and denotes as combination of two or more companies into a single entity where one survives, and the others is dissolved. Usually there is a process of negotiation involved in merger between the two companies before any combination taking place. From the acquire point of view, merger is the least complex and cheap method of acquisition as it gives more clarity about the transaction to target firm's shareholders, more time to conduct the due diligence and issuing merger proxy statement instead of going through the tendering process for shares. Merger process can take significantly longer than acquisition process through tendering for shares and possibility of losing target firm during merger process (MachirajuH.R. 2007).

Merger can also bring about obvious potential synergies. If two firms may decide to initiate favourable merger negotiations, they can form new larger whole organisation as a result of merger. There are three basic types of merger vertical integration, horizontal integration, and conglomeration.

1.2.2 Amalgamation

Amalgamation is the combination or blending of one or more companies into a new entity. The companies may combine for diversification of activities or expansion of services. It is more common in India rather than USA. It is different from a merger as completely new company is formed after the combination of assets and liabilities of two or more companies and none of the combining companies survives. The shareholders of blending companies substantially become the shareholders of new company which holds blending companies.

1.2.3 Acquisitions

Acquisition refers to a situation where one firm acquires another, and latter may cease to exist. In contrast to the mergers, in an acquisition, the negotiation process does not necessarily take place. In the context of business combinations, an acquisition is the purchase of a controlling interest or majority shareholding of one existing company (referred as Target Firm) by another company (referred as Acquiring Firm). Acquiring companies totally absorbed the target firms and cease to exist as a separate entity or sometimes, acquiring company might retain Target Companying its pre-acquired form (Limited Absorption) with the intention to sell off at a profit in future.

The acquisitions can be friendly or hostile. In friendly acquisitions, the target firms see an opportunity to get access to investments, new resources or expand into new areas and willing to be acquired due to lack of capital or resources. Whereas in hostile acquisitions, target firms opposed to be acquired by acquiring firms and sometimes referred to hostile takeovers.

1.2.4 Takeover

In addition to traditional M&A where both firms willing or combine to merge and acquired through buying and selling of controlling interest and shares in market which is described as more amicable transaction. Takeover typically suggests that the target firm resists or opposes the purchase when acquiring firm making bid to acquire. In fact, there is no technical difference between an acquisition and a takeover and both words are often used interchangeably and carry slightly different connotations.

In any deal, shareholders decide to sell the shares and if all or majority shareholders agreed to sell the shares the ownership will substantially be transferred to the acquirer. Shareholders make their decision based on the recommendations from board of directors to assess if deal is profitable. The acquirers then offer either cash or own shares in exchange for target firm's shares. To avoid hostile takeover, the target firms find another company to merge or acquired by called white knight if it agrees to merger or takeover and rescue the threatened target firm.

1.3 Types of mergers and acquisitions

1.3.1 Vertical Integration

Production companies obtain supplies of goods or raw materials from a range of different suppliers and firms merge or acquire their suppliers to reduce the risk associated with its suppliers. Vertical integration is the process of manufacturers merging with suppliers or retailers and characterized by forward or backward integration along the supply chain. In forward integration (upstream activities), company acquire the distribution or retailer units or selling directly to customers, whereas in backward integration (downstream activities), firms acquire their suppliers of goods or raw materials.

Merging companies may not compete but exist in the same supply chain and may create synergy where aggregate value and performance of merging firms greater than the sum of separate individual firms. For example, an automobile company merging or acquiring a parts supplier which will allow automobile company to save costs and gain more control over the manufacturing process.

1.3.2 Horizontal Integration

In horizontal integration, acquiring firms acquire companies at the same level of value chain in similar or different sectors which allow them to share resources at that level. Firms seek to merge with companies in the same product line referred as the acquisition of a competitor. The goal is to create a new, larger firm with more market share because the operations of merging firms may be very similar and there may be opportunities and reduce costs by combining both operations.

For example, a merger between Coca-Cola and the Pepsi beverage division or an automobile distribution company acquires other company with distribution franchises for ranges of vehicles from other manufacturers would be horizontal merger in nature.

Producers of goods or service in market merge together cause creation of monopoly in the market whereas if there are still competitors available in the market after merger, it would be considered an oligopoly.

1.3.3 Conglomeration

Conglomeration is defined as the acquisition of unrelated companies operated in unrelated sectors or different geographical regions and has nothing in common. Conglomeration can be used by firms who seek to spread its business risk or create synergies between the firms. Merger of Walt Disney and American Broadcasting Company (ABC) is an example of conglomerate merger. Conglomerate merger can be risky as it can divert the focus from main business and time spends by management time with unfamiliar new products, services, and markets.

1.3.4 Product Extension Mergers

A merger between firms that deal in related products operating in the same market called congeneric or product extension merger. Product extension merger allows firms to get access to a bigger set of consumers together and increase their market share so that they can increase the profits.

Merger of Mobilink Telecom Inc. and Broadcom is an example of product extension merger where Mobilink Telecom Inc. deals in the manufacturing of product designs meant for mobile phones and high-speed wireless networking chips whereas Broadcom deals in the manufacturing MP3 and Bluetooth personal area network hardware systems which will enable Broadcom to leverage its peripheral handset offerings, including MP3 and Bluetooth chipsets as complementary products of Mobilink Telecom Inc.

1.3.5 Market Extension Mergers

This type of mergers takes place between two companies that deal in the same products but in separate markets. The main purpose of the market extension merger is to get access to a bigger market, thus, a bigger client base.

A very good example of market extension merger is the acquisition of Eagle Bancshares Inc in Atlanta by the RBC Centura in 2002. This move would allow RBC to diversify its base of operations and get access to deal in financial market of Atlanta, a leading financial market in the USA.

1.3.6 Reverse Merger

A type of the merger in which a private company acquires a public company so that it can avoid the process of an initial public offering (IPO) in stock market. Firms use reverse mergers to acquire the name of already established brand of public company.

1.4 Rationale behind mergers and acquisitions

There are many reasons why firms involve in mergers and acquisitions and according to literature; there are rationales and motivations which encourage firms to do so. Decision to merge or acquire is based on high level reasoning representing underlying conditions of decision is referred as rationales. Rationales determine the nature of proposed merger or acquisition, for example, a strategy implementation where companies seek to merge after experiencing over capacity in industry referred as strategic rationale.

1.4.1 Strategic rationale

The strategic rationale comprised of strategic objectives at strategic level in any organisation for example, to secure control of capacity in the industry or sector, enter new markets, increase market share or gaining competitive edge over competitors are example of strategic objectives. Others strategic objectives can be adding expertise, facilities, new product line or service capability, successful sales staff, intellectual properties or develop a research and development division in new markets to overtake established firms if firms cannot acquire any other companies in the market.

Sometimes firms also pressured by the activities of other firms in market to involve in mergers or acquisitions to defend themselves as a result of competition however this tends to happen when market is denominated by major players. For example, between 1995 and 2002, all major oil producers in the world were involved in mergers. These mergers were driven by a need to respond to the merger activities of competitors.

1.4.2 Speculative rationale.

The speculative rationale of companies is based on the idea that firms are commodities that can be used to make potential profit without major strategic alignment. To achieve this, companies acquire established firms; develop them in a view to sell them at profit in future. Another way is

to acquire a company and split them with intention to sell the major parts of them for a price higher than the aggregate or total value of acquisition.

This can be highly risky move if the target firm is vulnerable to environmental changes or having highly skilled employed who may want to leave during the process of mergers and acquisitions or as a result of market condition changes, diminish the value of target firm significantly in short period of time.

1.4.3 Business redefining rationale

Firms acquire or merger with target firm and aligned their business with based on the specialized skills of target firm referred as business redefinition. This happens as a result of major change in business model due to changes in mission and vision caused by environmental or technological changes. In such cases firms are unable to implement new technology immediately due to limited resources and seek to acquire or merge with innovative firms to redefine its business.

1.4.4 Political rationale

The changing politics all over the world increase the impact of the mergers and acquisitions. For example, Chinese government policy to increase in acquiring foreign companies result in 33 percent decline in outbound M&A volumes compared to past five years though regulatory controls on foreign exchange (Mckinsey, 2017). Similarly, banks in Australia were very aggressive in acquiring overseas bank as a result of government policy to avoid local mergers between themselves.

1.4.5 Management rationale

Sometimes companies are forced to do mergers or acquisitions because of management failures. These failures can be management's lack of expertise or personal interests. Managers can make mistakes when they make strategies or planning and as a result cause errors or expose risk to long term existence of business. It could be because of customers' demand changes during implementation stage and result in variance from its vision and goals. The firms seek to merge with other companies to adjust the variance and come back on the right track of the organisation.

1.4.6 Financial necessity rationale

Firms involve in mergers and acquisitions for reasons of financial necessity. A firm could make inappropriate decisions and as a result lose value and shareholders confidence. Therefore, firms look out for merger with successful companies.

1.4.7 Synergy and price

M&As deal failure rate is between 70 and 90 percent (Kenny, 2020). There are several motives behind every M&As deals and significant number of theories in M&As have explained this (Roll, 1986; Fama, 1980; Jensen, 1986; Shleifer and Vishny, 1989) however synergy gains as a result of value gains, costs reduction, efficient operations, and revenue growth in significant number of cases are overestimated (Ho, Brownen-Trinh and Xu, 2020) and overoptimizing (Amel-Zadeh, Evans, and Meeks, 2008) merger deals for shareholders to get their approval. Therefore, overpriced mergers over synergy have implications for the long-term performance and integration of both merging firms (Ismail, 2011). Significant number of mergers failed because of synergy although the price paid being far too high. The analysis demonstrated by Sirower (2006) where 131 deals between 1994 and 1997 in the United States, Europe, and Asia were investigated where most deals were failed due to synergy and overpriced and never created value for its shareholders. For example, Kenny (2020) investigated the case of Quadrant which were dealing in only printing material business line when its share price stood at a quarter of its original price since its inception. In order to deal with reducing share price and find more profit streams, company decided to diversify (through M&As) the business to add graphic design services. However, soon after the acquisition, management were facing challenges of integrating both businesses because of unable to synergise both cultures and units within the organisations. Stress, anxiety, lack of professional skills, unable to retain existing staff and poor customer service were major problems caused failure of merger. Finally, it was sold in 2019 when its price was less than a tenth of its floating price.

Synergy trap is where firms pay premiums over the price to acquire potential synergies where underlying motivation for M&As can be different as a result highly negative cumulative abnormal return after the acquisitions which caused by destruction in value as a result of synergy failure (Harford et al. 2012; Ismail, 2011). High price being paid by bidding firms were not aligned with estimated synergies between the firms as a result management may pay higher premiums because of lower revenue and interested in acquiring potential bigger operation and higher profits target firm seen as good investment opportunity for shareholders hence attracted overpayment. High

price being paid could also be because of management own personal interest of increased compensation as a result of M&As (Ismail, 2011). For successful M&As integration, synergies and related values must be assessed very carefully (Garzella and Fiorentino, 2004; Hitt et al., 2009), look for problems in synergy that could potentially affect synergy management (Gomes et al., 2012) and cause risks of synergy failure (Fiorentino and Garzella 2015) which can eventually result in integration failure if not managed appropriately.

1.5 Motives behind mergers and acquisitions

There are several motives behind the M &A as explained by Seth, Song, and Pettit (2002) suggesting that with clear understanding of this would contribute to its success. The first reason for a merger is to gain synergy between the two businesses or units leading to a competitive advantage (Porter, 1985). Other factor explained by Carpenter and Sanders (2007) and Seth, Song, and Pettit (2000) include materialism (self-interest). It is considering this that scholars such as Campbell and Goold (1998, p. 139), explored the term synergy and concluded that it a Greek Work that means working together. In business context, Synergy entails the ability of two or more firms producing greater value for businesses that could ideally function separately. Carpenter and Sanders (2007) explores five sources of synergy that include reduction in threats, enhanced market share, sharing of costs, better financial strength, and leverage in capacity. Another key motive of merger and acquisition is diversification, which was explored by Graham, Lemmon, & Wolf, 2002; Campa & Kedia, (2002) to mean enhanced efficacy in business approach.

Understanding of various motives of mergers and acquisitions is very important in developing the literature. Motives of mergers are middle or operational level influences that encourage or contributes towards the justification of firms involve in mergers and acquisitions. There are many rationales behind mergers and acquisition but according to dominant rational, firms involve in mergers and acquisitions activities because of motives behind improving their performance and reducing the risk as follows

Economies of scale: The idea behind economies of scale is to increase the profit margins as a result of increased demand by reducing the fixed cost in the way of combination the operations of two firms and removing the duplications in operations, processes, or departments etc.

Economies of scope: Firms involve in mergers and acquisitions to attain the efficiencies by achieving proportionate saving as a result of increase in demand side of their distinct products and services.

Increased power or market share: This strategy of M&A applies when a firm acquire or merge with its competitor to increase the market share and improving its overall power in market.

Cross-selling: A firm involve in M&A to sell its products to the customers of target firm and inevitably target firm can sell its product to acquiring firm's customers in order to increase their revenue and gain access to wider customer base.

Synergies: Firms acquire or merge with other firms to get access to specialized skills or workforce and to increase the effect of combined productions.

Taxation: A profitable firm acquire or merger with loss making firm to set off their tax liabilities however there are regulations in place to limit the companies to do so.

Stock markets: A stock market boom increase acquisition activity, alternatively a falling stock market can lead to potential targets being valued lower and become more target for buyers.

Diversification: A firm may want to diversify into new areas or sectors to diversity its risk portfolio.

Pressure from Industry: In the 1990s, major banks in UK and oil producer over the world merge as a result of merger wave in industry.

Capacity reduction: As a result of increased production a company to merge with or acquire a competitor in order to secure a greater degree of control over total sector output.

Management effectiveness and efficiency: A firm may have a deficit in management expertise, or it need to develop new skills for a new growth area seek to merger with other firm who have the skills.

Acquire a new market or segments: Firm merger or acquire other firms to get access to new market or increase the customer base by getting access to new customer segment. An example of one bank accessing domestic and business customers after mergers.

Access into a growing market: Firms involve in mergers or acquisitions to enter a proposed new market or sector with a view to expand in the future.

Resource transfer: Firms involves in M&A to take of advantage of the resources among the merging firms. According to Barney (1991), the resources are unevenly distributed across firms however firms' involvement in mergers and acquisitions can create value for these unevenly distributed resources by overcoming information asymmetry and sharing scarce resources (King, D. R.; Slotegraaf, R.; Kesner, I. 2008).

Absorption of similar businesses under single management: Companies often merge or acquire the similar line of businesses to manage the different business lines under one management instead of separate firms or managements for each business line. This helps firms to better administer or manage the similar business lines under the one umbrella. For example, absorbing currency exchange and international currency transfer into the one management of international currency exchange and transfer.

Hiring: Acquiring firms also target the small hiring start-up firms as opposed to internal recruitment department were acquiring firm simply hires the best talent of target firm as best talent hunt strategy.

Vertical integration: In vertical integration, a firm acquire or merger with upstream or downstream firm in order to increase their margins and reduce the monopoly of upstream or downstream firm. Firms increase their profitability as a result vertical integration (Maddigan, Ruth; Zaima, Janis, 1985).

Intellectual property Firms acquire or merger in order to get the access to intellectual property rights such as patent, copyrights, and trademarks to enable to produce certain goods.

To access assets: Firms involve in mergers and acquisitions to gain access to underperforming or non-performing assets to make them profitable to gain returns out of it.

Management own interest: It is also suggested that M&A deals are self-serving for top management for ego gratification ad career advancement (Donaldson ad Preston, 1995).

Internationalization: Firms involve in mergers and acquisitions to get access to international markets and as a growth strategy. Majority of mergers and acquisitions of firms involves

transactions within the same country whereas, in recent decade, one third of transactions recorded international mergers and acquisitions. (Shimizu et al., 2004; Dealogic, 2013). International mergers and acquisitions widely used by firms as growth strategy into new international markets for their products and services. Firms also use M&A as mode of entry into foreign markets and it is counted as 70 percent of foreign direct investment (FDI) worldwide therefore, M&A is the main channel use by international organisations for outward foreign direct investment (Bresman et al., 1999; UNCTD, 2000; Peng, 2009; Zander and Zander, 2010).

Economic growth: It is evident that in recent years, growing economies such as India and China have used mergers and acquisitions as their main strategy for international expansion (Luo and Tung, 2007; Sun et al., 2012) and China as the largest emerging economy with booming economic worth of \$ 87.8 billion in the world have achieved the enormous increase in outward FDI in past decade which is one third of world's overall outward foreign direct investment (United Nations Conference on Trade and Development – UNCTAD, 2013). One of the reason China is booming in outward FDI is because it has undertaken mergers and acquisitions transactions of worth 43.4 billion US dollars in 2012 which is the 49.4% of total proportion of total M&A worth of transactions in world (Xinhua, 2013).

Acquire specialist skills and resources: Firms develop highly specialized skills over number of years. Sometimes, it is very difficult for companies to do so and keen to acquire firm who have specific specialized skill or resources because it would take them a long time and a great deal of investment to develop such skills.

1.6 Problem statement

The reasons for high failure rates are many and vary according to factors affecting firms during integration process. Some of these major factors involving inappropriate managing strategy, Inadequate due diligence, difference in culture, delays in communications, employees dissatisfaction, emotions, weak planning, poor leadership, and lack of clear vision, false sense of security, misunderstanding value added, badly designed IT/IS, lack of management involvement, non-recognition of culture, inefficient processes, unable to understand employees emotions and psychology during change and badly managing the overall change. There are number of studies investigated the factors during integration phase however a comprehensive study is absent from the research which investigate factors that causing increased failure rate during integration phase

when firm involve in mergers and acquisition. Therefore, this study intended to develop a comprehensive integrative framework which will incorporate all the factors for successful integration when firms involve in mergers and acquisition.

1.7 Title

Human integration issues during post mergers and acquisitions:

A mix methodology approach in the study of successful mergers of humans

1.8 Research aim

Research's aim is to provide the recommendations on the factors that affect the humans during post mergers and acquisitions period which can cause failure to M&A integration between the firms. This research will investigate the factors involves merging culture, leadership, communication, emotions, IT/IS, HRM issues such as employees' satisfactions, turnover of key people, post-merger performance drops, and morale problems. Finally, study will develop conceptual integrative framework which will achieve the mergers and acquisitions goals incorporating the human factors affecting mergers of two firms.

1.9 Research questions

Based on research objectives and aim, relevant research questions can be developed. These relevant questions will be helpful in fulfilling research aim and objectives

- What is the nature of contextual and process-related factors causing failures or successes of mergers between the firms?
- What are the current and expected challenges and their effects on firms managing integration process during merger and acquisition period?
- How to evaluate the key determinants of systems and processes which will smoothen the process of mergers and acquisitions.
- What is the nature of comprehensive integrative framework involving mediating factors to determine the successful merger process?

- How developed integration framework will deal with the challenges during the process of merger and acquisition between the firms?
- What are the feasible recommendations for merging firms to maintain their operational proficiency during post-merger and acquisition period?

1.10 Research objectives

Research objectives are as follows:

- To determine the contextual and process-related factors causing failures or successes of mergers and acquisitions between the firms.
- To assess the challenges face by merging firms during post mergers and acquisitions period.
- To evaluate the key determinants of systems and processes affecting the merging firms during mergers and acquisition process.
- To develop the framework that involves mediating factors which will determine successful mergers and deal with challenges during mergers.
- To testify the framework by applying in mergers of firms in financial sector.
- To generate feasible recommendations for firms to maintain their operational proficiency during mergers and acquisition period.

Chapter 2- Literature Review

2.1 Chapter Overview

The continuous and tremendous development of a company depends on the increase in demand and expansion of the marketplace, this leads the company owners to look for the expanding aspect of the marketplace. This vision results them to formulate the strategies for acquiring their business rivals and competitors. From past few decades the mergers and acquisitions (M& A) is the central theme among the researchers who want to study the various aspects of the stages involved in the process of M&A. The studies involved coined the successful and unsuccessful mergers in terms of the further growth of the merged company and from the satisfaction level felt by the workers associated with the new evolved company.

The goal of this literature review is to compare various research, studies, and papers to extract the successes and failures (unsuccessful attempt) of the mergers and acquisitions deals. The prime focus is towards the negative effects (either economical, physical, and social) experienced by the humans involved within both merger and acquisition organisations. Firms experience leadership issues, cultural issues, change management, IT/IS issues, communications, HRM, key workers turnover, employee's emotional issues and job dissatisfaction. This will further play a crucial role in proposing a constructive framework for the successful mergers considering the human point of view in mind.

2.2 Mergers and acquisitions (M&A)

Mergers and acquisitions (M&A) are an important source for firms to grow as studied by Cartwright and Schoenberg (2006) stating that the phenomenon of mergers and acquisitions is prevailed since the end of 19th century and as a result firms gaining new capabilities and expanding in new areas. Since the recent economic recession where it had affected the mergers and acquisitions volume down from 4 Trillion US dollars in 2007 (Bloomberg, 2011).

However, there are number of studies documented that sixth mergers and acquisitions wave has already started (Bauer and Matzler, 2013) and reached 2.91 Trillion US dollars which is nine percent higher since the 2008 (Dealogic, 2013). Another study surveyed that in 2014, mergers and acquisitions volume reached about 1.2 Trillion US dollars which is 42% up as compared to the

previous years (Financial Times, 2014). Mergers and acquisitions (M&A) entail transactions that lead to transfer or combination altering the ownership pattern of entities, which might lead to enlargement or shrinking of business for greater competitiveness.

A difference between a merger, acquisition, and takeover is exhibited due to the approach used in combining the two entities. Merger is a broad term and denotes as combination of two or more companies into a single entity where one survives, and the others is dissolved. Usually there is a process of negotiation involved in merger between the two companies before any combination taking place. From the acquire point of view, merger is the least complex and cheap method of acquisition as it gives more clarity about the transaction to target firm's shareholders, more time to conduct the due diligence and issuing merger proxy statement instead of going through the tendering process for shares. Merger process can take significantly longer than acquisition process through tendering for shares and possibility of losing target firm during merger process (Machiraju H.R. 2007).

2.2.1 Types of mergers and acquisitions

The M&A involves two companies (the acquirer), which is the buying firm with majority shareholding, and the (target), which is the acquired firm or business unit (Ahern & Weston, 2007). In instances where one company has the majority shareholding, it is considered as an acquisition, which is different from a merger where the two companies have equal ownership. In some instances, some people use the two terms interchangeably, but they are distinct with acquisition meaning a complete takeover. Some managers also use the term merger to alleviate fears that comes with a complete takeover. In such instances, it is imperative to ensure that a complete elucidation and details of the combination are outlined as there are variations between M&A (Søderberg & Vaara, 2003). Other than mergers and acquisitions, other forms of entities engagement also exist such as takeover, buyout, and divestments, with each exhibiting unique feature, motivation, as well as challenges (Teerikangas, Joseph, & Faulkner, 2012). The Merger and acquisitions (M&As) are often classified as horizontal, vertical, and conglomerates.

2.2.1.1 Horizontal merger entails a combination of two firms that deal with the same commodity and operating under the same region. An example of this is the ArcelorMittal, two firms that operate under the steel industry. A further classic example of horizontal integration is the merger

between Daimler-Benz and Chrysler. The primary aim of a horizontal merger is to improve the market share and help the two firms enjoy from economies of scale. Indeed, through this merger, there is a spread of the fixed costs and elimination of redundant costs as well as assets. Companies involved in the merger achieve this by spreading the fixed costs over higher revenues stream thereby also covering the redundant costs. The primary disadvantage of this is that the arrangement is devoid of the in competitive considerations.

There are two methods of mergers: market extension fusion and product extension merge. The market extension merger increases as well as expands the product lines that are offered to the market. In other words, companies manufacture the same products in different geographic markets. The merging companies will gain access to a larger industry and customer base by business growth merger. An example of a merger of market extension would be RBC Central acquiring Eagle Bancshares Inc. RBC diversified its activities by entering the Atlanta financial market. (*“Wealth Creation in the World’s Largest Mergers and Acquisitions.”* Management for Professionals Kumar, B. R. (2019).

2.2.1.2. A vertical merger entails a combination where a relationship is developed between one buyer and a seller. This is necessitated by the fact that the two entities operate in the same supply chain of the industry but under varying segments. The two companies could be dealing with varying products, but they get connected by the same product that they make. An example is the Turner Corporation and AOL–Time Warner's Time Warner acquisition Vertical mergers, which resulted to greater synergy. Vertical acquisition companies are distinguished by activities at various stages of the value chain or work at various stages of the value chain. Hence these organisations have very different resource sets and capabilities. Vertical mergers are intended to reduce the reliance on suppliers and purchasers. Such method of mergers lowers the risk of suppliers and increases efficiencies. The acquisition of Pizza Hut, and Taco Bell together with KFC is an example of vertical merger as quoted among the world largest mergers and Acquisition by Kumar (2019).

2.2.1.3. Conglomerate mergers are mergers between two firms which have completely unrelated business activities. The merger of The Walt Disney Company and American Broadcasting Company is an example of a merger of the conglomerates. Conglomerate mergers exploit the acquirer firm's financial strength. The tobacco company Philip Morris purchased General Foods

for \$5.6 billion in the year 1985. Economic synergy is the fundamental reason for conglomerate mergers.

A pure merger arrangement occurs where a company that has low demand and growth is acquired by another that is projected to have high growth and demand. The acquiring company uses the internal funds for financing its investment opportunities leading to a reduction in capital costs. In instance where the two companies do not have a perfect correlating cash flow, there is a reduction in the likelihood in bankruptcy. Risk for lenders may be reduced, and debt capacity may be increased. (“*Wealth Creation in the World’s Largest Mergers and Acquisitions.*” Management for Professionals Kumar, B. R. (2019).

2.2.1.4. Congeneric merger occurs where the combining firms under the same industry have no relationship in the buying and selling, for instance a combination between a bank and a leading firm. This was witnessed by the acquisition of Bache & Company acquisition by Prudential. Reverse mergers are widening product lines and markets. Reverse merger means a weaker or smaller corporation purchasing a bigger one. Reverse merger often entails a parent company being integrated into its subsidiary or a loss-making business being absorbed from a profit-making company. A reverse merger also happens when a private company acquires ownership of the public company to become a public company. Armand Hammer into Occidental Petroleum and Ted Turner with Rice Broadcasting to form Turner Broadcasting are two examples of a reverse mergers, which were also captured under the World Largest M & A by Kumar (2019).

2.3 Phases of mergers and acquisitions

Different studies documented the stages of mergers and acquisitions. According to Marks and Mirvis (1998) there are three phases for M&A, pre-combination, combination, and post-combination. The M&A process was divided into two phases by Boland (1970) i.e., pre-merger and post-merger. Schweiger and Weber (1989) divided the cycle into premerger and execution while the process was divided into three stages by Salus (1989) i.e., pre-merger, merger, and post-merger. The method was organized into three phases by Appelbaum et al. (2000b), Pre-merger, during the merger and post-merger. According to Carpenter and Sanders (2007), there are four phases of the merger: concept, rationale (including due diligence and negotiation), integration of mergers and acquisitions and assessment of outcomes. Vance, Fery, Odell, Marks, and Loomba (1969) documented that there are four stages; the first stage of mergers and acquisition is courtship

where both firms discussed their prospective management philosophies, policies, objectives, and strategies (p. 156). The second stage of mergers and acquisition is marriage ceremony which should involve inviting the key management such as board members of both companies get together so that mergers and acquisition can be announced and any reasons behind the M&As to the board members so that they can understand why company is involving in M&A with a particular organisation (Belisle & Hoveven, 2000a). Following the board meeting, an announcement should be made to the remaining employees and to the public about both companies involved in M&A. (p. 156).), The third stage is the honeymoon stage which involve starting the integration process of merging and integration of both firms. Communication at this is should be taken very important at this stage and there should be two-way communication between both firms going to involve in M&A. Vance, Fery, Odell, Marks, and Loomba (1969) explain that the merger was termed as the adjustment phase where the two companies tied the ribbon, and a philosophical infusion was affected (p. 159).) Every study has their own philosophy behind M&A and based on that suggesting distinctive stages for M&As which for them is best way to explain the stages of M&A. However, M&A is multidisciplinary field and each firm involved different factors which are different from other firms. Every firm have their own way of doing things such as culture, leadership, communication, processes, structures, HRM and IT/IS systems. Therefore, explaining M&A in stages will be narrowing down the process and possibility of missing the important factors which can be explained in more detail rather than categorizing them under stages. Kazemek and Grauman (1989) have seven stages of the process: assessment, collaborative preparation, and review of the problems, selection of systems, obtaining permissions, final planning, and implementation. Parenteau and Weston (2003) elucidates on four phases of the M&A process: strategy planning, screening of candidates, due diligence and execution of deals, and the ultimate integration phase.

2.3.1 Pre-combination phase

Pre-combination is considered as the most challenging phase in M&A as it is the most complex and challenging stage of managing M & A. At this phase merger or acquisition has just been announced and acquiring firms enter into puzzle and wait for the regulatory approvals. Very little information shared at this stage due to legal concerns which creates the uncertainty and ambiguity among the members of firms. Due to insufficient information, it is very difficult to prepare high-

level integration plan. Often firms not sure about the restructuring and HRM issues which cause anxiety and fear among employees.

2.3.2 Combination phase

At this stage, both firms start day to day activities to integrate with each other. It is the implementation phase of organisational architecture which is planned at pre combination phase and organisation's strategy clarification and appropriate goals are put in place. At this phase key functions of whole organisation are set up at micro level which includes integration of financial, HR and IT as well as work process integration, role clarification and policy setting. At this phase, firms know the roadmap and know the philosophy of the putting the new organisation together. The integration challenges between both firms and factors affecting integration at this stage face by firms such as cultural and system differences between the integrating firms.

2.3.3 Post-combination phase

This is the final and most lasting phase of mergers and acquisitions where firms ensure that all systems and processes have been integrated and new firm is having a clear roadmap of continuous improvement. The firms should ensure that its members have the right tools and information to perform efficiently.

2.4 Reasons for successful mergers

The extent of success in a merger or acquisition's is typically measured on the finance and accounting criteria (e.g., Hoskisson et al., 1994) or the accomplishment of a premeditated objective (e.g., Clarke, 1987). Larsson and Finkelstein (1999) gave additional functional perspectives for evaluating the outcome of a merger. If we keep organisational economics under consideration, the M & A is termed as the prime reason to promote organisational growth and interaction between the organisations. Cartwright and Schoenberg (2006) contend in a report that our present state of M&A knowledge seems to be incomplete. Cartwright and Schoenberg (2006) did not focus on adding another piece to the M & A puzzle, but the aim was to examine and explore the common variables that are commonly cited in literature such as (Gadiesh and Ormiston, 2002) as factors determining the success or failure of M & A thereby provide structure for enthusiastic managers for them to concentrate on their efforts. King et al. (2004) defined four factors that moderated the

performance of an acquisition-whether the business was a corporation, whether the transaction was associated or discrete, and whether the payment method was cash or equity.

There's no magic formula for making successful acquisitions. These are not inherently good or bad like any other business process, just like marketing and R&D are not. Each deal needs to have its own strategic rationale. Throughout our experience, acquirers have unique, well-articulated value creation ideas going into the most effective transactions. The strategic rationales – such as seeking an international scope, filling portfolio gaps, or constructing a third stage of the portfolio – appear to be ambiguous for less effective transactions. A merger between a firm that is bureaucratic and another that is adhocracy based would increase the need for better adjustments making the merger a difficult affair. In such an arrangement, there is a need for additional changes and adjustments that would make the process seamless for a better success of the deal.

2.4.1 Strategic Move

It is crucial & consider it as a prime point under consideration that the M&A motivation is strategic, without which the acquisition is probably not consistent with the capabilities and objectives of the organisation. A company needs to consider its own competitive standing, strengths and weaknesses and the expectations and competencies of top management while determining its goals (Mirvis & Marks, 1992). Kitching (1967) concluded that managers apply two approaches for their M&A: "golf course", which depicts the approach where the management utilizes the opportunity that could arise in a serendipitous manner and ' ' crystal ball "approach depicting the fact that the management looks at this strategically to help in decision making with the overall corporate strategy in mind.

Levinson (1970) recommended the possibility of two psychological factors for M&A: "fear", which means that merger stems out of the belief that, if the company does not grow, it will be ruined by bigger companies & "obsolescence" means the attempt to renew mergers – as companies like elderly persons get stereotyped in their practices because of their limited ability to adapt to changing conditions and limited agility in their attempts to cope with their environments. The approaches with acquisitiveness and hubris described by Seth et al. (2000), it is critical that M&A start with a logic that creates value that is compatible with the corporate approach.

2.4.2 Diversification and Relatedness

Another point keeping in mind during M & A is to check the type of the company i.e., the sector of both the companies. It seems obvious that target companies that are more closely related to an acquiring company, it should be more effective and perform better. There is a presumption that when the learning curve becomes steeper, there are greater chances of getting success while also having industry knowledge. As such, companies should apply a diversification strategy by following similar companies thereby minimize risk (Lubatkin & Chatterjee, 1994). Through diversification, companies can enjoy greater economies of scale leading to higher productivity and ultimately lead to competitive advantage in the long run (Shelton, 1988; Markides and Williamson, 1994; Brush, 1996). Indeed, with greater synergies, it is possible to have higher market power, improve administrative efficacies as well as reduction in capital costs (Chatterjee, 1986). In general, most companies prefer unrelated acquisitions (Hayward, 2002) and the diversification associated is more profitable (Park, 2003).

2.4.3 Selection Criteria

Selection criteria is the criteria for choosing prospective merger partners that are decided by the search team of the acquiring firm. The decision on the parameters is important because it allows the firm to be objective and not be swayed by feelings or respond impulsively (Kitching, 1967). Successful corporate leaders choose strategic requirements to support the search team in choosing suitable candidates by consensus (Mirvis & Marks, 1992). The points taken under consideration during the selection are Price and strategically suit, which are described as:

2.4.3.1. Price

Price paid for the acquired firm is generally considered as the success criterion (Kitching, 1967). Smith (1997) found there was little connection between price premiums and whether value was generated by the offer.

2.4.3.2. Strategic compatibility

The other primary selection criteria are strategic compatibility, it is “the degree to which the target firm augments or complements the parent’s strategy and thus makes identifiable contributions to the financial and nonfinancial goals of the parent”. The strategic fit is the synergy that leads to competitive advantage, where one firm gains due to strategic compatibility of the acquiring

company resulting to competitive strength and market growth (Weber & Power, 1989; Lubatkin (1983).

2.4.4 Human Resource Management

It is important that HR managers must be involved as early as possible in the M&A process (Mirvis & Marks, 1992). For keeping the human prospect and issues in the plan, the HR management must be merged in the plan for the successful execution of the plan. The basic amenities and needs of humans (labours) associated with the organisation are must for example Motivation, can be essential to handling post-merger integration. Furthermore, there is a need for the two companies involved to conduct job grading, training, assess the performance management, career development, salaries review as well as other HR management issues (Mirvis & Marks, 1992). On the same note, Schweiger et al. (1989) explored human resource aspects on 80 entities, with a focus on 15 HR factors that need to be addressed during an M & A. For instance, the issue of compensation arrangement and agreement between the employee and the management should be considered. From this study, it was evident that there are many HR issues that need HR attention for the company success.

Despite the dire need for due diligence in HR division during and after the M&A process, a study conducted by the year 2000, only 39% of the companies get involved in this important process but the number had increased to 62% by the year 2005 (Brown, 2005). The strategic HRM literature focuses on aligning HRM and business strategy (Fombrun et al., 1984; Schuler and Jackson, 1987). Strategy is a dominant force and there is a fit between strategy, structure and HRM (Fombrun and colleagues, 1984). Firms who change their strategies would change HRM practices (Schuler and Jackson, 1987). Similarly, Sanz-Valle and colleagues (1999) studied Spanish companies and find a link between business strategy and HRM practices. In contrast, for successful integration, HRM strategies need to be aligned with business strategy and consider the fit between M&A and HRM strategies. To understand the HRM challenges related to M & A, there is a need to engage in conceptual tools of resources, processes as well as the company values as they differ in different M&A contexts (Bower, 2001). Resources are defined and divided into tangible (People and money) and intangible assets (brands, customer loyalty and relationships).

In HRM context, resources considered as employees, their contracts, and retention and termination issues during merger and acquisitions process. Processes referred as activities to convert firm's resources into goods and services. In HRM strategic context, it would be employees training and development to cope with skills shortage during M&A. Finally, the most important thing that people would do are the values. Values are the values backed by their culture or religion. Values influence the way employees take the decisions and how to react to any phenomenon. There are studies which provide the relationship and identify the appropriate relationship between HRM strategies and M&As and strategies within M&As. For instance, Bower (2001) provide the in-depth analysis and finds the relationship and fit between HRM strategies and M&As strategies. He used the framework which he includes the practices of processes, resources and values incorporated in the framework.

Link of M&A and HRM strategies

Firms undertake different M&A strategies to gain competitive advantage such as horizontal, vertical, product extension, market extension and unrelated M&As (Federal Trade Commission, 1975). This typology of M&As strategies developed in 1970s to study the M&A process (Buono and Bowditch, 1989). However, during 1990s, new forms of M&A strategies including cross-borders M&As were adopted by firms (Bower, 2001). To explore resources, processes and values and the link HRM strategies with M&As, Bower (2001) proposes five distinct M&A strategies:

- a) Overcapacity M&A
- b) Geographic roll-up M&A
- c) Product or market extension M&A
- d) M&A as R&D
- e) Industry convergence M&A.

a) An overcapacity M&A

In overcapacity M&A, firms seek to eliminate excess capacity to create a more efficient corporation by eliminating or reducing the functions of human resources by creating the efficient resources without compromising the quality. This type of M&A can be seen happening in oligopolistic industries where firms of similar size and capacity involve in M&A to create the efficient structures and processes. For instance, the acquisition of the British Petroleum by Amoco and Daimler by Chrysler is a case of the company in the same industry but operating under the

same size. Processes and values of merging firms are frequently similar however relative status differences can create problems in M&A integration.

b) Geographic roll-up M&A

This takes place when firms go global to expand its operations. Large companies acquire smaller companies to retain local managers which can be experienced in the banking sector such as Banc One's acquisitions of several regional banks. Mostly firms acquire at an earlier stage in an industry's lifecycle. International M&A are designed to achieve economies of scale (Bower, 2001: 98), while overcapacity M&As mainly focus on reducing the duplication within the processes and the different departments of the organisations. HR are less disposable, and they tend to differ between companies in relation to overcapacity. Finally, status differences can cause problems in integrations however it is not as prevalent as in the overcapacity M&A.

c) A product or market extension M&A

This type of M&As involves expanding product lines locally or internationally where both firms are functionally related in production and/or distribution, or when a firm seeks to diversify. The success is depending on the local knowledge about customers, market conditions, legal framework, relative size, and the experience of the acquired firm in M&As. In this type of M&A, particularly international M&As, there are many factors involved such different culture, leadership styles and values of the employees and due to these factors' companies having difficulties in changing the processes and values of target firms. For instance, M&S (Marks & Spencer) having problems in relation to its distribution network where were having extension geographically and due to that M&S was having difficulties in acquiring Canadian firm PDS (Peoples Department Stores) (Bower, 2001). In contrast, General Electric company which acquired Nuovo Pignone an Italian engine producing company where GE shared its resources to develop business and introduced its systems and processes over the period sequentially and slowly so that it can understand its processes and less disruptions can happen (Bower, 2001).

d) M&A as a substitute for R&D

Rather than producing the knowledge in-house, firms acquire innovative firms so that they can acquire R&D knowledge; firms ideally be spending lot of resources on the R&D of new projects, new technologies, new products to advance their technological capabilities (Granstrand and

Sjolander, 1990). Acquiring firms needs enormous resources therefore it is inevitable to be bigger than the target firm they going to acquire. It is also evident that these firms have experience or trading in the same business line. For example, acquiring firms in manufacturing industry, would likely to acquire the software developing firms. The success depends on the ability of the two firms to get integrated and the ability of the acquiring firm to learn and enhance the capacity. Retention of human resources and knowledge is a paramount goal in this type of M&A. Processes and values of new firm will need to be changed in these types of M&As which could become challenge for the acquiring firm as target firm's employees feel their values are constrained or blocked by the new management structure. Integration issues can become complex, and they are industry contingent. For instance, firms in IT industry need rapid integration as compare to firms in pharmaceutical industry because under this industry, the product development cycle significantly shorter in information technology (IT) firms than that of the pharmaceutical firms.

e) An industry convergence

M&A also moving towards the convergence of the industry, such as media and telecom sectors will involve significant convergence. Similarly, mergers and acquisitions of Viacom acquisition of Paramount and Blockbuster taking industries to the next level which can cause the contractions within the industries. Industry have already experienced convergence as technology continues to disrupt and changing many business structures and creating a new industry from existing industries which is eroding its boundaries there, making it difficult to assess the analyse full business structures due to complexities. We are moving towards the M&As as substitution for R&D which can shift the focus towards the wrong direction.

2.4.5 Operating Managers and Key Staff People

While contemplating the involvement of managers and key management staff in the M&A process, it is important to remember that the day-to-day information that operational managers and key staff need to run the company. We are the ones who conduct the decision to purchase. Their presence in the pre-stage will make a huge contribution not only to the implementation's nuts and bolts but also to their overall dedication to the future fused organisation (Drucker, 1981; Searby, 1969).

2.4.6 Culture

Many studies have emphasized that focusing cultural differences and efficient integration policies in relation to culture are very important for the accomplishment after the post merge integration (Stahl, Mendenhall, & Weber, 2005; Shimizu et al., 2004). But Stahl and Voight (2008) outline the unclear and complex relationship that exists between corporate and national culture as well as integration of the merging firms, which can negatively affect the success of M & A and ultimately affect the infusion for success. In addition, Schoenberg, 2006; Teerikangas & Very, 2006) predicts that the results of empirical studies often contradict one another. Cultural differences can cause great challenges for merging firms which can badly affect the integration and result in higher cost of mergers and acquisitions (Brock, 2005; Cartwright & Price, 2003). In general, national cultural differences are often cited as complicated business transactions (Hofstede, 1980) which can cause integration problems and as a result failure of M&A (Li & Guisinger, 1991). Mayrhofer (2004) illustrates how national culture can badly affect the previous M&A choices. Brock, Barry, and Thomas (2000) show how cultural differences have more powerful effects from parent company towards its subsidiary companies' direction than vice versa and illustrate how linguistic differences can result in impeding the understanding between the units of both parent and subsidiary companies. Appelbaum et al. (2000b), in the pre-stage, the decision on which the used organisational culture model must be decided.

The cultural dimension offers a complementary study dimension regarding strategic as well as people's dimension regarding acquisitions. The research starts from the case study of Sales and Mirvis (1984) identified the cultural factors in acquisitions causes resistance to change whereas, Buono et al. (1985) focuses on combining different organisational cultures. Cultural research on mergers and acquisitions extended to identity and culture (Zaheer et al., 2003), employees understanding on integration process (Risberg, 2001), linking culture with knowledge transfer (Hasegawa, 2000) and with value creation (Blasko, Netter, and Sinkey, 2000). Napier, Schweiger, and Kosglow (1993) focused on research managing cultural diversity and its importance in foreign acquisitions and Olie (1994) (2005) concluded in case studies that different national cultures increased integration problems. Furthermore, Nummela (2005) provided versatility of integration of international firms from cultural perspective, case study on national and organisational cultures explored by Santti (2001) and mergers and acquisitions failure due to close cultures analysed by Fang, Fridh, and Schultzberg (2004). Additionally, Schoenberg, (2004) and Slangen (2006) focused on national cultural differences whereas Weber et al. (1996) and Weber & Camerer (2003)

focused on organisational cultural differences. Very, Lubatkin, Calori, & Veiga (1997) focused on acculturation process, cultural integration (Kavanagh & Ashkanasy, 2006), and cultural learning (Schweiger & Goulet, 2005). Bresman, Birkinshaw, and Nobel (1999) focused on the knowledge transfer and identified national cultural distance that caused misunderstandings between individuals in international acquisitions. Birkinshaw et al. (2000) investigate and identified the mechanism for mutual respect within the dynamics of cultural convergence and mutual respect and importance of human integration. Finally, Studies by Riad, (2005) and Vaara & Tienari, (2003) provided in depth analysis of cognitive challenges and stereotyping within the merging firms contributed to cultural dimension and cultural difference.

2.4.7 Size Difference

Size difference of the acquired and acquiring company may represent lack of empathy as well as misunderstanding especially if the companies have vast size difference. Common result of the size differences includes disparities in purchasing power and lack of knowledge on management of businesses. Brockhaus (1975, p. 44) defines size disparities as *“a situation in which the sales of one firm are less than two percent of the sales of the other.”* Further they figure out that, according to this definition, 84 per cent of the mergers deemed failures since the Second World War were size mismatches.

Bruton et al. (1994) performed a hypothesis which is based on a seven Likert scale (1- unsuccessful and 7 – successful). For these 817 firms were taken under considerations which are acquired between 1979 & 1987 (in which 32 acquisitions were eliminated due to many loopholes associated). The comparison in terms of size is measured based on the acquired firm’s revenue against the acquiring firms. The company’s performance is measured on subjective measures, which were created and compromised of academic evaluations for three university facilities. Kitching (1967, p. 92) concluded that there is no impact of relative size on the performance acquisition as there is a lack of influence on the management. From this study, size mismatch can be addressed if the acquiring firm has an appropriate organisation and reporting structure.

2.4.8 Organisational Structure

Proposed organisational structure should be planned and decided in early stage of M&A process and it must be an integral part of corporate level and organisational level policies (Brockhaus,

1975). Both merging firms should have the idea and plans in place of both firms' structure after mergers and acquisition decision is being made including how the business should be conducted and organized in post-merger process. For example, the degree of centralizations and decentralization should be discussed, and power and board structure should be decided. Many M&As failed due to having appropriate board and organisational structure in place and as a result employee of the firm unwilling to accept the new board structure which caused resistance and as a result board structured replaced in mergers of UK and USA jet airlines. Centralized structure can cause frustration among employees and create major difference between top leadership and rest of the employees (Young & Tavares, 2004). Acquiring firm's employees should remain work in their existing operating patterns which can eliminates uncertainty between the acquired firm which should operates independently. The firms should not drastically make any changes to the organisational structure until employees are settled with the new acquiring firm. Boland (1970) found that 42 per cent of executives considered the organisational structure's compatibility.

2.4.9 Control System

One structure-related issue is hold in control. In occasion where there are differences in control system, the merging companies may witness dysfunctional reporting, which needs to be resolved through an M & A process in order to avert misunderstanding in future. Issues that are commonly explored by scholars that relate to control systems include companies where one is applied bureaucracy and the other one is adhocracy based leading to problems (Mirvis & Marks, 1992, p. 72). A case study is the issue where HP acquired Apollo, where the latter was managed by a close-knit team contrary to HP.

2.4.10 Analysis of Future Capital Need

It is paramount to ensure that there is no underestimation of the investment as well as other capital needs for the acquired company before signing of the engagement (Kitching, 1967). Anything missing or neglected specially at this level can later results in major financial hardships.

2.4.11 Ambiguity

By the end of the due diligence process, parties in an M & A can obtain answers eliminate substantial ambiguity and avoid any misunderstanding between them for a successful combination

(Jemison & Sitkin, 1986). The persistence of the ambiguity to the stage of integration will lead to serious misunderstandings. The effect of ambiguity on investment decisions is quite different from that of risk. Any investor should spend more as the risk increases, as the higher risk increases the opportunity for upside and option value. Nonetheless, an uncertain investor intuitively overweights the probability of bad results and underweights the likelihood of good results (e.g., Tversky and Kahneman, 1992, Izhakian, 2017). It is imperative to eliminate higher levels of ambiguity as they reduce the perceived attractiveness of the parties in developing the intended investment opportunities as well as negatively affecting the investment decisions.

The significant negative effect of ambiguity on innovation measures at different stages of product development including investment in R&D and patents. These findings are consistent with our stylized model and are also consistent with Herron and Izhakian (2017), who demonstrate that ambiguity is important for firm pay-out policy. Izhakian's (2017) expected utility with uncertain probabilities (EUUP) paradigm introduces outcome-independent uncertainty preferences that allow us to differentiate risk and ambiguity definitions and define different preferences for both. Essentially, EUUP helps us to assess uncertainty independently of risk and risk attitude (Izhakian, 2018).

2.4.12 Leadership

The recent studies in M&A have pointed out that there is little known about the integration process and its effects on M&A success Haleblian et al. (2009). Specifically, the role of leadership is neglected in M&A literature, however, Sitkin and Pablo (2005) disagree by stating that studies on importance of leadership were provided in abundance but there is insufficient evidence about the how leadership influence the M&A outcome and what actually the M&A leadership is? M&As reshape the organisations and affects the employees involved in mergers therefore understanding the role of leadership is important in M&As.

According to Yukl, (2012) the role of leadership is very important in achieving the shared goals of M&A and during the process of integration, M&A leadership is steering up the efforts of organisational members toward achieving mutual goals. Junni and Sarala (2014) worked on the studies published between 2000 and 2013 and evident that the M&A leadership not being studied in terms of M&As effects on different levels and its outcomes measures (acquirer vs. target, higher

vs. lower organisational levels, different organisational functions or units, teams vs. individuals). They have stated that most studies focused on behavioural aspect of leadership of acquiring firms rather than targeted firms' leaders. Also missing focus on leadership behaviour in post mergers rather than pre-M&A stage and interactions between both leaders before and after M&As.

Furthermore, they have highlighted the gap in literature of identifying leadership for M&A and their dynamic aspects at each level of organisations. Finally, very few studies examined M&A leadership traits, M&A leadership contingencies, and power and politics in M&A leadership thus lack of a comprehensive study which combines several theoretical perspectives. Although studies recognized that the mergers and acquisitions failed to live up to their potential (Larsson and Finkelstein, 1999), the role of effective leadership on M&As have not been well articulated or studied and in fact the role of leaders has been ignored in M&As success or failure by scholars (Stahl, G., 2010). Richard M. (2002) evidenced that, a systematic approach needs to be followed to increase the success rates of mergers and acquisitions. He further states that any mergers involve significant change within the organisation and leadership is one of the first factor that contribute towards the successful change, therefore leadership is critical to the success of mergers and acquisitions.

In mergers cases of BP & AMACO and Chrysler & Daimler Benz, it is evident that to integrate effectively leadership is key role at many levels of organisation supported by the views of Heskett and Kotter (1992) and Kotter (1996) which suggests for change to be persistent, there must be leadership at many levels of organisations during mergers. Therefore, it is becoming increasingly clear that post mergers and acquisitions performance is strongly affected by leadership to achieve the integration (Waldman and Javidan, 2009).

2.4.13 Emotions

Although the emotions are covered in literature of M&A, its existence is only fraction as compared to the overall research on human side in M&As. Graebner et al., (2017) called for attention to emotions in M& A studies. Influence of emotions are characterized by the effects of socio-cultural processes and therefore can support or cause failure to M&A process (Brundin & Liu, 2015). Emotions determines the attitudes and behaviours of members in the process of M&As. Positive emotions have positive effects on M&A process, for example, positive emotions can increase

motivation for employees which can help employees to regulate their feelings (Kusstascher & Cooper, 2005), so that positive emotions can increase the job satisfaction and their commitment with the firms which can lead to successful M&As (Kusstascher, 2006) however, negative emotions lead towards fear, anger and frustration which ultimately can reduce the level of employees satisfaction and their commitment with their firm can be reduced (Mottola, Bachman, Gartner, & Dovidio, 1997) and finally, withdrawal (Kiefer, 2005) which can affect negatively on merger process and as a result this can have negative Impact on the success of M&As (Giessner, Viki, Otten, Terry, & Täuber, 2006). As a result, shifting the focus from actual problems to less constructive activities of emotion coping mechanisms. (Scheck & Kinicki, 2000). Additionally, emotions determine social identifications such as positive emotions improve organisational identity and enhance the relationships among themselves and with other firms (Kusstascher, 2006).

In contrast, negative emotions harm organisational identity (Ford & Harding, 2003), trust (Kiefer, 2005), cooperation (Sinkovics, Zagelmeyer, & Kusstatscher, 2011) and lead to social conflict (Saunders, Altinay, & Riordan, 2009). Therefore, employees' actions and behaviours can be determined by emotions as essential socio-cultural mechanisms as well as the extent to which members identify themselves with socio-cultural structures and engage in social relationships (Turner & Stets, 2005). Furthermore, M&A research link positive outcome with positive emotions and vice versa however these can be more complex. For instance, positive emotions can also increase false optimism, reduces the quality of decisions by creating illusion of control and encourage the reliance on simple rules, however negative emotions can induce criticality which improve the decision making (Rhee & Yoon, 2012). Overall negative emotions are not good for the firms involved in M&As specially when the intense dealings going on between the firms. Therefore, there is a need to explore more about the negative and positive emotions and its complex outcomes as literature do not give the full how negative emotions can be regulated which can benefit within the area of M&As (Sarala, Vaara and Junni, 2017). There is need to identify the determinants of emotions to understand its role in M&A. M&A is a major strategic process that involve intense emotions (Brundin & Liu, 2015) and as a result member experience different emotion among themselves.

To understand how emotion evolves, appraisal theory explains how socio-cultural effects can impact the emotions and exploring the factors that explains how socio-cultural of employees can affect the emergence and development of different emotions during M&A process (Lazarus, 1984; Strongman, 1996). It provides the discussion of where the emotions can be originated and how emotions are generated and what is the role of critical evaluations of appropriateness, valence, and efficacy to develop the emotions. Appropriateness involves to which extent firm's current strategy will advance as a result of M&A (Armenakis, Harris, & Feild, 1999; Harris & Gresch, 2010). Having the perceived validity is about the motives of firms involving in M&A and its effects on the appropriateness of the advancements of the firm's strategy.

Secondly, valence characterized by attractiveness or the goddness of the firm and expectations about the real outcome of firm and its members as a result of M&A (Armenakis et al., 1999; Harris & Gresch, 2010). Valence can be negative or positive in a sense positive valence can lead to positive emotions and negative valence can lead to negative emotions. Ultimately, we are looking at the intrinsic attractiveness of the firm. Following factor can lead to the high valence or positive valence such as higher level of power, strong position, high status (Kemper & Collins, 1990; Turner & Stets, 2005), having strong structures, systems, established intergroup boundaries (Terry et al., 2001), better incentives and compensation packages for the employees (Ahammad, Glaister, Weber, & Tarba, 2012; Datta, Iskandar-Datta, & Raman, 2001; Iverson & Pullman, 2000). In contrast, there are factors within the organisation which can negatively impact the organisation as a result of negative valence or reduced valence and these factors are about the perceptions of an insecure future about a firm by its members and it can also be because of any internal or internal poor position of organisation expected by its members (Kiefer, 2005), inadequate working conditions which is the strong indicator of bad image of firm (Kiefer, 2005), and lack of fairness (Sinkovics et al., 2011).

Finally, efficacy refers to the firm's the ability to produce a desired or intended result. In M&A context, firms required to meet strategic and social challenges with available or limited resources as a result of M&A process (Armenakis et al., 1999; Harris & Gresch, 2010). Emotional intelligence (Salleh, 2009), self-efficacy of the employees which believes that that would have the ability to be able to succeed (Idel et al., 2003), higher level of involvement of the management and leadership with the employees to achieve the targets (Ullrich et al., 2005), emotional attending

which means being sensitive to employee's feelings and experiences. It consists of both perceiving and processing various messages from employees and middle level management or supervisors. For example, many employees within the organisations communicate their emotions only nonverbally (Cormier and Cormier, 1991) (Reus, 2012), and finally social support which will involve making employees feel that they are cared for by the management as a result of M&As (Gunkel, Schlaegel, Rossteutscher, & Wolff, 2015). All these factors can contribute towards increasing the efficacy of the organisation as whole (Sarala et. al 2019) which can result in successful mergers and acquisitions integration process. For instance, employees of Lotus wanted to leave as a result of IBM acquiring Lotus fearing layoffs and dominance. (Chaudhuri, 2005). But IBM's leadership visited Lotus and involved the employees and show emotional intelligence by explaining the rationale behind the acquisition to the target firm (appropriateness). IBM's leadership also retain Lotus' key managerial positions and introduced compensation plans as a result of acquisition (valence) and provided resources for the integration process by providing the employees of target firm social support and high level of involvement (efficacy) (Chaudhuri, 2005). The role of communication is very important in any M&A as it is helpful in signalling appropriateness, valence, and efficacy to the members of target firm. Communication also provides the platform for members to determine any critical aspects and act as co-determinants of members' emotions documented by Zagelmeyer, Sinkovics, Sinkovics, and Kusstatscher (2016).

Therefore, emotions can play an important role in providing a socio-cultural mechanism and opportunity for the firms for its employees to have strong connection and improve the human factors such as status, personality, power, fairness, HR practices and social support within the organisations that affects the behaviours, attitudes, and eventually social M&A integration outcomes. Sense making is way forward to highlight the integrative emotions in M&A theories. Emotions varies from person to person, and it may arise through individual cognitive evaluations and members from and within the target and acquiring firms may have different emotions. As per the practice approach, strategic processes such as M&A emerge intense emotions at different levels within the organisations (Brundin & Liu, 2015). Therefore, members at each level within the organisation make cognitive appraisals based on a complex process of thinking about M&A strategy and resources assessment. Leadership at middle level face more challenges because of bridging the gap between the senior leadership and labour (Clarke & Salleh, 2011). The focus is moved from top management to individual level and emotional process including different aspects

and features at different levels and become dynamic in M&As. In case of health care mergers by Ford and Harding (2003), members from both firms were optimistic immediately after the merger as they hope that this merger and acquisition would bring more personal career development and higher organisational growth opportunities. However, during the integration process, members felt dejected and agitated that the firm has lost the humour of its culture and they had sacrificed too much of themselves. There is need of further work in socio-cultural area to identify the different outcomes as a result of dynamic emotions. Emphasis on individual members highlight the role of emotions at micro level antecedents however these can also be conceptualized at collective level. Social theory stems from the idea where emotions originate from the experience with others (Strongman, 1996). Sensemaking interlink these emotions at individual as well as organisational level (Stensaker & Falkenberg, 2007). As a result of M&A collective emotions shared among group members and members' reactions such as intensification or deintensification are evidenced (Von Scheve & Ismer, 2013; Von Scheve & Salmela, 2014) and these can include their reactions and emotions as a result of M&A such as combined disbelief or collective stimulation (Grodal & Granqvist, 2014). Additionally, it very important to understand the emotions within group members are their exciting capabilities can exist at group level which can become collective emotions. It is important to understand the formations of shared emotions and their response in a group to manage the change process characterized by Emotional aperture (Sanchez- Burks & Huy, 2009). However, this area of research is needed much more detailed discussion and analysis as the role of collective emotions and emotions capabilities in M&A and their connection with other collective level construct (role of media, national culture, and firm culture in forming emotions) is underexplored (Sarala, Vaara and Junni, 2017).

Furthermore, the relationship between individual emotions (field of psychology) and collective emotions and emotional capabilities (cognitive and sociological process) requires further research in M&A literature (Sarala, Vaara and Junni, 2017). Furthermore, managing emotions in M&A depend on the contextual factors such in cultural context, social beliefs system prevents individual from adding different meaning to their predefined activities and roles (Golsorkhi et al., 2015). For example, in study of merger of banks in Brunei by Clarke and Salleh (2011), the emotions of manager influence M&A guided by their beliefs that they have to endure the acquisition patiently and show gratitude. Similarly, emotional attending (ability to consider and care for emotions) can be different based on cultural context. Reus (2012) experienced reduced emotional attending in

different international cultures conducted by US acquirers. Also, expression of emotions also differs in different cultural settings and affects the member of firms accordingly. Countries likely to expect suppression of emotions where status and power culture exist (Matsumoto, Yoo, & Nakagawa, 2008). However, US firms adjusted their emotional attending according to the cultural context such as increased level of emotional attending in high level of people-oriented culture (Reus, 2012). Research in socio-economic context suggests that members in under-developed countries trigger positive emotions as a result of M&As. Members of target firm from under-developed economies perceived development in personal skills and career (increased valance) because of acquiring firm from developed country (Paustian-Underdahl et al., 2017). Research in field of emotions within different industries is lacking and It can be different according to characteristics of different industries in M&As. For example, high-tech industries are subject to radical changes as compared to traditional sectors such as retail or manufacturing. Subsequently, employees in high-tech industries are more resilient and can be ready for change easily within IT/IS department as compare to employees working in other industries as they have more abilities to deal with drastically changing environment of their firms in M&As. Additionally, emotions are different based on gender; women show sadness as low-activation emotions as compared to men which show anger as high-activating emotions (Strongman, 1996) therefore, industries with skewed gender biasness such as the nursing profession, which is commonly a female dominated profession while banking is a male dominated field.

Finally, occupational emotions form as a part of professional identity (Salmela, 2014) where conflict can arise when employees feel disgruntled because of M&A situation while performing their duties. Therefore, we need to have more detailed analysis by observing the embeddedness of emotional dynamics as a result of M&A in different countries and industries which may require comparative research designs to fully assess the emotional effects on employees and as a result on M&A (Sarala, Vaara and Junni, 2017).

2.4.14 Effective Communication

Communication plays a vital part in a M&A integration processes. It is source of delivering information within the organisation such as to its members and employees and outside the organisations such as stakeholders about the organisational change which can happen as a result of M&A. It also fosters motivation and commitment, controls organisational member behaviour,

enhances a sense of belonging as well as the release for the emotional expression as noted by Welch & Jackson (2007). It has several dimensions such as formal, informal, upward, downward, and/or lateral. Communication involves different sources of information and addressee which can be anyone or anonymous (Guirdham, 2002). Characteristics of effective communication include frequency and continuity (Angwin et al., 2016), consistency (Hubbard & Purcell, 2001), honesty (Bastien, 1987), openness (Zagelmeyer et al., 2016), and collegiality (Bastien, 1987). Pre-acquisition communication reduces fears and concerns in M&As (Tanure & Gonzalez- Duarte, 2007). Communication play role in motivating employees so that they can have positive attitude and behaviour and as a result this can have positive outcomes on post M&A integration process (Chaudhuri & Tabrizi, 1999) and finally it improves the commitment of employees with the organisation (Angwin, Mellahi, Gomes, & Peter, 2016) which can positively affect M&As integration. Communication processes can be manipulated based on someone interests, background, experience, and attitudes when sending or taking information by deliberately or subconsciously using filters.

M&As cause uncertainty and ambiguity about organisation and its future among employees which may be perceived as threatened (Amiot, Terry, & Jimmieson, 2006). As a result, employees look out for information about the deal and its implications for their employment (McClurg, 2002). Having formal communication process in place which employees base their expectations can be positive and sensemaking for the employees. Formal communication is communicated as it is by avoiding any ambiguities as compare to the informal process of communication or with a lack of communication which can have ambiguities and rumours, employees base their expectations on any information which can have negative impact for both firms and its members during M&A integration process. Therefore, communication helps in building the organisational frame that will facilitate managerial actions (Hubbard and Purcell, 2001). Also, in absence of information, employees tend to derive their own interpretations of events and their meanings which can be misleading sometimes (Lotz & Donald, 2006, p. 3). Additionally, employees feel ambiguities because of unclear, non-existence and misinterpretation of information (Risberg, 1997). However, clear, and genuine information is major determinant of successful M&A (Van Dick, Ullrich, and Tissington, 2006, p. 31).

Communication helps to create the right perception of fairness, procedural as well as interactional justice on workers (Lotz & Donald, 2006) and acceptance for change thus, better commitment from employees (Klendauer and Deller, 2009). Relevant communication can manage employees' expectations which can interpret their psychological contract with firm (Hubbard and Purcell, 2001). Vaara and Monin (2010) focus on leadership aspects of communication for discursive legitimization of an M&A which can be used to yield particular behaviours from employees to support the process of cultural integration and development (Soderberg, 2012). Also, communication play very important role in cultural integration as a result of merger of two firms from different cultures and it can also contribute towards socio-cultural building and outcomes (Evans et al., 2011). Communication is very important for building trust relationships when two firm's mergers happening as it can help to build the trust between the two newly merging firms by having open and clear communication of integration process at each level (Stahl, Larsson, Kremershof & Sitkin, 2011). Additionally, it helps to achieve and supports strategic outcomes such as knowledge transfer (Ranft & Lord, 2002) and finally it helps in merger survival in case of any complications involved in M&A integration process (Angwin et al., 2016).

2.4.14.1. Emotions in Communication

M&A integration can be highly complex process and involved enormous factors so communication during this process is very important. Communication whether it is formal or informal such as rumours among colleagues triggers emotional responses. According to Affective Events Theory (AET) certain aspects of the work environment systematically triggers pleasant and unpleasant emotions. As a result, these emotions can affect the behaviours of employees and resultantly changes in work attitudes are inevitable (Ashkanasy et al., 2000; Weiss & Cropanzano, 1996). Although emotions can be associated with group, but it is the individual who experience or triggered these emotions (Lazarus, 1995) and these emotions can be triggered by group-level processes characterized by Social Identity Theory (SIT) (Hogg & Terry, 2000; Ullrich, Wieseke, & Dick, 2005). This theory helps in understanding emotional dimensions in M&A of two firms by its individuals or by groups or identities. SIT elaborate on emotions building process as extent of identification of individuals or group will influence employee commitment, readiness, and willingness to accept or leave another identity and culture (Ellemers, Spears, & Doosje, 2002). According to cognitive appraisal approach, employees' emotions are shaped by the appraisal of

communication by management and leadership of the organisation as compare to their actions (Frijda, 2008).

However, the interpretation and giving meanings to these emotions is very important and the managerial communication effects on employees' emotions. In contrast, Liu and Perrewé (2005) stated that different stages of changes process trigger different emotional responses which affect the behaviours and attitudes of employees. Also, change process can trigger negative emotions which can cause withdrawal behaviour and trust issues during M&As Kiefer (2005). Sinkovics et al. (2011) developed framework on function of emotions in international M&As where he explained employees' actions influenced by independent variables or contextual factors, which include communication, behaviour of managers, and other M&A-related factors which triggers emotions which then affects the behaviours and attitudes of employees. However, Gunkel et al. (2015) tested this model and found no significant relationship between employees and management communication and as a result employee feeling of dissatisfaction and insecurity during an M&A. Nevertheless, communication does affect the employee's emotions and behaviour which shape their modes and attitudes regardless of the actions as it can be used to motivate the employees as many employees under transformational leadership have experienced it. It is universal truth that having positive communication with employees which can have positive outcomes and negative communication can trigger negative emotions and consequences.

2.4.15 Participation

In M&As, authors conceptualize top-down processes where decisions made at top levels in acquiring firms. At pre-acquisition stage, decisions are limited to small groups however, in post-acquisition period, organisations required broad range of engagement and participation for successful integration. Therefore, practice perspective focuses on the members who contribute to strategy making opposed to the top management (Jarzabkowski & Wolf, 2015; Vaara & Whittington, 2012). Top management of target firm should be involved in board to retain some power which can reduce employees' resistance and increase the employees' participation, which leads to transfer of knowledge and smoothly transferring the power to follow the best practices during integration process (Colman & Lunnan, 2011; Kale, Singh, & Raman, 2009). Top management at acquired firms can also contribute to mitigating and alleviating members concerns, resolving conflicts and avoid disruptions by target firm's employees during integration process

(Colman & Lunnan, 2011). Therefore, management from target firm can act as change agents for acquiring firm in identifying and providing solutions proactively (Colman & Lunnan, 2011). Middle management such as integration managers, HR managers and line managers also play important role as change managers in their capacity (Antila & Kakkonen, 2006) and act as active agents and interpret, mediate, and broker information (Shi et al., 2009). They also involve in devising strategy and implantation process (Balogun & Johnson, 2004). Subsequently, a shift from a “top-down” such as from centralized structure of management style towards decentralized structure such as “involvement and commitment.” which made middle level managers as recipient and change agents which will help to transform their position to enablers and empowerees such as higher-level management of acquiring firms (Caldwell, 2003). Furthermore, integration managers can also influence value creation and value leakage during M&A integration process (Teerikangas et al., 2011) whereas HR managers can advise and resolve any complications and provide training to the line managers with M&A process and as a result integration process (Antila & Kakkonen, 2006) during integration process. Employees also act as change agents which are not acknowledged in literature of change agency (Caldwell, 2003).

The most important element of M&A is the employees. These are not only implementers of strategies for the firms, but also initiate the change processes proactively during post mergers and acquisition integration process. This will allow members to discover information which is credible source of information for employees (Armenakis, Harris, & Mossholder, 1993). For example, employees will understand and realize the reasons behind the M&A integration process as a result of their input in planning strategy for integration process (Armenakis et al., 1993) as well as actively participate in integration by allowing them to visit merging firms through exchange program to share discoveries and create eagerness for change environment among other contemporaries by influencing them at personal level (Armenakis et al., 1993). Engaging in regular meetings and task forces enables workers to participate in change process (Vales, 2007) which can lead to successful M&As. Thus, employees’ involvement is a successful factor for M&A (Nguyen and Kleiner, 2003) and increase fairness, commitment, and trust about M&A Schraeder and Self (2003). Finally, other stakeholders such as customers, investment bankers, advocates as well as labour unions are essential in M&As and should be considered in decision making. For example, labour union became driving force and opposed by management of American Airlines during integration with US Airways (Reed, 2013). Studies should have examined the impact of other

stakeholders on processes, practices, and integration success mergers rather than on financial returns provided by Bodnaruk, Massa, & Simonov (2009) and Servaes & Zenner (2015).

2.5 Related and unrelated acquisitions

The acquisitions are specific investment types; Acquisitions are frequently made at peaks (Bruner 2002; Rappaport 1986), with global transactions climbing past \$3,000 billion (Tschoke and Csanad 2007). Related acquisition involved acquires other company within similar business industry. A relatively significant number of scholars have investigated the effect of acquiring firms that are related to offering premiums but most of the studies revealed no evidence of strong correlation (Walkling and Edmister, 1985). Previous studies have grouped general types of M&As into related acquisitions (Morck et al., 1990).

In contrast, unrelated mergers occur between firms that are neither rivals in the same industry, nor linked in a partnership between buyer and supplier. While in similar mergers there are many potential sources of value creation (mergers that can be categorized as either horizontal or vertical), the examples include eliminating double marginalization and transaction costs in vertical mergers and increasing and leveraging market power in horizontal mergers (Aggarwal and Baxamusa 2013). Where unrelated mergers are involved, the origins of value creation are less obvious. Intriguingly, we find the largest group of acquisitions happening between unrelated companies. Much work hasn't centered on these unrelated fusions in the previous literature. While there is a literature that focused on conglomerate merger waves (see e.g., for a review of the 1960s and 1980s, Shleifer and Vishny (1991).

Various studies investigate the impact of goal / acquirer relationships on goal and/or receiving irregular stock returns from firms (Flanagan O'Shaughnessy 2003). These studies ' results were somewhat mixed. Although related acquisitions have generally been considered superior to unrelated acquisitions, research has not generally shown that reports of linked mergers boost the wealth of stockholders acquiring firms.

2.6 Strategic fit and mergers

A strategic fit is defined as "a situation that occurs when a particular project, target company, or product is considered appropriate in relation to the overall goals of an organisation." Most managers who seek to expand their business by mergers and acquisition and seek another company

thereby leading to strategic fit. All of the early conversation between parties will concentrate on how the current business plan of the target matches with yours, whether you have the same expectations of success as they have, what advantages the transaction can bring to your respective customers, and what prospective new customers will be open to you. As Shelton (1988) points out, there is a strategic match when two organisations have generated value that would not otherwise have been accomplished if they tried to achieve a target separately. He claims that this extra value is created by the integration of the accumulated assets of the companies. It is possible to attain more so-called synergistic benefits, as described above. The strategic fit described as the capacity of a partnership, i.e., the organisational and relational matching issues emerging from a partnership, as identified by Ireland, Hitt and Vaidyanath (2002), is to some degree different. As an example, the two companies have an organisational potential, that is, they can achieve greater potential objectives as they complement each other if they cooperate successfully. A third approach to identifying strategic fit is the need for closely similar priorities between the combining or target / acquiring companies (Das & Teng, 2000). This could be a more explicit clarification of the term; it indicates that companies need to have things in common in order to work in the first place on the merger or acquisition, but also a great match of goals. The strategic fit described as: a target that would not be accomplished if the firms worked separately, rather when synergy is generated when they go together (Eun & Resnick, 2007). Figure 1 shows the four possible strategic fits (Shelton, 1988) between new potential partners.

Serving New Customers

Figure 2.1 Strategic Fits Between a Target & a Bidder Business

Shelton (1988) tested the hypothesis in his study by evaluating the different strategic fit, which can be ranked to create value beginning by starting with a related supplementary and related complementary and lastly the unrelated. The outcome showed that strategic fits are essential for the determination of the summative gains created by an acquisition. Related-supplementary and similar fits offer significant value creation opportunities, and related-supplementary fits do so with the least variation. Unrelated fits are least capable of producing interest. Medcof (1997) complements this by stating that the purpose of any collaboration is to further the strategic business interests of the companies involved. It is paramount to make consideration whether the potential partner can lead to a good strategic match. On this note, studies have revealed that merging similar companies can lead to value creation for the acquiring firm (Lubatkin 1983; Porter 1985). Similar mergers involve companies merging the same or similar company, market, or technical features (Singh and Montgomery, 1987). Such similarities help in creation of opportunities for the development of strategic fit for companies in a merger and acquisition arrangement as characterized by sharing of resources formation of synergies as well as economies of scale. The strategic fit strengthens the merged firm's competitive position while rising the financial performance over the long term. If the stock market perceives that associated combinations boost an acquirer's long-term financial performance, the stock price of an acquiring company will rise at the time of announcement of the related acquisition.

2.7 Role of Leadership

The recent studies in M&A have pointed out that there is little known about the combination process and its effects on M&A success Haleblan et al. (2009). Specifically, the role of leadership is neglected in M&A literature, however, Sitkin and Pablo (2005) disagree by stating that studies on importance of leadership were provided in abundance but there is insufficient evidence about the

how leadership influence the M&A outcome and what actually the M&A leadership is? M&As reshape the organisations and affects the employees involved in mergers therefore understanding the role of leadership is important in M&As. According to Yukl, (2012) the role of leadership is very important in achieving the shared goals of M&A and during the process of integration, M&A leadership should steer up the essential efforts for the achievement of the mutual goals.

Junni and Sarala (2014) worked on the studies published between 2000 and 2013 and evident that the M&A leadership not being studied in terms of M&As effects on different levels and its outcomes measures. They have stated that most studies focused on behavioural aspect of leadership of acquiring firms rather than targeted firms' leaders. Also missing focus on leadership behaviour in post mergers rather than pre-M&A stage and interactions between both leaders before and after M&As. Furthermore, they have highlighted the gap in literature of identifying leadership for M&A and their dynamic aspects at each level of organisations. Finally, very few studies examined M&A leadership traits, M&A leadership contingencies, and power and politics in M&A leadership thus lack of a comprehensive study which combines several theoretical perspectives.

Although studies recognized that the mergers and acquisitions have not succeeded up to the intended potential (Larsson and Finkelstein, 1999), the role of effective leadership on M&As have not been well articulated or studied and in fact the role of leaders has been ignored in M&As success or failure by scholars (Stahl, G., 2010). Richard M. (2002) evidenced that, a systematic approach needs to be followed to increase the success rates of mergers and acquisitions. He further states that any mergers involve significant change within the organisation and leadership is one of the first factor that contribute towards the successful change, therefore leadership is critical to the success of mergers and acquisitions. In mergers cases of BP & AMACO and Chrysler & Daimler Benz, it is evident that to integrate effectively leadership is key role at many levels of organisation supported by the views of Heskett and Kotter (1992) and Kotter (1996) which suggests for change to be persistent, there must be leadership at many levels of organisations during mergers. Therefore, it is becoming increasingly clear that post mergers and acquisitions performance is strongly affected by leadership to achieve the integration (Waldman and Javidan, 2009).

2.7.1. Weak leadership

Leadership crises including worries, delay in decision making, lack of purpose and courage, weak commitment and not able to trust anyone. Managers often insulated during mergers and prepare self- defeating gambits (Marks, 1997).

2.7.2. Improper management

Simpson, (2000) suggests that mergers failed due to improper management, strategy, delays in communications, culture difference and lack of clear vision. Improper managing of mergers results in employee's uncertainty, stress, anxiety which causes dissatisfaction, non-commitment, carelessness, distrust, and dishonesty regardless the employees affected by mergers or not (Appelbaum et al., 2000).

2.7.3. Delays in communications

Delays in communicating employees caused apprehensive feelings and hostility among employees and strained the further communications about mergers. It also creates the environment of uncertainty and speculation (Marks, 1999). With this in mind employees search for information themselves and distracted from their jobs and some cases employees focused on preserving their jobs rather than focus on customers as a result HP lost the customers (Kewamoto, 2002). Delay in communication also affects customers as they unsure of their purchasing decisions about products lines discontinuations. Customers interactions with employees result in jeopardise as they are unsure if they see the same support personal again or that personal with be at new company. As a result, they shift their business over competitors as studied in HP mergers where it expected to lose about 5 per cent revenue due to customers walk away (Men and Pham, 2002).

2.7.4. Lack of Vision

Without clear vision, shareholder value can be damaged during mergers where ideas giving looks promising but turn out to be useless later (Recklies, 2001). Kenellos and Peline, (1998) studied mergers of ambiguous visions between AT&T and NCR. Similar mergers between AOL and Time Warner studied by Walker (2002).

2.7.5. Leadership styles

Leadership is considered as the ability of an individual to motivate people for them to achieve the common goals and lead to an extraordinary performance on the followers (Dobbins and Pettman, 1997). Leadership has been studied widely in the literature of management as soft skills of knowledge (Kinkus, 2007; Vasconcelos, Kimble, & Rocha, 2016). Leadership is related to the personal ability in respect to skills, ability, and degree of influence on people when they are in the right direction to ensure that they make decision that led to the right direction and result in better outcome (Kets De Vries & Florent- Treacy, 2002).

Leadership styles can be categorized as three major groups:

Autocratic or authoritative leadership is very strict type of style where leaders keep close control on the followers and keep close regulation for policies and procedures that are given to followers as they are required to obey the instructions without questioning (Lewin, Lippit & White, 1939). They make decisions without consulting their team members and like to focus on the distinction of the authoritarian leader and their followers and only create a distinct professional relationship. This style is appropriate when quick decisions need to be made and less importance give to the team agreement however, this leadership style can lead to increased staff turnover.

Democratic leaders take input from the team members but retain the final say over final decision and focus on team input in decision making process. This style encourage discussion, debate, creativity and sharing of ideas between the members and focus on people to feel good about their involvement. As a result, members feel more engaged, have high job satisfaction and productivity.

Laissez-faire style delegates the tasks to their followers with little guidance or directions. Team members have freedom over their description of work and deadlines. They provide full autonomy with support, resources and advice if needed and have less involvement in decisions to complete the task by members. Members feel high job satisfaction, but it can often lead to poorly defined roles and a lack of motivation if members are not expert or self-motivated.

Contingency school of thought suggests that it depend on the situation which makes an effective leader (Krech, Crutchfield, & Ballachey, 1962; Fiedler, 1967; House, 1971 and Robbins, 1997). This theory encourages the idea that leaders provide directions (Path-goal theory) to team members setting up goals and help in goal setting process. They assess the leadership based on three patterns:

- Assess the characteristics of the leader.

- Evaluate the situation regarding key contingency variables.
- Seek a match between the leader and the situation.

Path-goal theory was introduced by Martin Evans in the year 1970 and improved by House in 1971. The theory is founded on the expectancy theory developed by Vroom (1964), which states that a person will act in a certain manner based on the expectations and the given outcome as well as the attractiveness that is created by a leader. The theory elucidates on three steps:

- Determination of the worker's and environmental characteristics
- Selection of the style of leadership
- Focusing on motivational factors that should help employees to succeed

A path-goal theory is a specific manifestation of contingency theory that best fits the employee and work environment in order to achieve a goal (House and Mitchell, 1974). The goal can be to increase the member's motivation, empowerment, and job satisfaction so they become productive.

Four types of leaders' styles were identified which included directive leaders, supportive, participative, and achievement-oriented leaders. Directive leaders provide the instructions, creating timelines, setting performance standards and clear set of for their members. Directive leaders are considered more effective in management of authoritative subordinates, unambiguous, and complicated responsibilities. Whereas Supportive leaders focus on needs for affiliation of members. A repetitive and unchallenging work environment is best suited for supportive leaders. Participative leadership behaviour focuses on encouraging their members into decision making process. And finally, Achievement-oriented leaders focus on challenging the members to achieve the highest standards of excellence. Members who are self-motivated and highly skilled confidence in accomplishing goals and work well under complex and challenging environment can work well with achievement-oriented leaders.

The behavioural school of thought is based on the suggestion that effective leaders make adoption of the various certain styles (Adair, 1983; Blake & Mouton, 1982; Hersey & Blanchard, 1988), especially the ones studied in theory X and theory Y provided by McGregor in 1960 (Bass, 1990): Theory X managers have the notion that every worker have some element of dislike on the work that they do, and they make attempts to avoid it if possible. Such people believe that their employees are lazy and tend to avoid great responsibilities and make preference to getting out of

their workplace and do not desire to exert huge efforts. Due to this fact, employees tend to be directly controlled through threat and punishments in order to ensure that they put adequate efforts for the achievement of organisational objectives. Theory Y managers have the notion that workers tend to care about their organisations and seek responsibilities through self-control for achievement of the intended goals. Such managers tend to believe that when a person exerts physical and mental efforts, it is as a result of seamless natural way and they learn from the leaders. Such leaders can exercise significant level of imagination through creativity and through organisational problems. Bobic and Davis (2003) concluded that majority of the population had the ability to exert innovation and be creativity, which is in line with the theory Y managers' assumptions, which contribute positively towards the participative decision-making and ultimately leading to the benefit of the organisation (Russ, 2011).

On the same note, Bass (1990) identified two other leadership categories: transformational and transactional. The literature focused on the complexity of the contexts where leaders could emerge and acknowledge that transactional leaders emerge in situations of low complexity and high complexity (Sousa and Rocha, 2018):

Transactional leadership rewards their members for achieving goals and performance targets. Transactional leaders focus on the role of supervision, responsibilities, compliance, and group performance. The one factor of transactional leadership is to focus on motivating members and recognise their efforts through a system of rewards and punishments. There other factor is management-by-exception which allows leadership to maintain the status quo by taking corrective actions when members not performing to boost up the performance to acceptable levels.

Transformational leadership works with members to identify the need of change by developing a vision through aspiration. Leader exhibits charisma, respect, and trust. With a focus on the followers, transformational leadership helps to stimulate them and challenge them to be innovative and develop new ideas and approaches. The members feel trusted and admire the leader as they exhibit their loyalty and respect on the leader and work harder than expected with leadership because of these qualities. They inspire members with mission and clear vision and offer members more than just for self-gain. They also encourage members to challenge status quo and environment to become successful however Bass, (1990) suggested that leadership can be both transformational and transactional simultaneously. The research shows that leadership style has

the ability to determine the performance of the organisation as contributed by the individual efforts and workers' group (Bass and Bass 2009). Transformational leadership motivates members through their charisma, intellectual stimulation as well as individual consideration.

2.7.5.1. Leadership styles and mergers

There are number of studies focuses on leadership qualities and styles which conceptualized and providing justification of applicability during mergers and acquisitions. For instance, Mumford & Van Doorn (2001) contrasted pragmatic and charismatic forms of leadership. It involves, objective analysis of situation, identification of problem and develop and implement the solution. Pragmatic style of leadership is suitable when there are clear goals and objectives in place however, pragmatic leaders have very limited applicability to M&A when goals are unclear, different vested interests, difficulty in achieving consensus and when uncertainty prevails. Mumford and Van Doorn (2001). Whereas charismatic leadership focuses on achieving consensus and developing a vision in an attempt to integrate multiple groups.

A comparison of charismatic and ideological leadership is studied by Strange and Mumford (2002) and described both leadership styles provide basis for the formation of vision and overlaps in terms of identification of change requirements, vision articulation and identified ideological leadership as subtype of charismatic leadership. Finally, they have concluded that charismatic leadership is associated with the type of change and integration efforts required in M&A implementation.

However, applicability of charismatic leadership to M&A might be timely and organisation based which focuses heavily on processes rather than the influence of leaders over groups within organisation Yukl (1999). Yukl believed that coordination, trust, cooperation, and agreement regarding objectives and priorities among group members is likely to be relevant to the effective implementation of an M&A.

Beyer (1999) suggested that charismatic theory should focus on achieving organisational-level change and outcomes whereas a range of neo-charismatic conceptualizations have considered this suggestion and focused on organisational based changing processes (House & Aditya, 1997) and number of studied concluded that M&A represents major change and transformation at organisational level therefore charismatic leadership can be suitable.

Charismatic leadership theory also focusses on strategic management as it's related to the effects of top-level management characteristics on strategy formulation and change and charismatic leadership considered more important when formulating strategy (Cannella & Monroe, 1997; Finkelstein & Hambrick, 1996). Therefore M&A may reveal more leadership qualities when applied at strategic level (Sitkin & Pablo, 2005, p. 212).

2.7.6. Transformational leadership role

2.7.6.1. Create vision and objective

Developing vision and providing direction is such a transformational task and leadership must provide a clear vision for the merging firms to their members as it is very important for whole organisation. This will allow members to predict the future of transition in organisation. However, leaders will need charisma and inspiration to model the behaviour and creating a sense of purpose for what their members are experiencing during transition period (Appelbaum et al, 2000; DiGeorgio, 2003).

2.7.6.2. Openness and participative style

During transition, a participative or democratic style of leadership is more preferable than autocratic style. Leadership style plays an important role for their members about the behaviour of overall leadership in organisation. For example, NHS Staff felt more positive during transition when they perceived a greater degree of consultation Cortvriend (2004).

2.7.6.3. Shaping change and making sense

Sense making defined as 'Active agent "Structure the unknown" How they construct what they construct, why, and with what effects are the central questions for people interested in sense-making' (Weick, 1995, 9.04). The leaders should be able to read the environment, identify the challenges, constructed by members of the organisation, and find the way out of it. According to Grint, (2005), leaders make sense out of problems and provide a solution to a specific problem. Therefore, leaders of transitions not only have responsibility of shaping (as well as being shaped by) the changes but also making sense for members of what is happening (eg. Vaara, 2003). Haspeslagh and Jemison (1991) concluded that rational view of mergers failed to consider all sources of conflict which are negatively impacting the acquisition decision and the implementation

of the merger and therefore suggested organisational process perspective to counter the procedural (and perhaps more transactional) approaches. They have stated four factors which cause uncertainty during decision making process such as different perspective by different managers and unclear expected benefit on acquisitions. As a result, leaders facing challenges in sense-making on individual level as well as in collective interactions with members.

2.7.7. Transactional leadership role

2.7.7.1. Managing the human resource

When it comes to mergers failures, human resources management (HRM) and culture are neglected and classed as second priority compare to the commercial and financial consideration. Jeris et al, (2002) and Aguilera & Dencker, (2004) documented the importance of HMR as crucial element during the process of mergers and acquisitions. Literature is emphasizing the importance and suggest that HRM should be the main task for all senior and general management and should not be ignored during transition. It requires constant and comprehensive attention by senior managers to transactional activities ensuring recruitment, retention, redundancies, communication, staff support, staff training and development etc. and post-merger integration work associated tasks related to HRM during transition period (Epstein, 2004).

2.7.7.2. Effective Communicate

It is evident that the firms who pay more attention to communication by management perform more successfully than those where communications were poor Tourish and Hargie (1998). Communication is one of their golden rules of mergers and directors should get out of their boardrooms and communicate with employees another golden rule stated by Nguyen and Kleiner (2003) where these rules derived from executive interviews who have been through transition process of mergers and acquisitions. Providing clear and consistent, factual, sympathetic, and up-to-date information in several areas will increase the coping abilities of employees for success in transition process. Similarly, Jeris et al (2002) and Hubbard and Purcell (2001) identify the communication is one of the key issues in managing the transitions.

2.7.7.3. Appointment of effective Leaders

In merger of equals where both companies are equal size wants to integrate as a result of merger and acquisition. Appointment of leadership can be very difficult in new organisational structure. Following are the different approaches provided different implications for integration.

2.7.7.4. The principal leader approaches

As a result, for merger, a new firm is formed and for this reason most appropriate leadership is chosen out of available eligible candidates from both organisations. The candidates who are not selected for leadership roles are either reassigned to other departments or released.

Principal leadership approach has many advantages such as this process of appointing leadership will choose the most competent leadership as per the objectives and achieving the required targets of different organisational functions. Also, this process is very quick and efficient. This process gives leadership with autonomy over the different functions so that they can conduct their duties without any power struggle or disagreements.

However, principal leadership approaches have some disadvantages such as familiarity and biasness where leadership chosen is more familiar with his or her own firm than merging firm. As a result, leader will give priority and support staff from his own firm and team. This can lead to the culture of organisational politics and developing cronyism where one group can get stronger over other group which can cause post-acquisition conflict.

2.7.7.5. The coalition approaches

Under coalition approach, a group of two or more leaders formed chosen from each merging firm where they work together to form a team in order to perform different organisational functions.

This approach has advantage over other approaches to choose the best coalition of leaders from both merging firms and based on that Idea they choose the appropriate employees to perform different functions of new organisation. This approach ensures that each merging firm has its representative in board and have balance of power over the functions of new organisation. Finally, coalition of leadership chosen has the familiarity of people, processes, cultures, and structures of their own firms.

However, coalition approach of appointing leadership has some disadvantages. This process can be costly and decision-making process can become complicated and time consuming. As a result, there can be compromises which can cause post-acquisition conflict.

2.7.7.6. The delegation approaches

The delegation approach referred to hiring external consultant who is impartial for integration of both firms. Consultant in this approach is performing the similar duty performed by recruitment agency's consultant and external recruitment consultant interviews the employees from both organisations for suitable posts. Consultant duty is to assess both firms existing structures and proposed structure for new firm and employee members based on his or her assessment.

The advantage of this approach is that this approach can avoid the threats of familiarity and biasness and choose the best candidates out of both firms and allocate the resources appropriately after considering the external market conditions. Also, impartiality offered by this approach lead towards avoiding demotivation by members of both firms which is naturally occurs as a result of choosing the familiar members by leaders from their perspective firms.

However, this approach can be very costly, complex and time consuming. The consultant is from outside the firm and he or she might not put many efforts and commitment that required fulfilling the required position compared to internal leaders of firms when faced with similar situation who can better understand the needs of the organisation.

2.7.7.7. The broadcast approaches

Finally, broadcast approach communicates all the available positions internally throughout to the members of organisation. Applicants are invited internally from any qualification and experience within the organisation where every member can get the chance to apply for any position. The disadvantages of this approach including costly and time consuming where large number of applications can be received from members for more attractive positions and as a result take time to sort the appropriate candidate from large sample. Researchers call for the research due to underexplored areas and their practical implications such as Insufficient Due diligence and resources allocation M&A (Oon, 1998), Level and quality of planning in M&A (Oon, 1998), Lack of comprehensive M&A leadership research inculcating Power and politics and Leadership contingencies (Junni, P. and Sarala, R., 2014).

Leadership should be involved in the due diligence process and there should be role for leaders during change management and organisational change processes so that they can effectively manage the human during the integration process. They should also be involved in the integration of information technology and systems, during change of any business process, analysing enterprise processes and help in the Improvement and optimization of the organisational processes. In case as a result of M&A, firms need redesigning the processes and systems, leaders should also provide their input in controlling risks and implementing projects such as enterprise systems such as Enterprise Resource Planning (ERP). If a firm needs new or needs improvements in the total quality management (TQM) system, leadership and the employees from both firms should provide their input as employees and leadership understand the system dynamics of both firms and also business structures, processes, and culture.

Leadership can also help firms and provide input in business process management to value stream analysis which can involve activities such as mapping in the organisation and subsequently identification of opportunities for more improvement within the systems and processes so that they can provide better value to final consumer. For instance, as a result of M&A, leadership can provide help with the involvement of employees in preparation of the map indicating the current state and description of the existing problems and based on that experts can plan in preparation of the future state map showing improvement and action plans. Getting direct feedback from customers and employees can help in reduction of lead time, project cycles as well as resource demand within the organisational processes.

2.8 Role of culture

Culture is among one of the main reasons why mergers and acquisitions between the organisations failed as it is often underestimated during planning and execution of integration process. In M&A, firm's years of success is deep rooted by culture and probability of cultural failure can be anticipated in the pre-merger stages. Indicators of weaker culture could be misalignment in strategic and production goals, high staff turnover, difficulties in retaining key employees, lower level of employees' motivation and commitment, increase in employees' conflict and stress levels etc. Mergers and acquisitions can exert a lot of pressure on cultural integrity of an organisation and these indicators will assess where the existing culture may be somewhat weaker. Emergence of proposed merger can increase the chances of cultural failure where these indicators are present.

The cultural stance on mergers and acquisitions strongly draws from people dimension and strategic fit literature. Cultural dimension is closely related with people dimension and research based on these areas started in mid-1980s where culture was source of competitive advantage (Barney 1986) and linked with organisational performance (Peters and Waterman 1982). The cultural perspective of people dimension focuses on the cultural variables 'impact on mergers and acquisition and considers the integration of people and cultures (acculturation) whereas strategic fit perspective focuses on the integration of resources in post mergers and acquisitions periods. The cultural dimension is an aspect that emphasizes on the culture related differences that may exist between parties in a merger or acquisition.

The cultural dimension complements studies on strategic and people dimensions of acquisitions the research starts from the case study of Sales and Mirvis (1984) recognized the cultural factors in acquisitions causes resistance to change whereas, Buono et al. (1985) focuses on combining different organisational cultures. Cultural research on mergers and acquisitions extended to identity and culture (Zaheer et al., 2003), employees understanding on integration process (Risberg, 2001), linking culture with knowledge transfer (Hasegawa, 2000) and with value creation (Blasko, Netter, and Sinkey, 2000).

Napier, Schweiger, and Kosglow (1993) focused on research managing cultural diversity and its importance in foreign acquisitions and Olie (1994) (2005) concluded in case studies that different national cultures increased integration problems. Furthermore, Nummela (2005) provided versatility of integration of international firms from cultural perspective, case study on national and organisational cultures explored by Santti (2001) and mergers and acquisitions failure due to close cultures analysed by Fang, Fridh, and Schultzberg (2004).

Additionally, Schoenberg, (2004) and Slangen (2006) focused on national cultural differences whereas Weber et al. (1996) focused on organisational cultural differences. Very et al. (1997) studied on the process of acculturation as well as the integration while Kavanagh & Ashkanasy, (2006) focused on learning the culture (Schweiger & Goulet, 2005). Bresman et al. (1999) studied on the transfer of knowledge and identified national cultural distance that caused misunderstandings between individuals in international acquisitions. Birkinshaw et al. (2000) unveiled the essence of conducting a proper human integration among people from the organisations with the intent of attaining the intended cultural convergence and endorse mutual

respect. Finally, Studies by Riad, (2005) and Vaara & Tienari, (2003) provided in depth analysis through the exploration of the cognitive related challenges that also includes stereotyping based on cultural dimensions. This study will focus on addressing cultural and people related dimensions through suggestion of relevant approaches that alleviate post-acquisition conflict.

2.8.1 National culture

National culture encompasses the collective programming on the mind of people that is subsequently acquired when growing within a specific geographical location (Hofstede, 1991). Such programming is then reflected in the people's core values that define one's ability to discern right or wrong, rational, or irrational, justified, and unjustified (Olie, 1994). Several studies have been expedited relating to the identification of national cultural dimensions and suggested its effects on organisational culture in terms of behaviour and structure (Trompenaars & Hampden-Turner, 1998). For instance, there are different legal or administrative systems and working styles which stems from different national cultures which affect organisational culture accordingly in that country and cause difference in values and beliefs of members of organisation when they interact with other nationals of organisations (Hofstede, 1980, 1991; House et al., 2004; Inglehart, 2004)

Empirical studies have found that in foreign acquisitions, national cultural differences can be challenging and documented that decrease in shareholder value as a result of high national cultural differences Datta and Puia (1995). Additionally, increase in complication of resource allocation and post-acquisitions integration efforts caused by national culture which is hurdle in value creation of mergers and acquisitions (Brock, 2005). Furthermore, national cultures differences caused increase in top management turnover (Krug & Nigh, 1998) and well as increase in stress levels and negative attitudes of members (Weber et al., 1996).

In contrast, several studies represent conflicting views and suggest no resistance from members in international cultures acquisitions (Larsson & Finkelstein, 1999) and no clash of national culture in international acquisitions in their samples (Very et al., 1997). Furthermore, Goulet and Schweiger (2006) implied that cultural differences is an insignificant factor that should be considered as complementary and tolerable accepted as complementary and tolerable and it may

dilute the conflict potential by giving greater attention to national cultural differences (Goulet & Schweiger, 2006).

Finally, some studies have explored on the positive issues that are associated with national cultural differences (Bjorkman, Stahl, & Vaara, 2007; Morosini et al., 1998; Slangen, 2006). Logic behind the positive effects is because different national cultures hold different Idea behind is that different national cultures stem from different set routines and acquire different sets of knowledge (Morosini et al., 1998) which will complement new structure and avoid any duplications and thus potential for synergies and knowledge transfer (Bjorkman et al., 2007; Larsson & Finkelstein, 1999; Shenkar, 2001; Larsson & Risberg, 1998).

National cultural differences provide better synergies, complementary resources, reduce overlapping and costs such as lay-offs of members from duplicate the functions could reduce post-acquisition conflict.

2.8.2 Organisational culture

Organisational culture is defined by Schein (1990) as pattern developed, invented, or developed on basic assumptions, which helps people to learn on how to cope with societal problems and adapt to external issues. Organisational culture has to be well thought of to be considered valid, be taught to new followers in a correct way to be well perceived and be seen to solve the stated problems. These elements form the assumptions providing basic dissimilarities which can be seen in different organisational cultures.

Theories on cultural dimensions on M&A stated that similar organisational cultures create better synergies and easy to integrate however different organisational cultures can cause conflict during integration of both organisations. For instance, according to the social interaction theories, stereotypical group and negative groups perceive themselves different from other groups and these differences can be generated socially to justify their old identities (Cartwright & McCarthy, 2005). Additionally, members experience difficulties working with and understanding members from different cultures (Nahavandi & Malekzadeh, 1993; Olie, 1994) and cause ambiguity and post-acquisition conflict if both firms have dissimilar understanding about other firm's culture (David & Singh, 1993). Therefore, these differences can lead to post-acquisition conflict due to cultural ambiguity and cultural dominance uncertainty (Datta, 1991). Furthermore, firms with different

culture likely to cause conflict when both firms clear about cultural dominance due to members struggle to integrate with new members from different culture (Cartwright & Cooper, 1996).

Empirical study of David and Singh (1993) supports the theoretical arguments of post-acquisition conflict due to organisational cultural difference. This is also supported by Elsass and Veiga (1994) and Weber et al. (1996) who concluded less cooperation from members due to the rise in tension, stress, anxiety, lower engagement, and negative energies that emanate from cultural differences. Similar results showed decreased trust and cooperation by Bijlsma-Frankema (2001) in integration phase. Additionally, Weber and Camerer (2003) stated increased conflict and mistaken blame due to organisational cultural differences. Furthermore, Yu, Engleman, and Van de Ven (2005) demonstrated that persistent cultural differences in a post-acquisition are a cause for conflict.

2.8.3 Acculturation

Despite the studies that focus on cultural differences in acquisition field, there are factors that still need consideration during integration process, so the theory of acculturation will identify these cultural factors.

Acculturation encompasses cultural changes that arise between parties after cultural contact as characterized by dominance of one group over other (Berry, 1980). Acculturation theory originates from the fields of anthropology and intercultural psychology.

The theory is stem from social movement theory provides an elucidation on how immigrants are able to acculturate in their new host country. Since 1980s, this theory has increasingly been applied to organisational level as well (Monin, 2002). Acculturation can be physical or symbolic and can occur at individual level as well as group level. Furthermore, domestic, and international acquisitions generate high acculturation intensity (Monin, 2002) therefore; this theory is relevant to cultural integration of two firms as a result of acquisition event to assess the behaviour of members.

In contrast, some studies taking the view of acculturation differently and suggest that success or failure of integration is depend upon the nature of relationship between two merging firms and not dependent upon their cultural differences (Birkinshaw et al., 2000; Very et al., 1997). However, acculturation process derived several factors that can impact post-acquisition integration and subsequently defines the outcome. Nahavandi & Malekzadeh, 1988; (1993) documented different

factors that relate to acculturation theory, which included multiculturalism, cultural preservation, and partner attractiveness.

2.8.4 Multiculturalism of firms

Multiculturalism is defined as the extent to which an entity is able to accommodate people from different cultural orientations, a move that requires that the host organisation values diversity (Nahavandi & Malekzadeh, 1988).

2.8.13. Acquiring firm's multiculturalism effects

There are theories who argue that acquiring a company will create the essence of multiculturalism, which has the potential of reducing the post-acquisition conflict, but it may be commonly be met with non-conformity due to cultural differences with the target firm (Chatterjee, et al., 1992). In addition, the acquiring company may oblige a high level of integration even in instances where low level of integration is needed (Datta & Grant, 1990). Hence, multiculturalism can boost multidirectional flow of cultural elements where unclear direction on cultural elements can be associated to post-acquisition conflict (Sales & Mirvis, 1984) thus; multidirectional flows could ultimately reduce the level of post-acquisition conflicts. In contrast, multiculturalism can raise post-acquisition conflict if employees of target firm feel acquiring firm's culture difficult to understand and experience acquiring firm's culture fragmented, ambiguous and conflicting. As a result, increase in uncertainty due to feeling stressful in post-acquisition period (Cartwright & Cooper, 1990; Datta, 1991). Acquiring firm's multiculturalism could also cause an enhancement in doubt and negative personnel reactions in post-acquisition period as a result of potentially unclear leadership of acquiring firm.

2.8.14. Target firm's multiculturalism effects

The idea of target firm's multiculturalism is originating from cultural strength and cohesion literature. Nahavandi and Malekzadeh (1988) considers multiculturalism only in the acquiring firm however it could also be relevant in the target firm. Employees of target firms with weaker and less cohesive culture cause lower level of post-acquisition conflict and less resistance to change because they are more likely to despair their culture and identities (Cartwright & Cooper, 1993; Haunschild, Moreland, & Murrell, 1994; Sales & Mirvis, 1984). Therefore, target firm's

multiculturalism is a potential cause for post-acquisition conflict because the target firm is less likely to demonstrate cultural strength and build cohesion in comparison to a disorganized culture.

2.8.5 Organisational cultural preservation

Organisational cultural preservation originates from social identity theory and it encompasses the extent to which members in an organisation preserve their already developed culture (Nahavandi & Malekzadeh, 1988). Under this theory, organisation's culture becomes group identity and members intend to protect their culture as well as hold on to their original identity (Sales & Mirvis, 1984; Haunschild et al., 1994; Sidle, 2006) and members likely to preserve the cultural identity even when there are eminent threats including job loss (Sidle, 2006).

2.8.16. Acquiring firm's cultural preservation

Acquiring firm's cultural preservation is also relevant in post-acquisitions (Nahavandi and Malekzadeh, 1988). Firstly, because culture in acquiring firm requires changes as a result of integration with target firm's new or shared culture. If acquiring firm wants to preserve their own culture and impose its culture to target firm, it will create hurdle in creating new shared culture with target firm (Larsson & Lubatkin, 2001; Siehl & Martin, 1981). Also, acquiring firm's cultural preservation could possibly lead to the idea of dominance and protecting its own culture where this could lead to sending negative signal to target firm as if acquiring firm's culture is superior (Marks & Mirvis, 2001). Therefore, target firm is likely to react negatively, and this can lead to increased post-acquisition conflict.

2.8.17. Target firm's cultural preservation

In most of the cases, acquiring firm dominates and imposes its culture on target firm's culture. Therefore, it can be stated that target firm's cultural preservation can increase post-acquisition conflict (Sales & Mirvis, 1984).

Qualitative studies suggest that target firm's cultural preservation can lead to negative people reactions where members treat their group members fairly and supportive however unfair to other group members which can cause increased post-acquisition conflict (Haunschild et al., 1994). Similarly, target firm's cultural preservation can prevent culture from integration effectively (Elsass and Veiga, 1994) and defined as the main antecedents for post-acquisition conflict (Sales

and Mirvis, 1984). However, target firm's cultural preservation has not been quantitatively tested in mergers and acquisitions field.

2.8.6 Attractiveness of partner

Attractiveness of partner refers to the degree to which an organisation can maintain a positive perception between the partners involved in the acquisition (Buono & Bowditch, 1989; Sales & Mirvis, 1984). This factor can affect the level of post-acquisition conflict firstly because, if the new firm's culture is attractive, then members will accept the new culture and likely to abandon their old one (Haunschild et al., 1994). However, members are more likely to reject the culture if new partner's culture quality is uncertain or it seems inferior therefore these conditions can lead towards increasing post-acquisition conflict (Haunschild et al. (1994).

Additionally, members of firms think that acquisition will have negative effects on their personal image as well as firm's reputation Empson (2001) is referred to as fear of contamination. Having an attractive partner can reduce the fear of contamination however, this can be very difficult to justify and can cause post-acquisition conflict (Empson, 2001).

2.8.19. Acquiring firm's attractiveness

Target firm ascertain that acquiring firms will dominate its culture and it has to adjust or modify its culture according to requirements of acquiring firm's culture based on how attractive the culture of the acquiring company is as per the original model of Nahavandi and Malekzadeh (1988). So therefore, according to empirical studies such as Nahavandi & Malekzadeh (1988) the acquiring firm's culture and its attractiveness is very important in mergers and acquisitions which could potentially reduce the post-acquisition conflict (Birkinshaw et al., 2000).

2.8.20. Target firm's attractiveness

The attractiveness of the target firm is as much important as the attractiveness of the acquiring firm and both acquiring firm and target firm may need some amendment to their culture to potentially reduce the post-acquisition conflict and likely to increase the chances of successful integration. The changes in both firms' cultures are particularly important if both firms wanted to achieve and build completely new culture which is shared among them (Larsson & Lubatkin, 2001; Siehl & Martin, 1981).

In contrast, acquiring firm may be reluctant to make any amendments in its culture if target firm's culture is unattractive perceived by acquiring firm. Subsequently, it may impose its own culture on target firm without consideration of possible strengths existed in target firm's culture (Sarala, 2010). Similarly, post-acquisition successful integration is dependent upon the acquiring firm's perception toward target firm's cultural attractiveness Cartwright and Cooper (1993) hence; target firm's cultural attractiveness can reduce the post-acquisition conflict.

2.8.7 Levels of Acculturation

Acculturation arises when there are contacts between entities that have autonomous culture (Berry, 1980). The contact between the two organisations can result to a balance in culture, which rarely occurs especially when the culture of one firm dominates over the other in a strong way, causing a directional change in culture. Scholars have also studied that cultural conflicts originate from modernization of culture, which are less prone compared to mispositioning of the dominant culture (Berry, 1983). Further, such engagements result in use of force, which also cause resistance and ultimately cause undesirable effect on the M & A process.

2.8.8 Modes of acculturation

The modes of acculturation are defined by a fourfold model, which is a bilinear model that categorizes the different acculturation strategies based on two dimensions (Berry, 1997). Dominance and ethnicity are common aspects that are witnessed in cultural issues, which are negative aspects that are associated with retention or rejection of the native culture through change of identity and character. Dominance may entail the adoption or rejection of the dominant culture or acceptance of what is accepted by the larger society (Berry, 1997).

- **Assimilation** takes place when people manage to adopt cultural norms of the dominant culture over the against culture.
- **Separation** occurs when people desist the dominant host culture but rather preserve the culture of their origin. Separation is facilitated by immigration to ethnic based enclaves.
- **Integration** is witnessed when individuals accept the dominant culture norms, which is in line with the culture of origin. This is similar to biculturalism.
- **Marginalization** occurs when people reject the culture of origin as well as the dominant culture.

Scholars have suggested that individual respective acculturation strategy may have a difference in the private and public life (Arends et al., 2004). For example, one may fail to accept the norms and values that are exhibited through the dominant culture in his private life (separation) but accept the dominant culture in the public life, which depicts assimilation or integration on public.

2.8.9 Acculturative Stress

Acculturative stress entails the psychological state of a person that collectively affects the organisational members, which is characterized by mild pathological disruptive behaviour (Berry, 1980), commonly resulting from the cultural contact among parties in an M&As process. According to Nahavandi and Malekzadeh (1988), acculturative stress is related with the compatibility of acculturation mode and successful integration. The acculturative stress will likely to be lowers if both firms and their members agree on acculturation mode, as a result reduction in post-acquisition conflict. However, if members do not agree on the acculturation mode, a high level of acculturative stress will occur which will affect negatively on conflict resolution and leading towards disruption in individual and group functioning (Nahavandi & Malekzadeh, 1988). Subsequently, rise in post-acquisition conflict.

Empirical studies investigating the impact of culture on result of M&As using acculturation modes seen that the success of the integration process particularly depends on how employees from both merging firms perceive the culture of new firm as a result of M&As (Dackert, Jackson, Brenner, & Johansson, 2003). Studies revealed that successful acculturation can occur by controlling acculturative stress using social controls and rituals through introduction programs, training, cross-visits, retreats, and celebrations by acquiring firm (Larsson & Lubatkin, 2001). Furthermore, conceptual studies have refined the model and suggest acculturative dynamics for assessment of acculturative patterns (Elsass & Veiga, 1994) by highlighting that acculturation is occur in cycles as a result of changes in post-acquisition period affected by the performance of both merging partners. This process of change in culture is also referred to as cultural change process in acculturation literature (Bijlsma-Frankema, 2001; Brooks & Dawes, 1999; Kaplan, 2001; Smith, 2000).

2.8.10 Application of Acculturation Model

Research carried on application of acculturation model ideally puts a focus on the domestic M&As but in an international scenario M&As is a complicated process due to issues of stereotyping, prejudice, and sense of nationalism among some parties (Olie, 1990; Vaara et al., 2003) which can be a cause for post-acquisition conflict, mistrust, and a decline in the level of commitment subsequently leading to acculturative stress (Rottig, 2007). For instance, it would be difficult for local target firm to completely adopt foreign acquiring firms organisational as well as national cultural characteristics (assimilation mode of acculturation) or a disintegration leading to the abandonment of own's cultural identity.

Similarly, it is not probable for the acquiring firm to allow the target firm to make a choice of the mode of separation because the most appropriate approach would be integration of culture, transfer of knowledge, resources, and capabilities as well as valuable routines. The integration should be expedited with the understanding that there are valuable routines and repertoires that are commonly embedded in the foreign culture and aid in accessing valuable specific knowledge transfer. In essence, application of the acculturation model in international acquisitions is commonly limited (Rottig, 2007, p. 102).

2.8.11 Sociocultural Integration

Sociocultural integration process not only focuses on acculturation but also incorporates international M&As cultural attributes for effective integration. Sociocultural integration is encompassed of a process of effective culture assimilation or combination of the various organisation and public cultures that result in the development of a common organisational identity that is accepted by the acquisition parties (Rottig, 2011, p. 416). Sociocultural integration plays role in cultural construct and is a major determining factor for the success of the M&As (Birkinshaw et al., 2000)

Stahl and Voigt (2008) has provided the meta-analysis of 46 studies and documented successful sociocultural integration of firms involve in M&As however a negative correlation with the cultural differences that are exhibited in organisation and ultimately examination of the cultural effect on the process of M & A. Simultaneously, on international M&As, a five-C's framework (cultural due diligence, cross-cultural communication, combination, control, and connection) for sociocultural integration developed by Rottig (2007.p. 157). The framework describes the key

determinants valuable for successful cultural combination process involving firms' structural and relational social ties and networks (Rottig, 2007). Furthermore, he developed a social capital perspective which is moderated by an acquiring firm's internal and external social capital aligned with meta-analysis of Stahl and Voigt (2008) showing negative relationship between cultural differences and successful socio-cultural integration Rottig (2011). Thus, this framework provides valuable resources that can be useful in successful socio-cultural integration process in international M&As.

Recent studies suggested that socio-cultural integration process does not merely depend on the events on post-acquisition phase but also pre-acquisition and closing phases of whole M&As spectrum Rottig (2013). Based on the idea of social constructivist approach (Berger & Luckmann, 1967) there is a clear indication that the marriage metaphor model opining that the process of socio-cultural integration is a three-phase model: the dating (pre-M&A phase), mating (closing phase), and creating (post-M&A phase) periods. However, socio-cultural integration process area not enough researched across all the phases of M&As and its consequences not much researched incorporating its importance, relevance, and possible distinct determinants.

2.8.12 Culture Identity Building

To explore M&As process (Kleppesto, 1998; Vaara, 2000), researchers built on sense-making perspective (Weick, 1995). The sense-making perspective highlights internal discussion of organisational processes as well as complex socio-psychological processes in which players in the organisation can interpret the organisational issue at hand and construction of social realities (Dutton and Jackson, 1987; O'Connell, 1998; Weick, 1995; Porac, Thomas and Baden-Fuller, 1989; Dutton and Dukerich, 1991; Gioia and Chittipeddi, 1991; Czarniawska-Joerges, 1992; Gioia and Thomas, 1996; Brown and Jones, 2000). 'Sensemaking' is a framework that helps in understanding how corporate decision making process can be expedited as characterized by uncertainty and ambiguity together with political tensions (Miller et al., 1996). Studies based on sense-making perspective recognized that success or failure of M&As is determined by perceived cultural differences by its members of firms involved in M&As rather than cultural differences itself (Vaara, 2000). Vaara stated that sensemaking approach primarily focused on the post-acquisition process when organisational managers engage in interpreting cultural differences involved in the assimilation of cultures in organisational process.

Culture identity building encompasses the process of sense-making that involves self-categorization of the members where they place themselves in either in-group or out-group category (Vaara et al., 2003) that is based on a possible cultural identity building process (1-creation of a difference, creation of a common future identity). This process is very important in understanding member's planned or anticipated changes as a result of cognitively and emotional response due to cultural differences. This process also assists in understanding of emergent force (such as enthusiasm or resistance) during integration within target firm (Vaara et al., 2003). This process expects that overall culture become compatible if members of target firm respond positively to cultural differences; however, high level of acculturative stress occurs when members affect the negative and resist the cultural changes that arise.

This process explains the interrelation between post-acquisition factors that relate to process and those context-related, which shows how post-acquisition identity building (a process factor) may determine the effect of pre-M&As cultural differences (a contextual factor) on integration process (Rottig et al., 2013).

2.8.13 Cultural Discourse

Cultural discourse is very important factor in integration of M&As which explain the process of justification of actions made or required from members of merging firms and (re)framing the success (or failure) of M&As (Vaara, 2002). Cultural discourses are considered as an opportunity where parties in an M & A can conduct reconstructions as well as reinterpretations of the post M & A cultural assimilation process. According to Rottig et al. (2013), if this is not properly addressed, it can lead to problems and affect performance in an M & A situation, which is a cause for confrontation at the different hierarchies of cultures (national to organisational levels). Cultural discourse can help to clarify the relationship that exist between contextual as well as process-based factors due to structural or situational factors could be (re)constructed or (re)interpreted by members due to cultural differences. Subsequently, this will cause acculturative stress and eventually occasion cultural conflict.

2.8.14 Talent Retention in Cultural Integration

Degree of integration between acquiring and target firms depend upon the extent of transitional change within their structures and processes. Integration between both firms can be failed due to

ineffective cultural integration. Combining two firms' cultures is very difficult task where two firms evolved two completely different cultures and each firm have their own way of response towards external and internal stimuli. In cultural integration, there can be of cultural integration either to dominate the culture of target firm or let the target firm work independently without cultural integration.

2.8.29. Adoption or adaption

Acquiring firm can allow target firm to preserve their culture and let them operate their culture separately and independently. The reason for this kind of cultural preservation might be because of a speculative finance deal where acquiring firm want to buy target firm and let them work independently to sell it in future for profit. In this case the level of integration is very minimum therefore the risk of post-acquisition conflict is very low.

However, where acquiring firms want to dominate and impose its culture over target firms and target firm either adapt or adopt the acquiring firm's culture. In these circumstances, significant proportion of members and senior leadership from target firm can leave during or after the integration process. During this cultural imposition or dominance by target firm, only leadership who adapt to the new culture or adopt the culture of target firm will be appointed. The disadvantage of this action can lead to the loss of valuable members of firm to other competitors.

According to empirical studies, cultural failure rates are higher between those firms where there is higher degree of cultural integration is required and these can be experienced in mergers of equals where members of board comprised from both firms and the structure of board is based on best management personnel from both firms. During the integration process, employees at different levels are also evaluated for appropriate positions in new firm. As a result, employees can have different types of reaction as a result of this evaluation process. Some employees might feel motivated and take this as opportunity so that they can take the advantage of the situation. However, on the other employees can feel demotivated and vulnerable in such situations where they experience anxiety, fear, and stress. This can lead to key members look out for jobs in market to secure their future and potential loss of valuable employees to competitors which can cause post-acquisition conflict. Therefore, when firms involve in mergers and acquisitions, retention of critical members and particularly considering people dimension is key to success.

2.8.15 Understanding stages of culture clash (Experiment approach)

As with companies have different products, services, and markets, similarly culture is different too. When companies merge together, each company perceive their own culture is distinct and unique from other merging partners. Employees still tend to see the cultures are distinct even if they aren't (Martin, Feldman, Hatch, & Sitkin, 1983). To achieve the desire merger goals and manage the merger process appropriately, the understanding of culture clash arises between firms when they merge together is important to deal with the cultural challenges between (Marks & Mirvis, 2010).

2.8.16 Perceive Differences.

At this first stage, people focus on reputation, products or services, leadership styles, decision making process and difference between people.

2.8.17 Magnify Differences.

Next, people begin to magnify differences that they observe. Distinctions become sharper and more polarized. This is the start of “we” versus “they” when talking about cultures.

Stereotypes.

Then people start to see and view others from the partner firm as an embodiment of their cultural practice.

Put-downs.

The clash in the norms and beliefs (culture) may get to a greater height when the partner company is considered as inferior by the other, which takes the superior position leading to denigration.

During mergers, the structural problems may arise such as centralised and decentralised control process, speed of decision making, risk taking, and results orientation are most critical when firms do cultural fit.

Cultural fit

Cartwright and cooper (1993) say that M&As failed due to incompatible cultures and suggest that the cultural fit as important as the structural fit is in evaluating the M&A deal. Chatterjee et al.,

(1992) agreed that poor cultural fit caused failure in mergers when there is obvious suitable strategic partnership. Chatterjee also insisted that investors are sensitive to the cultural fit in study of 30 M&As. Dealing with culture clash - Define a Cultural End state from Preservation, Absorption, Reverse takeover, Best of both and Transformation.

2.8.18 Systematically Learning About Partners' Cultures

Managing the Transformation of Culture

Mike Schraeder, Dennis R. Self, (2003) "Enhancing the success of mergers and acquisitions: an organisational culture perspective", Management Decision, Vol. 41 Issue: 5, pp.511-522,

Absence of framework

Cartwright and Cooper (1993) acknowledged the need for the framework of cultural fit. Further Weber (1996) insisted that cultural fit is poorly defined in M&As.

Disparate Cultures

Burton and Tanouye (1998) studied the mergers between Monsanto and American Home Products failed due to disparate cultures.

Different management styles

CEOs of Monsanto and American Home Products having different management styles and as a result the disagreement about employee layoffs and assignment of staff to headquarters. These differences could have been avoided by incorporating into integration plans (Burton and Tanouye, 1998).

Strategic fit and Unrelated Acquisitions

Porter (1987) studied the M&A, and his findings suggest that some M&A selection decisions lack logical, comprehensive, and objective evaluation of deals and explained 74% of divestiture was unrelated acquisitions.

Due Diligence and Culture fit Audit

When firms acquire others, they go through the process of due diligence and despite the importance of cultural fit, there were no knowledge firms incorporating cultural fit audit into its due diligence

process (Carleton 1997). Success rate of M&A could improve by incorporating cultural compatibility into due diligence process.

2.8.19 Culture and change management

Employee's / Management involvements in cultural change

Nadler, Thies and Nadler (2001) made scholarly suggestion that the best approach for cultural change is to engage the CEO together with the executive team as well as involving the chief architect in the change process. Cartwright and Cooper (1993) appreciating this idea by making further suggestion that employees despite their levels should actively take part in the integration or change management in a merger and acquisition. In order to deal with the issue of cultural differences, people considered in the senior management should emphasize on the promoting multiculturalism, elimination of culture collisions, as well as promote gradual adaptation of culture throughout.

Culture and Transactional leadership

Transactional leadership managing the culture needs to take into consideration the following points to make the cultural transition process smooth and successful.

Psychological protection for staff

Leadership in transition must pay attention to psychological needs of employees at managerial as well as operational levels. This ensures that

1. Employees will get personal support to mitigate the psychological issues arise due to merger
2. It will strengthen the psychological bound between the employer and the employee.

Employees often experience anxiety and stress and need support to go through the transition process and leadership roles, behaviour and attitude influence the employees during merger process (Devine and Hirsh, 1998). Similarly, Hendel (1998) conducted the study on merger of two hospital divisions and stated that most members of organisation experience grief and felt the transition process painful characterized by a loss of status identity. Hendel suggested that leaders can support employees using small group discussions, individual approach and the sharing of feelings and provide the resources. Furthermore, failure to manage the psychological expectation

of employees can affect the attitude towards the company management (Hubbard and Purcell, 2001). To avoid this happening, they suggest that leaders are mindful of the importance of:

1. Putting trust in their managerial actions
2. Put in place credible leaders.
3. Promote fairness in the actions
4. Demonstrate logic thinking on the management actions and behaviours.

2.8.20 Identify difference in culture using cultural Audit

Research suggests that leaders should pay attention to the culture fit before transition process. Cultural fit is very important for successful transition however some cultural types is more successful than others therefore, understanding cultural characteristics and its effects on merger success is very important Cartwright and Cooper (1994; 1998). Similarly, Meyerson & Martin, (1987) suggests that culture is a concept, and it should be dealt carefully however, (Parker, 2000) argued that there is an element of uncertainty whether organisational culture is amendable to leadership expectation.

Nevertheless, literature suggests suitability of cultural fit between potential merging partners should be assessed, and transition should only go ahead if there is suitable cultural fit. It highlights the areas where transition process can be affected due to culture (Tetenbaum, 1999; Ashkenas et al, 1998).

2.9 Emotions in M&A

Although the emotions are covered in literature of M&A, its existence is only fraction as compared to the general research relating to humans in M&As. Graebner et al., (2017) called for attention to emotions in M& A studies. Influence of emotions is characterized by the effects of socio-cultural processes and therefore can support or cause failure to M&A process (Brundin & Liu, 2015). Emotions determines the attitudes and behaviours of members in the process of M&As. Positive emotions have positive effects on M&A process, for example, positive emotions is a probable cause for higher motivation (Kusstatscher & Cooper, 2005), job satisfaction and commitment of members with firm (Kusstatscher, 2006) however, negative emotions lead towards fear, anger and frustration negatively affects the level of commitment (Mottolaet al., 1997) and withdrawal

(Kiefer, 2005) which can affect negatively on merger process can affect merger process negatively (Giessner, Viki, Otten, Terry, & Täuber, 2006). As a result, shifting the focus from actual problems to less constructive activities of emotion coping mechanisms (Scheck & Kinicki, 2000). Additionally, emotions determine social identifications such as positive emotions improve organisational identity and enhance the relationships among themselves and with other firms (Kusstatscher, 2006). In contrast, negative emotions harm organisational identity (Ford & Harding, 2003), trust (Kiefer, 2005), cooperation (Sinkovics, Zagelmeyer, & Kusstatscher, 2011) and lead to social conflict (Saunders, Altinay, & Riordan, 2009). Therefore, employees' actions and behaviours can be determined by emotions as essential socio-cultural mechanisms as well as the extent to which members identify themselves with socio-cultural structures and engage in social relationships (Turner & Stets, 2005). Furthermore, M&A research link positive outcome with positive emotions and vice versa however these can be more complex. For instance, positive emotions can also increase false optimism, reduces the quality of decisions by creating illusion of control and encourage the reliance on simple rules, however negative emotions can induce criticality which improve the decision making (Rhee & Yoon, 2012). Therefore, it is imperative to have an in-depth exploration of more counterintuitive as well as complex outcomes that are related to emotions in a M & As (Sarala, Vaara and Junni, 2017).

It is crucial to identify factors affecting emotions to understand its role in M&A. M&A is a major strategic process that involves intense emotions (Brundin & Liu, 2015) and as a result member experience different emotion among themselves. To understand how emotions, evolve, Appraisal theory explains the effect of social and cultural factors on the effect of emotions in a merger and acquisition arrangement (Lazarus, 1984; Strongman, 1996). It suggests that emotions originate from an ideal evaluation of their appropriateness, valence, and efficiency. From an appropriateness perspective, the essence is to determine the extent to which extent firm's current strategy will advance as a result of M&A Armenakis et al., 1999, which is also explored by Harris and Gresch (2010). Perceived validity about motive of firms involving in M&A affects appropriateness. Valence characterized by attractiveness and expectations about the real outcome of firm and its members as a result of M&A (Armenakis et al., 1999).

Higher level of power status as studied by Kemper and Collins (1990) was shown to establish intergroup boundaries, sentiments shared by Terry et al. (2001), incentives and compensation

(Ahammad et al., 2012) leads to higher valence however, but concerns on the future security still remains (Kiefer, 2005), uncertainty in functioning conditions (Kiefer, 2005), and deprivation of fairness as studied by Sinkovics et al. (2011) lessen valence. Finally, efficacy refers to the firm's key resources for the attainment of the strategic goals and addressing the social challenges that are related to the M & A (Armenakis et al., 1999; Harris & Gresch, 2010). Several factors were studied by different scholars as factors affecting efficacy on socio culture: emotional intelligence, self-efficacy (Idel et al., 2003), superior level of participation (Ullrich et al., 2005), emotional attending (Reus, 2012), together with the ability of providing social support (Gunkel et al., 2015) (Salleh, 2009).

For instance, employees of Lotus wanted to leave as a result of IBM acquiring Lotus fearing layoffs and dominance (Chaudhuri, 2005). But IBM's leadership visited Lotus and explained the rationale behind the acquisition (appropriateness). The company also retained primary organisational management positions and introduced appropriate remuneration plans as well as the key resources that are needed for an integration process (Chaudhuri, 2005). Communication is key as it acts as signal on the appropriateness of the compensation plan, the efficacy, and determinant of the emotional members (Zagelmeyer et al., 2016).

Therefore, emotions provide a socio-cultural mechanism that provides connection with human factors such as status, personality, power, fairness, HR practices and social support that affects the behaviours, attitudes, and eventually social M& A outcomes.

Sensemaking is way forward to highlight the integrative emotions in M&A theories. Emotions arise through a complex process of individual cognitive evaluations and members from and within the target and acquiring firms may have different emotions. As per the practice approach, strategic processes such as M&A emerge powerful emotions at different phases within the organisations (Brundin & Liu, 2015). Therefore, members at each level make cognitive appraisals of M&A strategy and resources assessment. Leadership at middle level face more challenges because of bridging the gap between the senior leadership and labour (Clarke & Salleh, 2011). The focus is moved from top management to individual level and emotional process including different aspects and features at different levels and become dynamic in M&As. In case of health care mergers by Ford and Harding (2003), members from both firms were optimistic immediately after the merger as they perceived that it would help the organisation together with the employees with the right

opportunity. However, during the integration process, members felt dejected and agitated that the firm has lost the humour of its culture and they had sacrificed too much of themselves. There is need of further work in socio-cultural area to identify the different outcomes as a result of dynamic emotions.

Emphasis on individual members explores the role of emotions at micro level antecedents however these can also be conceived at collective level. Social theory stem from the idea where emotions originate from the experience with others (Strongman, 1996). Sensemaking interlink these emotions at individual as well as organisational level (Stensaker & Falkenberg, 2007). Members' reactions and intensification or deintensification in M&As as a result of collective emotions shared among group members (Von Scheve & Ismer, 2013) which include collective uncertainty and collective excitement (Grodal & Granqvist, 2014). Sanchez- Burks and Huy, (2009) explains that is important to understand the formations of shared emotions and their response in a group to manage the change process characterized by Emotional aperture

However, role of collective emotions and emotions capabilities in M&A and their relationship with other collective level construct (role of media, national culture, and firm culture in forming emotions) is underexplored (Sarala, Vaara and Junni, 2017). Furthermore, the relationship between individual emotions (field of psychology) and collective emotions and emotional capabilities (cognitive and sociological process) requires further research in M&A literature (Sarala, Vaara and Junni, 2017).

Furthermore, managing emotions in M&A depend on the contextual factors such in cultural context, social beliefs system prevents individual from adding different meaning to their predefined activities and roles (Golsorkhi et al., 2015), which was in consistent with Lounsbury and Crumley (2007). For example, in study of merger of banks in Brunei by Clarke and Salleh (2011), the emotions of managers influence M&A guided by their beliefs that they have to endure the acquisition patiently and show gratitude. Similarly, emotional attending (ability to consider and care for emotions) can be different based on cultural context. Reus (2012) experienced reduced emotional commitment in different international cultures conducted on the US based acquirers. Also, expression of emotions also differs in different cultural settings and affects the member of firms accordingly. Countries likely to expect suppression of emotions where status and power culture exist (Matsumoto, Yoo, & Nakagawa, 2008). However, US firms adjusted their emotional

attending according to the cultural context such as increased level of emotional attending in high level of people-oriented culture (Reus, 2012).

Research in socio-economic context suggests that members in under-developed countries trigger positive emotions as a result of M&As. Members of target firm from under-developed economies perceived development in personal skills and career (increased valance) because of acquiring firm from developed country (Paustian-Underdahl et al., 2017).

Research in field of emotions within different industries is lacking and I can be different according to characteristics of different industries in M&As. For example, high-tech industries are subject to radical changes as compared to traditional sectors such as retail or manufacturing. Subsequently, employees working in technological firms are more contented with expedited change and having more abilities to deal with drastically changing environment of their firms in M&As. Additionally, emotions are different based on gender; women show sadness as low-activation emotions as compared to men which show anger as high-activating emotions (Strongman, 1996) therefore, industries with skewed gender emotions distributions such as nursing profession that is female dominated and an investment banking field- a male dominated.

Finally, occupational emotions forms as a part of professional identity (Salmela, 2014) where conflict can arise when employees feel disgruntled because of M&A situation while performing their duties. Therefore, observing how emotional dynamics is embedded may necessitate a comparative research design that cuts across the different countries and industries (Sarala, Vaara and Junni, 2017).

2.10 Effective Communication

Communication is an essential tool for the M & A process. It is through communication that parties in an acquisition can deliver information on the extent of engagement, implication of the process, promote motivation, enhance level of engagement as well as instil the sense of belonging among the parties (Welch & Jackson, 2007). Communication also provides basis for the emotional expression among the parties. Communication in an M & A can be either formal or informal and or exhibit an upward or a downward phenomenon. Guirdham (2002) explains that parties in a merger can source information from different sources including specific individuals, known employees, or even anonymous people. An ideal and effective communication should have the

necessary frequency and continuity (Angwin et al., 2016), be consistent (Hubbard & Purcell, 2001) exhibit the necessary honesty (Bastien, 1987), involve parties with openness (Zagelmeyer et al., 2016), and collegiality (Bastien, 1987).

Communication in a M & A takes different stages. During the pre-qualification stage, the process is characterized by the need to alleviate fears and concerns (Tanure & Gonzalez- Duarte, 2007) while in the post-acquisition phase, the communication is intended at motivating employees through providing support and enhance positive attitudinal and behavioural outcomes (Chaudhuri & Tabrizi, 1999) and commitment (Angwin et al., 2016). Communication can be manipulated depending on the interests of the involved parties, their backgrounds, level of experience, and their attitudes when sending information.

M&As cause uncertainty and ambiguity about organisation and its future among employees which may be seeming as vulnerable (Amiot et al., 2006). As a result, employees look out for information about the deal and its effects for their employment (McClurg, 2002). Communication enables employees to formulate and develop their expectations through an appropriate sensemaking process depending on how such information is conveyed. On the contrast, lack of communication would mean employees rely on unverified information. According to Hubbard and Purcell (2001), communication helps in building framework for future managerial actions depending on the interpretation by the management. Nonetheless, this cannot be attained in absence of information because employees tend to make interpretation based on relayed data (Lotz & Donald, 2006, p. 3). Furthermore, employees should also get unambiguous information, but such should be marked with clarity to avert any misinterpretation (Risberg, 1997). Indeed, clear, and honest information is a key success factor for a M & A engagement (Van Dick, Ullrich, and Tissington, 2006).

Communication improves the perceptions of fairness as well as procedural and interactional justice among employees (Lotz & Donald, 2006) and acceptance for change thus, better commitment from employees (Klendauer and Deller, 2009). Relevant communication can manage employees' expectations which can interpret their psychological contract with firm (Hubbard and Purcell, 2001). Vaara and Monin (2010) focus on leadership aspects of communication for discursive legitimization of an M&A which can be used to yield particular behaviours from employees to support the process of cultural integration and development (Soderberg, 2012). Communication is a key contributor to the socio-cultural outcome of the cultural assimilation as noted by (Evans et

al., 2011) and enhances trust-building (Stahl et al. 2011), supports attainment of strategic goals including knowledge transfer (Ranft & Lord, 2002) and ultimately sustenance of the acquisition/merger (Angwin et al., 2016).

2.10.1. Emotions in communication

Information related to M&A processes needs to be devoid of unverified information, especially among colleagues as it is a trigger to emotional response. The Affective events theory (AET) posits that certain situations that relate to working environment may trigger pleasant or unpleasant reactions. Such emotions can have an effect on behaviours including changes in the employee's attitudes (Ashkanasy et al., 2000; Weiss & Cropanzano, 1996).

Emotions are commonly associated with group thinking but it is imperative to understand that they originate from individual emotions (Lazarus, 1995) hence the such cannot be dissociated with group-level processes in line with SIT (social identity theory) (Hogg & Terry, 2000; Ullrich et al., 2005). The SIT provides for an understanding of the various emotional dimensions in an acquisition for two group identities. According to the SIT, the level of group identification influences employee commitment, impacts on the level of readiness and the willingness of the parties to adopt or abandon the culture- which represents the emotional process of M & As (Ellemers, Spears, & Doosje, 2002; Terry, Carey, & Callan, 2001).

According to cognitive appraisal approach, employees' emotions are rarely affected by the actions of managers' actions but influenced by how communication appraisal is conducted (Frijda, 2008). However, the interpretation and giving meanings to these emotions is very important and the managerial communication effects on employees' emotions. In contrast, Liu and Perrewé (2005) stated that different stages of changes process trigger different emotional responses which affects the behaviours and attitudes of employees. Also, change process can trigger negative emotions which can cause withdrawal behaviour and trust issues during M&As Kiefer (2005).

Sinkovics et al. (2011) developed framework on role played by emotions in international M&As where he explained employees' actions influenced by three sets of independent variables or contextual factors, namely communication, management behaviour and other M&A-related factors which triggers emotions which then affects the behaviours and attitudes of employees. However, Gunkel et al. (2015) tested this model and found no significant correlation between

managerial communication and the level of employee feelings or dissatisfaction and insecurity during an M&A.

2.11 Organisational Change Management

Firms have to go through process of integration during M&As and as a result changes are inevitable however, changes become more complicated when firms belong to two different cultures and backgrounds and their systems are different which make changes more difficult due to increasing unpredictability and changing environment (Ulrich, 1997). M&A is considered to be the most complex organizational changes experienced by employees during transition phases. M&As often have negative consequences for both firms because of different cultural (Hofstede, 1980), and as a result involve in cultural clash international M&As (Chakrabarti et al., 2009), and work alienation for employees (Brannen & Peterson, 2009). Employees go through anxiety and distress as a result of change process of interacting of different organizational and national cultures. Implementing a change is a challenging process as change projects (integration of two firms as a result of M&As) having a failure rate of 70–90% (Keney, 2020) which are alarming and therefore require careful management integration process during M&As. Moreover, studies on global M&As have primarily focused on resolving macro-level factors of M&A integration such as governance system, and strategic issues however overlooking micro level factors or soft issues such as culture, communication, leadership, employee stress and anxiety which affect the integration as a result of M&A (Larsson and Lubatkin, 2001). Although some studies have brought attention to soft issues such as such as cultural learning intervention and communication initiative (Stahl et., all, 2013, Vaara, 2012; Schweiger and Denisi, 1991; Schweiger and Goulet, 2005), however in-depth analysis and investigation required which involve multidimensional approach to provide a mechanism through which change as a result of M&A lead to favourable outcomes.

Organisational change in different functions within organisation a result of M&A cover wide range of literature, such as innovation (Van de Ven, Angle & Poole, 2000), IS integration (Toppenberg & Henningsson, 2013), IT integration (Kovela and Skok,2015) processes (Weick and Quinn, 1999), structural and communication-based change and interventions (Steigenberger, 2016) human factors (Cooper and Tarba, 2016; Hajro, 2015; Stahl et al., 2013) emotion (Graebner et al., 2017, Kiefer, 2002, Brundin & Liu, 2015), communication (Duncan N. Angwin, Kamel Mellahi, Emanuel Gomes and Emmanuel Peter, 2016) and among many others. As a result of M&A, the

transformation of both firms into a new requires change management which leads to the integration of both firms. The efficiency of this changing project or processes is measured by integration costs and duration of integration processes and effectiveness is achieved if appropriate synergies are obtained (according to the 2+2=5 formula). From a change management point of view, synergy is dependent on organisational identity preservation with respect to integration of cultures between the two firms as a result of M&As. Ideally, successful integration can only be achieved if both firms form a new culture at the same time preserving their own culture running smoothly within the new organisation.

Firms must focus on the successful integration activities as a result of change as this is the most complex and complicated stage and whole success of the change project is based on the successful M&A integration. There is no perfect framework which can be generally applied to all firms however it can vary according to the nature and complexity of M&A integration between the two merging firms. Successful integration management can be divided into five generic sectors of the merging firms as shown in the following figure.

Figure 2.2: M&A-Integration Management (Reiss, 2013)

Organisational change process can affect many areas within the merging firms such as culture, HMRC, leadership, IT/IS and structures and processes as depicted in the above figure.

2.11.1 Organisational Structure and Change

An organizational structure is a system that consist of different processes and the way certain activities or processes are performed and directed in order to achieve organisational goals. These

processes can include rules, job roles, responsibilities and the way certain activities and operations are performed within the organisation. The organizational structure determines how information flows from one unit to another and within the organisation. For example, if organisation have a centralized structure, the decisions and information flow will follow top-down approach and while information flow use bottom-up approach in a decentralized structure. Organizational structure consists of five elements: job design, departmentation, delegation, span of control and chain of command which comprise an organizational chart and create the organizational structure.

2.11.1.1 Forms of Organizational Structures

Organizational have different structures based on their goals and divided into three broad categories firstly vertically integrated functional structure or vertically integrated divisional structure, secondly mix of vertical and horizontal such as matrix structure and finally boundary-less which also referred to as "open boundary" structure. In M&As, firms should understand the structures of each other before they devise the strategy. Particularly the processes involved, decision making and how employees work within the particular structure. Their willingness to change and if there is any training that would require to make changes in day-to-day work. For merging firms, it would be complicated if one organisation follows centralised structured and other follows decentralised structure of decision making. Merging two different structure would require appropriate planning and employees involve for successful integration strategy. Employees in decentralised structure face difficulties when new firms would require different process of decision making.

2.11.1.2 Managing Structural Change

Structural integration refers to the combination of formerly distinct organizational units, processes and structures merged or dissolved into the same organizational unit, process, or structure as a result of M&As (Paruchuri et al. 2009; Haspeslagh and Jemison 1991; Puranam et al. 2006). One of the reasons for M&As are removing the unnecessary processes and structures and make them more efficient by dissolving the inefficient units or processes. In particular, the focus is on the coordination between bidding and target firms' units, reorganisation of processes and structures created by structural integration and combination of processes and different units. However, grouping of organizational units and structural integration is different from linking mechanisms between organizational units (Thompson, 1967; Nadler and Tushman, 1998; Galbraith, 1977).

This changing strategy is very important decision needs to be made by management in relation to the structures. Normally organisations have two choices either complete absorption or preservation of separate and autonomous organizational units and structures which can potentially impact the overall project of integration between two firms as a result of M&As (Ranft and Lord, 2002; Zollo and Singh, 2004, Haspeslagh and Jemison, 1991; Pablo 1994). Structural integration results in coordination effect between merging partners which is very important if there is interdependence between the structures of both merging partners exist (Thompson, 1967). These Interdependence between target and bidding firms across different units determines how value will be created (Haspeslagh and Jemison, 1991). If these interdependencies are higher, the coordination between the bidding and target firms will be higher and vice versa which will result in employees need of change, better integration, reduced disruptions, and efficient structural changes (Brown and Eisenhardt, 1997; Galunic and Eisenhardt, 2001; Karim and Mitchell, 2004). Therefore, sound decisions should be made in relation to structural integration by creating interdependencies and coordination among the units so that efficient integration can be achieved.

2.11.1.3 Interdependence and Structural Integration

Coordination among employees is very important as it helps flow of information within and across different structures and units of organisations so that firms can achieve its goals. It is not only help smooth integration during change process but also helps individuals to adequately anticipate each other's actions and adjust their own actions accordingly. Furthermore, another important aspect of communication where members from both firms decide how to divide the tasks and job roles between themselves to ensure that the results of each individual efforts can be combined effectively to achieve the goals of both integrating firms (Gulati et al., 2005; Grant, 1996). There must be coherence and agreement between the members of both firms so that they know the common goal to achieve eventually. These coherence and agreement can be conducted by the management which enable members from both firms to reach a state of agreement on issues and increase coordination among them (Thompson, 1967; Galbraith, 1977; March and Simon, 1958). For successful integration, firms should encourage informal coordination and communication between the members based on common goal and agreement for discourse followed by the formal coordination and communication process driven by structural integration. These measures can help to encourage

positive relationship and interdependence between the acquiring and target firms and likelihood of structural integration can be increased as a result of these measures (Paruchuri et al., 2009). Therefore, firms must look out for coordination activities and develop the processes which boost interdependencies between the employees of acquiring and target firms as it can effectively aid structural integration as a result of change process of M&As.

2.11.2 Power, Politics, Change and Conflict

Organizational politics refers to self-interest of individuals within organization without proper consideration how those interests affect organizational quest to achieve its objectives (Gotsis and Kortezi, 2011, Allen et al., 1979). Power is mean to “the production, facilitation or maintenance of particular outcomes, processes, or social relations (Cooper,1994, p. 452). The power of an organisation exists in a strong relationship due to its valuable resources, knowledge, values, and culture it possesses which gives firms a competitive advantage over other firms. ((Enrique Bigné, Blesa, Küster and Andreu, 2004). Politics, change, and power are intertwined together as politics depend on how power plays at any organization as a result of change process (Weissenberger-Eibl and Teufel, 2011), The use of power within the firms affect the change management that determine the effective integration process. These political powers can be legitimate power, expert power, coercive power, referent power, and reward power (Field, 2011).

Organization during merger or acquisition environment must adopt behaviours that inject positive political behaviour. In M&As, employees protect their own interests and therefore, change management can be difficult as a result of employees’ politics which can jeopardise the whole change and integration process as a result, this can cause integration problems and affect the success of M&As. Members are subject to take pressure from different sources such as external and internal stakeholders therefore, engaging in micro-politics (Rees and Edwards 2009). Some members struggle due to change process of integration as a result high turnover rate for merging firms (Angwin 2004b). The issues of change, politics and power become much more complicated and cause conflicts when firms involve in international M&As deals where employees are from different nationalities and possess different organisational cultures (Quah & Young 2005). The application of power in these circumstances can be either coercive or collaborative and both options can have positive and negative impacts on the employees, which can affect managing change process as a result of integration ((Enrique Bigné, Blesa, Küster and Andreu, 2004)). Some

employees perceive the change process of integration as political and negative. As a result, they can feel anxiety and become distressed, demotivated and less productive which result turnover of key members from the firms. Members' perceptions of these political environments can cause stress (Cropanzano, Howes, Grandey, & Toth, 1997; Ferris et al., 1996) which can negatively affect organizational change process of M&As which firms involved to improve its financial performance. Organizations are political in nature (March, 1962; Pfeffer & Salancik, 1974), and members work to gain power and use politics to affect the change processes during transition period, which explain employees' sensemaking processes (Vaara and Monin, 2010). As the change process unfolds, each employee's perception about the reality and cognitive framework is shaped, and, in turn, affects the stress experienced during integration phase caused by change process.

2.11.2.1 Political and power sensemaking

Sensemaking and critical sensemaking (CSM) may help to understand the processes underlying change and its power and political structure for the desired outcome (Weick, 1995; Thurlow and Helms Mills, 2015). It may be difficult to rationalize the changing priorities of the members of the organisations, their changing job roles, and a changing mission as a result of organisational change process (Fiss and Zajac, 2006). It accounts for how members in both firms interpret the integration as change process and how this process can affect them individually and collectively. M&As integration might be the result of negotiations, compromise and collective sensemaking instead of strategic decision. The news of M&As will be processed by the employees as it can affect their cognitive framework, their minds engage in sensemaking based on the historical event to create meaning surrounding the change. Group of members sharing collective views towards underlying effects of change on them individually and collectively as a result of M&As can form collective decisions which can affect the integration between the two firms as change process (Vaara, 2003). Leadership or supervisors can affect the collective sensemaking process using structural intervention (Monin et al., 2013; Vaara and Monin, 2010). This can affect employees positively or negatively and members can in return affect the leadership. The reasons behind exerting pressure which can affect based on various factors which can depend on the complexity of change and its effects on employees. For instance, if tendency to preserve the individual culture is strong within can negatively affect the structural changes specially in the firms where cultural integration is one of the main objectives (Drori et al., 2013). To resolve this, middle managers considered key

facilitator of the integration which can negotiate using communication and by promoting discourse to bring all parties to an agreement (Harwood and Chapman 2009; Meyer, 2006). To understand the changing environment, employees understand incoming information through values, beliefs, and currently held knowledge as their cognitive framework that is built-up from the events over the period of time and working in firms (Weick, 1995). Sensemaking process processed when members feel anxiety and stress if merger announcement cannot be rationalized based on their existing cognitive frameworks (Monin et al., 2013).

Organisational processes such as job or work distribution, hierarchies of autonomy (Muhammad, 2007) through which organizational politics lenses can be viewed and relationships between management, supervisors, and members (Gadot, 2009) trust between supervisor and employees and their willingness to resolves problems (Sheard et al., 2011), within merging firms explain the level of politics and power involved. Positive relationship between the members and facilitators such as supervisors will help efficient change management processes and vice versa (Aral et al., 2010). Leadership should encourage members showing optimistic view about of organizational change and ensure members are provided with opportunities so that they can process this information with their exiting cognitive framework (provided firms already providing the feasible environment) as this can help members to mitigate unproductive stress and optimism can help highlight the positive aspects of the changing environment as a result of M&As (DeGhetto, Russell and Ferris, 2017). Changes at board level can also result of at great uncertainty for members as they might be feeling stressed about working with unknown leadership or working at new place with new people. The uncertainty about their potential to influence on new firm's culture and people might be reduced as they feel less powerful and their limited ability to achieve their personal goals. Failure to identify and manage organizational political and sense making process and identifying power networks within integrating firms can be detrimental to any kind of change as a result of M&As.

2.11.3 Learning, Knowledge and Innovation and Change

Knowledge can be gained and realized through research and development (R&D) however knowledge within the firms is embedded socially and dispersed across the firms involved in M&As (Brown and Duguid 1991). As a result of change, knowledge required sharing among different parts of the firms. Such knowledge sharing and its transfer (Carlile 2004, Hansen and Lovas 2004)

is an important source of firm innovation and competitive advantage (Galunic and Rodan 1998, Rosenkopf and Nerkar 2001, Tsai 2001, Miller et al. 2007). Structural recombination on subsequent innovation quality is positively related to high knowledge coherence and resources (Karim and Kaul, 2015).

Changes in structures meaning changes in business units as well as restructuring and channelising the existing knowledge resources within the firms and instead going for the difficult options to acquire new knowledge resources or dissipating the original bases of the knowledge exiting within the organisation and bringing knowledge together by removing the structural boundaries so that information can be shared smoothly (Paruchuri et al., 2009; Carlile and Reberich, 2003; Carlile, 2004; Tushman and Katz, 1980; Brown and Duguid, 2001). Similarly having less structural boundaries enable firms to have efficient communication and improve the decision making between the merging firms (Cardinal et al., 2011; Argyres, 1996; Argyres and Silverman, 2004; Hargadon and Bechky, 2006). There are several factors which can affect organisational learning and knowledge such as change as a result of merging different cultures (Olav-Eikeland, 2011) however, there is a positive correlation between organization learning processes and change management (Field, 2011), with performance and growth and productivity as a result of M&As (Olav-Eikeland, 2011). Learning is an essential part of any firm's innovation (de Weerd-Nederhof, Pacitti, da Silva Gomes and Pearson, 2002).

Firms' structures and processes exist which enable the flow of the information and integration of knowledge and learning across different units within the organisation (Karim, 2012; Szulanski, 1996) however, it can be difficult to transfer the knowledge as a result of change process (Brown and Duguid, 2001) therefore, firms structures prove are not sufficient in to achieve the full potential required synergies as a result of change process of M&As (Samina Karim, Aseem Kaul 2014). Reasons such it may not be efficient (Grant 1996) and higher cost involved in maintaining knowledge links (Hansen 2002). The design of organisational structures cause difficulties for new knowledge to embed (Brown and Duguid, 2001; Kogut and Zander, 1996). Also, some members in firms have limited understanding of knowledge and information sits within the different units and therefore, unable to take advantage of it (Nerkar and Paruchuri, 2005). Furthermore, transfer of knowledge can also be difficult due to politics and power involved during changing process (Kellogg et al. 2006; Carlile, 2004; Reberich, 2003) and sharing knowledge would compromise

their performance (Porter 1987). Last but not least, knowledge shared among other units less valuable which cause ambiguity (Thompson 1967, Van de Ven et al. 1976).

In order to successfully manage the change process, firms should realize the potential for knowledge recombination and knowledge transformation across different units within the firms (Kogut and Zander, 1996; Grant, 1996). Establishing common ground which promote interdependencies among members of both firms and use knowledge to coordinate those interdependence that is shared and known to be shared within different unit of the organisation (Clark 1996). Interdependencies and effective knowledge transformation can help members to increase the coordination (Becker and Murphy, 1992; Chwe, 2001; Schelling, 1960) thereby avoiding the disruptive consequences of change. Structural integration can disrupt the target firm's innovative capabilities because it can change the autonomous status which can lowered motivation and productivity of employees and they could potentially leave the target firm after they are structurally integrated which can negatively affect the target firm's innovation capacity (Ernst and Vitt 2000). Changes in decision making structures, job roles and practices can cause disruption, however, cross-unit teams and integration managers which can develop the bridge between management and employees to preserve the structural autonomy and communication with employees to stop demotivation can result in less disruptions. There should also be informal organizational processes that aid knowledge transfer, informal communications, and group identity (Moran and Ghoshal, 1996). It can also be useful for strengthening knowledge if structural integration also results in stronger coordination between the acquiring and target firm members. The successful factor of merger of JustEat and Takeaway was that they have introduced the online and social speed networking groups which helps employees to have informal communications which helps them to feel like a family, increased coordination and share the knowledge among themselves. The role of enablers and inhibitors which can communicate dynamics of change with the members of organisation and promote sensemaking which can make sense with cognitive framework of members and share knowledge across units efficiently which boost innovation within the organisation. As identified by the Bessant (2013), there are five key organisational and leadership competencies which are very important for the successful transformation as a result of change process. These competencies include recognition of the challenge, determination of a transformational strategy, demand and support extensive innovation, manage systemic change, and

upgrade leadership processes. These qualities can help reducing the disruptions during change process and aid in efficient integration as a result of M&As.

2.11.4 Participation and Change management

In M&As, authors conceptualize top-down processes where decisions made at top levels in acquiring firms. At pre-acquisition stage, decisions are limited to small groups however, in post-acquisition period, organisations required broad range of engagement and participation for successful integration. Therefore, practice perspective focuses on the members who contribute to strategy making opposed to the top management (Jarzabkowski & Wolf, 2015; Vaara & Whittington, 2012).

Top management of target firm should be involved in board to retain some power which can reduce employees' resistance and increase the employee's participation, which leads to transfer of knowledge smoothly and best practices during integration process (Colman & Lunnan, 2011; Kale, Singh, & Raman, 2009). Top management at target firm can play mitigating role in alleviating members concerns, resolving conflicts and avoid disruptions by target firm's employees during integration process (Colman & Lunnan, 2011). Therefore, management from target firm can act as change agents for acquiring firm in identifying and providing solutions proactively (Colman & Lunnan, 2011).

Middle management such as integration managers, HR managers and line managers also play important role as change managers in their capacity (Shi et al., 2009) and act as active agents during interpretation, mediation, and brokerage of information (Shi et al., 2009). They also involve in devising strategy and implantation process (Balogun & Johnson, 2004). Subsequently, a shift from a "top-down" management style towards "involvement and commitment", which made middle managers as recipient and change agents and transforming their position to enablers and empowerees (Caldwell, 2003). Furthermore, integration managers can influence value creation and value leakage (Teerikangas et al., 2011) whereas HR managers and other members of management are involved in the integration process (Antila & Kakkonen, 2006).

Employees also act as change agents which are not acknowledged in literature of change agency (Caldwell, 2003). Employees are not only involved in the implementation of the strategy but also should be involved in the initiation process of change after the acquisition and integration. This

will allow members to discover information which is credible source of information for employees (Armenakis, Harris, & Mossholder, 1993). For example, employees will perceive the reason for M&A as a result of their input in planning strategy for integration (Armenakis et al., 1993) as well as actively participate in integration by allowing them to visit merging firms through exchange program to share discoveries and create readiness for change environment among other colleagues through personal influence (Armenakis et al., 1993). Organizing roundtable meetings and forming task forces helps employees to participate in change process (Vales, 2007) which can lead to successful M&As. Thus, employees' involvement is a successful factor for M&A (Nguyen and Kleiner, 2003) and increase fairness, commitment, and trust about M&A Schraeder and Self (2003).

Finally, other stake holders such as customers, investment bankers, lawyers, consultants, and labour unions are very important in M&As and should be considered in decision making. For example, labour union became driving force and opposed by management of American Airlines during integration with US Airways (Reed, 2013). Studies should examine the impact of other stakeholders on processes, practices, and integration success mergers rather than on financial returns provided by Bodnaruk et al. (2009) and Servaes & Zenner (2015).

2.12 Resistance in M&A

Management studies illustrate resistance as illegitimate organisational behaviour, which has the potential of creating barriers in management however, in "human side" literature of M&A, the resistance is categorized as "merger syndrome" followed by employee's negative reactions in M&As (Sinkovics et al., 2011). The focus of this study was on negativity and psychological reactions by employees. As a result of these reactions, employees feel demotivation as explained by Kusstatscher and Cooper (2005) and promotion of anxious behaviours Ivancevich et al., (1987) and reduced commitment (Sinkovics et al., 2011). Finally, these adverse reactions linked to the behaviour of employees through resistance, which may take the form of power struggles and failure to cooperate well.

However, resistance is inherently negative phenomenon, which is explored from the resistance perspective by Ford et al. (2008), conflict as noted by Tjosvold (2008) and contended by Piderit (2000). Additionally, resistance can be backed by valid employees concerns or good intentions (Piderit, 2000). Resistance can also be used to point unrealistic expectations or negative behaviour

which can improve the change process (Ford et al., 2008). Additionally, resistance may also be improving the commitment than acceptance if it followed the change process in some cases (Ford et al., 2008). Furthermore, it can also improve the resilience among members provided members have strength to success in difficult situations like M&A (Seligman & Csikszentmihalyi, 2000). Also, resistance can be a learning process which bring about innovation and can strengthen the employees' relationship if the conflicts and different views discussed constructively (Tjosvold, 2008) and as a result employee can perceive M&A as positive change (Raitis, Harikkala-Laihin, Hassett, and Nummela, 2017).

The role of resistance is complex and often mixed with power and struggle according to practice perspective (Laine & Vaara, 2015) and it may construct other forms in M&As (Monin, Noorderhaven, Vaara, & Kroon, 2013). For example, members deliberately distancing themselves and offer poor engagement (Laine and Vaara, 2007) and response to change in contradictory ways (Piderit, 2000) that can create difficulties for management to act as a result of multi-layered attitudes and behaviours. Additionally, resistance can also occur at top level management (Laine & Vaara, 2015) particularly in target firm caused as a result of disagreement with acquiring firm management. Furthermore, resistance can emanate from other stakeholders including policy makers, trade unions, not for profit firm, investors, and the media (Whittington, 2006). For example, DP world had to back off due to political resistance from the bid its placed to acquire port operations in US (Sanger, 2006). Similarly, a merger of British BAE systems and EADS were unsuccessful because of investor and NGO concerns and political resistance over job guarantees and location of their headquarters (Campbell, 2013). Furthermore, health and safety and security concerns for employees and consumer protection laws are source of resistance and reasons that have their roots on the level of relationship among personnel who feel that their position is under threat and hence oppose. Finally, the management can also be witty to resist if issues under their perspective are not considered if involved in factors beyond their control as tactic to justify failure or to delegitimize valid concerns from the members (Piderit, 2000).

Serial acquisitions have distinct dynamics and managers of target firms are compelled to utilize a new sensemaking frames on daily basis due to resistance (Chreim& Tafaghod, 2012). The literature on "human side" in serial acquisitions, from the perspective of a "serial target," is incomplete. Serial target firm negatively affect its employees (Hambrick and Cannella, 1993,

p.134) and as a result affect mode of resistance (Ezzamel & Willmott, 2008). However, motivations of employees can be maintained by incentives, level of decentralization and weaker social pressures (Hajro, 2015). Also, members of serial target identify themselves by their profession instead of their firm identity (Hajro, 2015) therefore, it is unclear that they experience higher level of resistance.

There is need for more studies to re-conceptualize the concept of resistance in M&As which make sense why firms involved into the mergers and acquisition on the basis of the varied interests of firms as per their power positions adjust their actions and behaviours accordingly so that it can make sense why there is resistance in M&As (Sarala, Vaara and Junni, 2017).

Researcher should understand why and how employees working within the firms involved in mergers and acquisitions can change the whole course as a result of shift in the practices, strategies within the firms as a result of M&As (Chapman, Chua, & Mahama, 2015; Long, 2001). It is not only important to find out why employees within the merging firms change their course of actions or act as change agents but also identify under which circumstances their actions are justify and find and compare both positive and negative actions of the organisation and as a result employee change their way of doing things (Long, 2001).

2.13 Human resource management

2.13.1 Ineffective HRM

One of the main challenges the company faces is the loss of job opportunities due to participation in mergers and acquisitions, which may lead to dysfunction and inefficiency in human resource management due to the inability to provide human resources. The right talent. After announcing the merger, uncertainty tends to be at the highest level where employees feel very vulnerable. The human resources functions in each merged organisation are susceptible to merger announcements, and the risk of losing key personnel is greater. This can make the strong HR function the weakest. Therefore, the Human Resources Department must take preventive measures immediately after announcing the merger.

After mergers and acquisitions, the combined company often experiences a net migration of employees during the integration process. During the evaluation phase, people may be forced to leave in an attempt to develop synergies at different levels identified within the organisation. As a result, managers and top managers may decide to block mergers, or join competitors as competitors, in order to use the uncertainty and ambiguity brought about by mergers and acquisitions to find key people.

One way to retain key personnel is the preventive method. In this way, after the two companies agree to discuss the merger, the top management of each organisation should hold an informal meeting as soon as possible. Then, the task of these senior managers is to contact their various functional managers and ask them to prepare a list of essential personnel in each functional department. After the meeting was held within a few days of the first meeting, these lists were merged, and senior management prepared and agreed on the final list of key individuals. Therefore, the usual practice is to appoint a person (usually a senior manager) who is responsible for ensuring that as many key individuals as possible are retained through the merger.

Each M&A strategy will involve different human resource practices and strategies. When international mergers take place, human resource strategies become more complicated. It is important to understand the connection between human resource strategy and business strategy to estimate the reasons behind the merger that may affect the human resource function, so preventive measures can be recommended to retain key personnel and prevent personnel loss. The function of human resources is weakened.

2.13.2 Strategic link between HRM and M&A

The strategic human resource management literature focuses on aligning human resource management with business strategy (Fombrun et al., 1984; Schuler and Jackson, 1987). Strategy is the dominant force, and there is a good fit between strategy, structure, and human resource management (Fombrun and colleagues, 1984). Companies that change strategy will change human resource management practices (Schuler and Jackson, 1987). Similarly, Sanz-Valle et al. (1999) studied Spanish companies and found a connection between business strategy and human resource management practices.

It is important for human resource managers to participate in the merger process as early as possible (Mirvis & Marks, 1992). In order to retain people's views and issues in the plan, human resource management must be incorporated into the plan to successfully execute the plan. The basic comfort and needs of humans (work) related to the organisation are critical, for example, motivation may be critical to deal with post-merger integration. In addition, the differences in job classification, training, performance evaluation, career development, salary and other human resource management between the acquiring company and the acquired company should be resolved. (Mirvis and Marks, 1992). Schweiger et al. (1989) reviewed the human resources aspect and asked the executives of 80 organisations to determine 15 human resource factors, and whether the M&A decision included executive compensation agreements and labour agreements. They found that although these standards are very important to the company's success, they did not pay much attention.

According to a research conducted in 2000 by the human resources consulting company Towers Perrin, only 39% of human resources personnel participated in due diligence. By 2005, this number had increased to 62% (Brown, 2005). The strategic human resource management literature focuses on aligning human resource management with business strategy (Fombrun et al., 1984; Schuler and Jackson, 1987). Strategy is the dominant force, and there is a good fit between strategy, structure, and human resource management (Fombrun and colleagues, 1984). Companies that change strategy will change human resource management practices (Schuler and Jackson, 1987). Similarly, Sanz-Valle et al. (1999) studied Spanish companies and found a connection between business strategy and human resource management practices. On the contrary, in order to successfully integrate, the HRM strategy must be consistent with the business strategy and consider the fit between M&A and HRM strategy. Understand the challenges of human resource management in mergers and acquisitions, the conceptual tools of resources, processes and values used in different situations of mergers and acquisitions (Bower, 2001). Resources are defined and divided into tangible assets (people and money) and intangible assets (brand, customer loyalty and relationships).

In the context of human resource management, the resources are treated as employees in the merger process, their contracts, and retention and termination issues. Refers to the activity of converting company resources into goods and services. In the context of HRM's strategy, staff training, and

development will be carried out to solve the skill shortage in the M&A process. Ultimately, the most important thing people do is values. Values are the values supported by your culture or religion. Values influence how employees make decisions and how they react to any phenomenon. Studies have provided this relationship and determined the appropriate relationship between human resource management strategies and M&A and strategies within M&A. For example, Bower (2001) provided an in-depth analysis and discovered the relationship and fit between M&A strategy and human resource management strategy. He used a framework including resource practices, processes, and value frameworks.

2.13.3 Link of M&A and HRM strategies

Companies adopt different merger and acquisition strategies to gain competitive advantage, such as horizontal, vertical, product expansion, market expansion and unrelated mergers and acquisitions (Federal Trade Commission, 1975). This merger typology was developed in the 1970s to study the merger process (Buono and Bowditch, 1989). However, in the 1990s, companies adopted new M&A strategies, including cross-border mergers and acquisitions (Bower, 2001). In order to link human resource management strategies with mergers and acquisitions and the meaning of resources, processes, and values, Bower (2001) proposed five different merger strategies:

- Overcapacity M&A
- Geographic roll-up M&A
- Product or market extension M&A
- M&A as R&D
- Industry convergence M&A.

a) An overcapacity M&A

In mergers and acquisitions with overcapacity, the company seeks to eliminate the overcapacity in order to create a more efficient company by eliminating human resources. These types of mergers and acquisitions usually occur in oligopoly industries characterized by overcapacity and involve companies of similar size, such as BP's acquisition of Amoco and Daimler's acquisition of Chrysler. The process and value of merging companies are usually similar, but differences in relative positions can cause problems in merger integration.

b) Geographic roll-up M&A

This happens when the company expands its business globally. Large companies acquire small companies to retain local managers who may have experience in the banking industry, such as Banc One's acquisition of several regional banks. Most companies make acquisitions earlier in the industry life cycle. International mergers and acquisitions aim to achieve economies of scale (Bower, 2001: 98), while mergers and acquisitions with overcapacity are mainly focused on reducing the duplication of processes and organisations between different departments. With fewer human resources, the process and value of the merged entity may be different compared to an overcapacity merger. Finally, differences in status can cause integration problems, but due to overcapacity, this situation is not as frequent as in mergers and acquisitions.

c) A product or market extension M&A

This type of merger and acquisition means expanding the product line locally or internationally when the production and/or distribution of the two companies are functionally related or the company seeks to diversify. Success depends on the local understanding of the customer, market conditions, legal framework, relative size, and the experience of the company acquired in the merger. In this type of mergers and acquisitions, especially in international mergers and acquisitions, there are many factors that interfere with culture, leadership style and lifestyle, so there are great differences. This is why companies find it difficult to change the process and value of the acquired company. For example, Marks & Spencer encountered geographic distribution problems due to the acquisition of the Canadian company PDS (People's Department Store) (Bower, 2001). Instead, GE acquired Nuovo Pignone, an Italian engine producer, where GE shared its resources to grow its business and gradually introduced its systems over time (Bower, 2001).

d) M&A as a substitute for R&D

Instead of producing knowledge internally, companies are acquiring innovative companies so that they can acquire R&D knowledge. Ideally, the company will invest a lot of resources in the research and development of new projects, new technologies, and new products to improve its technical capabilities (Granstrand and Sjolander, 1990). Acquiring a company requires a lot of resources, so it is inevitably larger than the target company to be acquired. It is also obvious that these companies have experience or trading experience in the same business area. For example,

buying a manufacturing company might buy a software development company. Success depends on the integration ability of the acquired company and the learning ability of the acquirer. Retaining human resources and knowledge is the main goal of these types of mergers and acquisitions. In these types of mergers and acquisitions, the process and value of the new company will need to be changed, which may become a challenge for the merged company, because the target company's employees feel that their value is restricted or hindered by the new structure. management. Integration issues can become complex and depend on the industry. For example, compared with companies in the pharmaceutical industry, companies in the IT industry need to integrate quickly because information technology (IT) companies usually have a much shorter product development cycle than companies in the pharmaceutical industry.

e) An industry convergence

Mergers and acquisitions that are also moving toward industry convergence, such as the media and telecommunications industries, will involve major convergence. Similarly, Viacom's mergers and acquisitions of Paramount and Blockbuster have pushed the industry to new heights, which may lead to internal contraction in the industry. As technology continues to disrupt and fundamentally change many business models, and to create a new industry in existing industries, cross-industry integration has eroded their boundaries, but people have fully understood this, so it is difficult for analysis, we have seen cross-industry convergence. We are moving in the direction of mergers and acquisitions to replace R&D, which may shift the focus to the wrong direction.

2.14 Environmental context of International M&A

According to the contingency theory, the company's strategy and structure depend on environmental conditions. If the conditions are more diversified, the company's structure will be different accordingly (Lawrence and Lorsch, 1967). Similarly, different parts of an organisation have different effects, so the environmental impact on the organisation will vary within the organisation. For example, in order to achieve the required work behaviour, management practices in certain countries must meet environmental requirements. In addition, the environment also affects companies through the legal system. The European Commission opposes the US\$37 million merger agreement between the two US telephone companies MCI and WorldCom. Similarly, according to the New York Times (March 2018), President Trump blocked Broadcom's proposal to acquire chip maker Qualcomm for \$117 billion on the grounds of national security

concerns. Therefore, it can be inferred that these companies operate within national and international borders and may be affected by the environment. It is important to recognize when and how the national environment affects international mergers and acquisitions. The concept of integration indicates that environmental factors such as institutions or culture can affect the organisation's strategy and structure. National culture is rooted in organisational and management practices, such as individual performance awards, team-oriented short-term results, and decentralized and informal organisational structures (Schneider, 1989). National cultural differences will affect companies' cross-border mergers and acquisitions, so individualism and openness to foreign cultures will vary from country to country (Adler et al., 1986) and will affect mergers. And cross-border acquisitions (Gersten et al., 1998). The national culture in the form of institutional environment differs from country to country and affects the transformation process of the merged company. These institutional influences include national characteristics of the country; financial system; education and training system; labour-management relations (Whitley and Kristensen, 1997). When companies merge from two different countries, they are also affected by accidental environmental impacts that depend on the different dimensions of the two countries. According to the state institutions that describe their financial and labour market systems, countries can be divided into two basic types: free market economies (LME) and coordinated market economies (CME) (Hall and Soskice, 2001; Gospel and Pendleton, 2003).

LME countries include the United Kingdom, the United States, Australia, Canada, New Zealand, and Ireland in the OECD (Hall and Soskice, 2001). The systems of these countries/regions are based on the competitiveness of the supply and demand market, which affects the performance and processes of the company and can be regarded as a value country for shareholders. Performance is measured by market value, while state institutions have the least intervention in the economy. The London Metal Exchange (LME) country focuses on current earnings, and the regulatory environment can tolerate mergers and acquisitions. In the LME, the company is free to hire and fire employees. The company does not pay attention to the professional training of employees because the training and education are conducted in schools and universities and the skills acquired by employees are relatively common.

In CME countries, including Germany, Japan, Switzerland, and the Benelux and Scandinavian countries, they are characterized by off-market relationships and relatively weak equity culture

(Hall and Soskice, 2001). The overall performance of the company is measured according to the national model of "stakeholder capitalism", the overall relationship or performance of employees, suppliers, customers, and financial institutions. The corporate governance market is not entirely dependent on public information about companies. Therefore, mergers and acquisitions can be prevented in various ways. An example of Vodafone taking over from Mannesmann, Germany in 1999. Vodafone must deal with completely different company laws, engineering and production cultures, ownership structures influenced by banks, opaque accounting and disclosure rules, and board structures. Two levels (Hopner and Jackson, 2001). The field use of human resource management adjusts the national institutional environment. Human resource management practices in EMC "include more restricted employer autonomy, difficult hiring and dismissal decisions, fewer employee geographic and professional mobility, and a closer connection between education types and career development" (Sparrow et al., 1994: 286). In CME, the company's rate of return is often measured over the long term. Employers are obliged to protect employees' rights and collectivism. However, minority shareholders do not protect large shareholders effectively. Organisations have the legal right to intervene in labour reorganisation (Casper and Hancke, 1999) and focus on the professional skills of employees.

2.15 HRM practices in international M&A

Human resource management is influential at every stage of M&A. In the pre-merger stage, the Human Resources Administration helped in assessing salary differences between the merged companies, managing retention agreements, and ensuring legal compliance regarding equal opportunities and collective bargaining agreements (Mirvis and Max (1992). In the implementation of the new During the integration stage of practices and new policies, we can see the main role of human resource management. Since cultural differences will affect company policies and practices, human resource management is very important. This is due to the different nature of integration in different countries (Child and colleagues ,2001).

2.15.1 Overcapacity M&As

Resources, in mergers and acquisitions with overcapacity, large-scale layoffs are inevitable. Therefore, the role of human resource management here is essential for successful integration to quickly determine reduction strategies, planning, and reorganizing personnel tasks (such as

relocation plans). The challenge of human resources is not only layoffs, but also retention issues at different levels within the company. For example, compared with unrelated mergers, senior executives in related mergers have higher turnover because they are familiar with the business of the acquired company (Walsh, 1988).

One of the factors that affect the merger of a company is the country involved in the merger. Compared with EMM countries, in EMC countries, due to institutional restrictions, the number of layoffs is greater, and the ways in which layoffs are used are different. For example, compared with British companies, American companies use short-term methods for hiring and firing (Child et al., 2001). However, in the case of a merger involving two different market economies, due to the legal protection of the employment contract and the long-term cooperative relationship, the acquiring company will be subject to greater restrictions. Participants in these labour markets

Processes, Due to domestic overcapacity, the merger process has hardly changed. Children etc. (2001:89) confirmed that in domestic mergers and acquisitions, compared with the acquisition of British companies by foreign companies, companies have made relatively few changes to human resource management practices and processes. Similarly, the minor changes in the process of the merger of countries stem from the common values of the two companies. Therefore, British, and American companies are closely related to their human resource management systems and practices, such as performance pay and other management practices and styles (Child et al., 2001: 178).

In the case of mergers and acquisitions in a market economy, such as the Daimler-Chrysler merger (that is, the acquisition of LME by CME), the issue of strategic adjustment becomes more complicated. This is an almost equal merger, and they have similar characteristics of overcapacity, and the HR administration will conflict. Daimler-Benz's executive pay is lower than that of Chrysler, so they have to adjust the performance system. The human resource management process also depends on the nationality of the acquiring company, so companies of small and medium-sized companies are more likely to change the process of acquired companies than companies of multinational companies. For example, American executives believe that it is appropriate to align the salary levels of German executives with those of American executives. Although Daimler-Chrysler is facing pressure from the German Labour-Management Federation, there is still

evidence that Child and his colleagues (2001) trained and developed LME on the acquisition of LME by Japanese and German companies. Development of British companies.

Values, Mergers with overcapacity of equal value may lead to integration difficulties between the two companies (Bower, 2001). Mergers and acquisitions with overcapacity are sometimes difficult to integrate because the processes and corporate values in the industry are complex and deeply rooted. For example, the main problem occurs in equivalence mergers

"Losers" make it difficult for buyers to integrate. Specifically, the nearly equal merger of Daimler-Chrysler demonstrates how national differences between market economies can exacerbate conflicts, and Daimler is a German bureaucratic company that is heavily dependent on a bureaucratic company with staff management rules and procedures. In contrast, the decision-making process of the US subsidiary Chrysler is more flexible and decentralized. However, differences in personnel management and national culture, such as lunch and drinking and other differentiated company values, have caused problems in the humanistic aspect of this merger (Vlasic and Stertz, 2000). In addition, Daimler-Chrysler also emphasized the important role of communication and trust. Senior managers of Daimler-Benz knew from the beginning that they would eventually hold all the highest positions in the merged entity. However, they did not communicate with key executives. As a result, many people left the company.

2.15.1.1 Job security and redundancy

As a result of M&As, employees feel insecure about their jobs due to the uncertainty about the future. Therefore, firms provide provides stable employment for employees (Herzberg, 1968) refers to as job security. In order to make processes and operations efficient, firms involved in practices making employees redundant because they are no longer required for the job as a result of making the job design efficient and removing duplications in the job roles. M&As is the process where both firms look to reduce their costs by restructuring and change process to make their processes and operation efficient. Therefore, following the merger announcement, employees feel uncertainty and experiencing lower job security as they are more likely to be made redundant (Rafferty & Restubog, 2010). Redundancy decision are made by supervisors or management and decide which jobs to retain and eliminated to meet the objectives (Huselid, 1995). Often employees feel helpless and powerless and remain uncertain about the future during this process which cause anxiety and distress and due to having limited information available (Schweiger and

Walsh, 1990). Employees concerned about jobs and the direction of the combined firm cause them to involve in politics to protect themselves or gain power (Vaara & Monin, 2010).

Employees know that management possess important information about changing roles change and form sensemaking from their communications and related with their existing cognitive framework. However, communication coming from management can affect the behaviours of employees as this can change their perception about change as leaders have power over information and control the way is it communicated (Hope, 2010). For example, employees can perceive job loss as political in nature rather than job loss due to their shortage of skills. Therefore, leaders should communicate with employees clearly so that employees can have clear picture about their job's roles.

Similarly, leadership and management are concerned about being made redundant after mergers as this will overlap the CEO or board level positions in new firm after merger. Similarly, in most of the cases one culture prevails following mergers. As a result, board members of target firm feel powerless as the change process might result in job loss therefore, management will use political tactics to fractionalization of upper management to exert their power and stop the change process of M&As. This process of politicisation can cause the key executives leaving the firms (Vaara, 2001) which can jeopardise the change process of M&As. For example, in case of merger of Daimler-Benz and Chrysler where directors of Daimler-Benz used politics to push all the directors of Chrysler out of the board of combined firm despite being promised to have equal level of board after merger. This result in job losses for many of the Chrysler employees (Monin et al., 2013). Similarly, in Procter & Gamble's acquisition of Gillette, there were 6,000 jobs losses (Syre, 2005), and 7,800 jobs losses in Microsoft's acquisition of Nokia (Zillman, 2015).

Job insecurity may lead to increased stress, anxiety which decreased commitment and job satisfaction and affect the performance at work during change process (Ashford, Lee, & Bobko, 1989). In order to manage change efficiently, is assuring the job security of employees as this can reduce anxiety and stress caused by change process of M&As which can increase the performance of members (Stahl & Mendenhall, 2005; Stanwick & Stanwick, 2001). Providing training in order to increase the skills so that employee is compatible with the changing role which enabling them to meet new job demands and promoting their understanding of post-M&A expectations and values, this can affect individual cognitive framework regarding change, which can increase the

performance of members (Burke & Litwin, 1992; Stahl & Mendenhall, 2005) which result in positive attitude towards change (Davy et al., 1997). It can also make employees familiar with the new organizational culture which can also assure job security and deal with negative emotions such as anxiety and stress and improve their behaviour (Scheck, Kinicki and Davy, 1997).

2.15.2 Product or market extension M&As

Resources,

Although product or market expansion mergers and acquisitions usually involve layoffs, human resource management strategies mainly focus on retaining key employees, because such mergers and acquisitions strategies involve the purchase of new product lines or expansion into new markets, which may lead to a little overlap between companies. In terms of overcapacity, product mergers and acquisitions and market expansion, layoffs vary in different countries/regions. For example, compared with market economies, small and medium-sized enterprises tend to be resource-oriented in the short term. In a market economy, the size of US companies acquiring British companies may be reduced (Child et al., 2001). However, Child and his colleagues believe that when CME acquires LME, they will adopt a laissez-faire attitude and focus on the long-term positioning or cultural characteristics of employees. There are fewer cases of LME companies acquiring CME companies, and perhaps the trend of retaining human resources and protecting employees in CME is obvious. For example, GE (General Electric) often adopts a long-term approach, partly because of its response to past negative experiences in cross-border mergers and acquisitions.

Processes,

In mergers and acquisitions in terms of product or market expansion, changes in company processes are greater than changes in mergers and acquisitions with overcapacity. Therefore, changes in business and human resource management systems and practices are inevitable. Although there is not much overlap between the products, the manufacturing and distribution processes of both companies may change. For example, the merger of Quaker Oats and Snapple can only succeed if the advertising and distribution process of Quaker Oats is changed to adapt to the Snapple product line (Bower, 2001). This is evident in the LME, where American companies

have changed many human resource management practices in British companies by increasing the use of job rotation to reduce the number of management hierarchies (Child et al. (2001).

Generally, process changes will reflect the market economy of the acquiring company. Compared with CME, LME is more likely to integrate with the acquired company. Obviously, only when Japanese and German CME companies are likely to increase their use of small and medium-sized business formation companies, will they be more likely to introduce acquired British companies. For example, Child and colleagues (2001) showed that although British companies retain autonomy in many decisions and practices, British companies have established training programs in the process of purchasing new product lines. A German pharmaceutical company acquired a British company.

In addition, Japanese acquisition of British companies in Japan shows that CME acquisition companies with long-term focus are reflected in the country/region characteristics, but the acquired companies may lack experience. Similarly, the acquisition of CME by LME means a reduction in the degree of integration. For example, compared with domestic acquisitions, General Electric has gradually converted the process to CME acquisition.

Values,

Bower (2011) found that compared with overcapacity mergers and acquisitions, there are often more differences in company value in terms of product or market extension; however, conflicts in resources and processes may be reduced, especially when acquiring companies When the company is acquired. For example, Japanese companies use subtle or soft methods to integrate and avoid imposing collectively oriented values (Child et al., 2001). In the case of General Electric (LME acquired CME), GE refused to impose its value on the acquired company, but gradually adopted incremental methods and processes. In contrast, American companies are more likely to replicate their value in acquiring other LME companies.

2.15.3 M&A as a substitute for R&D

Resources.

The key employee resource as a substitute for R&D in M&A is a very critical component of HRM, because in this type of M&A strategy, the company acquires the knowledge possessed by the

employees of the acquired company. The main reason for these mergers and acquisitions is that they insist on human and social capital. However, retention can be a challenge for human resource management because the cost of selling employees' shares is high, which can be seen in many IT company mergers and acquisitions. In the case of substituting mergers and acquisitions for R&D, companies from different market economies are involved, thus gaining the focus of the company's retention of human resources to the same extent as this type of national mergers and acquisitions. In the case of CME Group, the German company acquired a British start-up and retained the entrepreneur (Child et al., 2001). Similarly, in the United States and the United Kingdom, the three Swedish CME companies retain 90% to 100% of the employees of R&D companies (Birkinshaw and Bresman, 2000). In addition, LME company Microsoft strongly supported the management team of the acquired CME company TITUS and achieved similar results in acquiring Cisco System from the Israeli company Pentacom.

Processes.

One of the main components of M&A alternative R&D is human resource management to establish systems and processes for transferring knowledge from the acquired company to the acquiring company. This can be accomplished through effective communication and the development of a systematic learning process. In addition, this type of M&A only takes very little time for R&D, especially in information technology-related M&As, because R&D changes very quickly and require immediate use of the results of new system acquisitions (Bower, 2001). For example, in the merger of Cisco and Cerent Corporation, Cisco used a transition team to transfer existing employees and give them jobs at Cisco while communicating with them (Child et al., 2001: 3). Although integration is expensive for Cisco Systems, if the development cycle exceeds six months, it prefers to acquire knowledge through mergers and acquisitions. The speed of assimilation is very important and depends on the type of industry and the country of origin of the acquired company. For example, compared with pharmaceutical companies, the IT industry has a faster development cycle. Similarly, in the case of CME acquiring LME, the IT industry has a slower development cycle. Specifically, CME companies that conduct cross-border mergers and acquisitions with LME companies tend to leave the process in the acquired company.

Like a Japanese company acquiring a British pharmaceutical company, there is a risk of acquiring a company that may lose potential synergies (Child et al., 2001). It may be because the M&A

strategy does not match the specific characteristics of the country, or because the Japanese company does not have enough experience. For example, two German companies took a laissez-faire approach (Child et al., 2001), but they were more successful than Japanese acquisitions. It can be said that American companies (i.e., Microsoft) tend to absorb the acquired company and make exceptions to the integration policy when necessary, even if the acquired company belongs to CME. For example, if the system of the acquired company is better than that of Cisco, then Cisco is willing to follow a non-interference policy on certain practices.

Values,

The acquirer in these types of mergers and acquisitions becomes bureaucratic due to the value of the acquired company, which has a negative impact and is difficult to integrate. For example, no matter how much you value integration, small businesses will feel fettered after acquisition (Bower, 2001). Generally, companies anywhere in the world have similar value to IT companies in these types of mergers and acquisitions. This highlights the importance of industry knowledge and values in reducing conflicts between companies caused by the values of specific countries.

M&A activities emerged as substitute for R&D and affected R&D efficiency negatively in recent years. Investing into R&D is technically more complex, time consuming and is not cost as effective as M&As as most of the times particularly for preclinical and clinical test for new drugs and long awaiting approval from drug regulatory authority can potentially increase the overall costs of R&D project which negatively affects the profitability ((Danzon, Epstein and Nicholson, 2007), (Ornaghi, 2009) and (DiMasi, Kim and Getz, 2014)). As a result, most of medicines either fail to reach the market or fail to regain the benefits due to these issues. Therefore, attractiveness of purchasing a readymade compound has increased as it can fill the R&D gap by M&As who already have developed the drug without spending enormous amount of money of R&D projects in house and waiting for approval. It can also help reducing risk from competitor products, risk of new drug not reaching market on time, risk of failures by having too many R&D projects and concentrating on key areas to increase their strength. Similarly, the shortfall in Research and development (R&D) pipeline can also result in M&A (Gemini et al., 2002).

Since the financial crisis, M&As have become increasingly important in the pharma industry as it can compensate revenue losses of blockbuster patent expirations using assets swaps, easy access intellectual property (IP), filling R&D pipeline gaps, exploiting technology-based innovative

treatments and developing core competencies (Schuhmacher et al., 2013). 50 % of the R&D pipeline projects come from external sources using M&As, most of the research-based pharmaceutical companies can get access to R&D projects from external companies who already done research to supplement their in-house pipeline or to meet its objectives (Schuhmacher et al., 2013). In 1995, Glaxo was facing the issue of expiring patent of one of the main drug Zantac. Rather than investing into R&D, it decided to merge with Wellcome and managed to create an innovative product like Seroxat (Gemini et al., 2002). Similarly, asset swaps between Novartis/GSK, which enabled Novartis to strengthen their hold in the Oncology market and GSK to further add to its vaccine portfolio. (Ringel and Choy, 2017).

Furthermore, both Pfizer and GSK combined their consumer health businesses battling against the surging costs of R&D projects and lower prices pressure, this merger created the world's biggest supplier of over-the-counter medicines which will potentially bring innovation and substantial cost synergies. The proposed transaction also to restructure the busines to build further support for investment in its R&D pipeline by 2022. (Chapman, 2021).

2.16. Information technology and systems (IS/IT)

This section provides the literature concerning the challenges of IT/IS integration within the context of mergers and acquisition which can cause failures in integration of companies involve in M&As. Challenges stem from literature will be source for framework development.

2.16.1 Assessing Information technology and information Systems

According to O'Brien, J A. (2003), IS defined as collection of systems which help to control the performance of business processes in logical way whereas IT consists of components which enables IS to function. The only difference is that IT generally does not include business logic. Hence Proctor, K. Scott (2011) mentioned IT as "the study, design, development, application, implementation, support or management of computer-based information systems" Proctor, K. Scott (2011). IT and IS will be used in combination as IT/IS as this study considered both aspects of IT and IS and it might cause confusion if used separately. IT/IS integration refers to the connection of internal business activities and functions together (Henningsson, 2008).^{[11][SEP]}

Restructuring because of corporate takeovers can generate many benefits for the firms but at the same time, it can create inefficiencies or problems in their operations. In every area and each stage, firms rely on systems and technology so that these can provide accurate information on time. In literature of mergers and acquisitions, the area of information systems and information technology is ignored when firms go for takeovers at planning stage (Johnson, 1989; McCartney & Kelly, 1984). The compatibility of systems and processes should be assessed at the stage of planning before corporate takeover and professionals who understand the IT and IS should be involved during the entire process of mergers so that any problems can be identified for successful mergers (Buck-Lew, Wardle & Pliskin, 1992).

In a study, two-thirds of the firms involved in takeover experienced inadequate information to integrate the systems and unable to make informed decisions (Bohl, 1989). 50% of population responded that no one realise about it and there was no information available. Often systems professionals not involved and put on hold until further announcement (McReil, 1989; Bozman, 1989). Systems professionals then expected to identify and reconcile the incompatibilities in systems of both firms to integrate without disruptions and this can be difficult because firstly, IS and IT professionals not included in planning process of takeovers and integration of systems do not start until merger is formally taken place therefore delay in the process. Secondly, technological issues in terms of compatibility of software, hardware, connectivity are not resolved in planning process therefore integration of incompatible systems waste time and can be failed to provide information on time. Third, it can also cause delay in developing the new applications to integrate systems of both firms. Finally, firms do not focus on changes in system policies and procedures (Fiderio, 1989; Weber & Pliskin, 1996).

Firms should have more flexible and adaptive business application system such as service-oriented architectures (SOA) which can integrate wide range of business applications Also firms should have one enterprise-resource-planning (ERP) system which incorporates not only current firm's data but also have ability to integrate data from new firms because of M&A (Sarrazin, H. & West, A. 2011). In a study of two banks First Chicago NFD merging with Bank one, management were unable to integrate IT systems for both banks for two years because of integration issues and as a result lost 200,000 customers (Thornton, Arndt & Weber, 2004). Another merger of United and

Continental Airline in 2012 caused failure of systems after two years when customers' reservation system failed which caused delaying or cancelling flights (Mouawad, 2012).

2.16.2 Mergers and Acquisitions Context

The area of Mergers and acquisitions is very vast and cannot be covered by a single definition. According to the Caves, it is an economic transaction and socially desirable and create value for the firms (Caves, 1989). Synergy and efficiency in operations and systems can be achieved through mergers and acquisition as it is the best tool to integrate systems and processes (Maquieira et.al, 1998). Firms not only focus on operational and financial synergies but also include risk of obsolescence, diversification, competition, and managerial compensation that triggers organisation to look out for M&As (Lev,1993). Firms have acknowledged the fact that through mergers and acquisitions, firms can readily achieve many goals such as increase in market share, diversifications, patents rights, growth in size and strength, skills, talent, improvements in IT/IS structure, processes, and operations.

Acquisitions refers to a firm that can buy another firm with cash, stock, or a combination of both whereas mergers involve horizontal mergers, where two competitors merge together and share similar products. Firms acquire suppliers or customers in vertical mergers and in congeneric mergers, firms expand their products or market base with other firms. The terms takeover, mergers and acquisitions are used interchangeably. M&A process consist of assessments of organisational capabilities, strategic planning, due diligence analysis, initial negotiations, and compliance check. In post-merger period, firms start integration and continue until firm settles down and sometimes takes many years to integrate (Empson, 2000).

As part of the takeover process, firms may introduce new IT, information systems and new structures which can be helpful in running business operations smoothly and solve problems efficiently (Senn,1994). Because of integration between merging firms, operations and systems of merging firms get bigger and become complex if integration is not managed appropriately however, effective planning can better tackle integration problems and generate value for the firms (Berger et.al. 1998).

2.16.3 Due Diligence

It is evident that investment in IT since last few decades has increased the profitability of firms (McAfee and Brynjolfsson 2008). Therefore, to gain competitive advantage, IT systems should be valuable to the user as friendly whether the software is standardized or customized. Therefore, managers should assess both costs and benefits of merging of standardised or customised IT systems.

Fully combines the IT systems can generate larger benefits however it can be challenging due to the complexities within the systems for larger firms. In contrast, separate accounting systems avoid integration issues but at the same time reduce the potential to gain benefits from M&A.

The extent of intergradation of infrastructure depends upon its IT/IS characteristics which includes the standardization and customization of software in each firm.

In most of M&As, management focuses on operational, legal, or financial issues and as a result ignore the expected issues caused by integration of systems of both firms and only realise when the issues are arising during the merging process. Therefore, management should assess the importance of IT systems to gain competitive advantage and involve the IT and Systems personnel to smooth the process of mergers and sustain the competitive advantage at the same time (Stylianou, Jeffries and Robbins, 1996).

A study indicates that management should include systems integrations and problems with these systems in the planning motivations process for mergers and acquisitions. (Buck-Lew, Wardle, & Pliskin, 1992). Merger's evaluations should not only be based on the benefits of increased efficiency, reducing costs etc. but also consider if integrating systems can enhance the competitive advantage for firm. In contrast, ignoring potential systematic issues can cause problems in integrations and missed to grasp the opportunities. These information systems provide the financial details as well as operational information to decide whether to acquire or merge other firms therefore managers need to assess the systems in place to assess the validity of information provided by these systems (Shaffer and Schrock, 2012).

In case study of Land O' Lakes US agro firm acquiring GeoSys French firm that give information for corps health using satellite data, it had been experienced that the GeoSys can increased the strategic capability of Land O' Lakes when professionals done due diligence test (Nash, 2014).

2.16.4 Aligning Business strategy with IT/IS

Firms use three major M&A strategies – absorption, symbiosis, and preservation (Wijnhoven *et al.* 2006). In absorption (rip and replace), acquiring firm fully absorb the target firm including its systems, operation, IT, and processes. In symbiosis (partial), the acquiring firm only acquire the functions which relates to core competencies or structures that create competitive advantage from target firm. In preservation (no integration), acquiring firm do no integrate any of their IT and systems or operations and remains fully intact within the merged entity. This strategy normally adopts by firm when it merged into totally different business line and when it has not operational expertise or capacity necessary to be completely absorbed the new systems. Integrating IT/IS of forms has become challenging due to time and budget involve as firms may experience costs and risks of failure due to not managing the integration efficiently and being described as dilemma (Paruchuri *et al.* 2006). Therefore, allocating appropriate balance of resources to align business strategy with IT/IS integration is an essential part of integration success.

IT/IS objectives should also be aligned with the business strategy (Reich & Benbasat, 2000) however, this is not a rule, but it is part of process to adapt the change efficiently (Hirschheim & Sabherwal 2001:87). It is argued that alignment is not very important, but it can help to reduce the risk of IT/IS integration failure (Baker & Niederman 2014). However, alignment itself is not sufficient for successful integration as strategy is not always pre-determined and follows top-down approach as it is more of emergent in nature and companies tend to change their strategies due to changes in technological needs (Baker & Niederman 2014). Also, both Baker and Niederman and Mehta and Hirschheim argue that integration success is depend on synergies within timeframe however alignment is not on priority.

2.16.5 Culture and IS/IT

Culture represents a variety of different conceptual sets, including values, norms, beliefs, and symbols, but cultural studies also show how to treat cultural changes as the result of analytical levels and dynamic values, norms or belief changes, etc. when it comes to information System and technology, in order to make information system research and culture clearer, culture will become more complex, Martin (2002) three-perspective method (integration, differentiation and fragmentation) will be used to integrate different concepts of IS culture competition . According

to these viewpoints, not only value is related to social relations, but also culture is essentially integrated, divided, and fragmented, symbolically expressing detailed organisational metaphors.

2.16.5.1 Integration

From an integration point of view, this culture is well integrated within the organisation, and there is consensus among all members. The cultural integration perspective focuses on those representations that have mutually consistent interpretations Martin (Martin, 2002, p.94). IS cultural studies emphasize the construction of an integrated culture suitable for the system (Cabrera et al., 2001; Claver, Llopis, González and Gasco, 2001). Therefore, the stronger the shared cultural value, the greater the company's chances of successfully adopting the technology. Claver et al. (2001), established two cultural positions on IS: one calculation and one information culture, where calculations are based on short-term IS plans/budgets, independent IT and business strategies, and the supporting information culture IS based on long-term IS planning/budget adjustment, IT, and business strategy. They emphasized that managers must establish or strengthen an information culture to maximize the efficiency of information systems. Similarly, Ruppel and Harrington (2001) pointed out that managers must establish a code of ethics (trust and care for people). Development (creativity and flexibility) and hierarchical culture (policy and information management) to adopt intranet and promote effective exchange of knowledge,

2.16.5.2 Differentiation

The difference perspective considers culture because it is not shared equally, and technology can be interpreted differently by subgroups (or subcultures) in the organisation. Martin (2002, p. 102) explained that consensus only exists between subcultures or lower levels within organisations. Huang et al. (2003) applied Martin's (2002) perspective of differentiation in the bank's component-based development (CBD) case study and showed that subcultural differences may have a negative impact on the adoption of IS. The difference between technicians, managers, and businessmen reduces the team's workload and, therefore, does not realize the expected benefits of adoption. A group of traders believe that CBD is beneficial, but managers find it increases the workload. In addition, due to the perception of threats by the employed technicians, the permanent technicians stopped disclosing information. Therefore, managers must consider sub-cultural differences when planning a new IS within the organisation. Similarly, Barrett (1999) studied the adoption of electronic placement support (EPS) systems in the London insurance market. A team of IT

professionals and senior managers hope that the system will increase transparency and efficiency between brokers and underwriters. However, brokers and subscribers believe that the new system is very different from traditional face-to-face communication and interpersonal trust, and therefore, the acceptance is poor. EPS system.

2.16.5.3 Fragmentation

Finally, from the point of view of fragmentation, culture is ambiguous in every organisational function and opposed to the vision of integration and differentiation (Martin, 2002, p. 105). The main purpose of the split perspective is to prove and understand the changing cultural complexity. Kappos, Rivard, and Lapointe (2005) used this view to study the cultural change caused by the hospital clinical information system (CIS). They demonstrated a series of conflicting and strange views that were not consistent or clear within the boundaries of the subgroup. Although the medical staff experienced efficiency due to the new system at the initial stage, the doctor believed that this was just an additional job, and therefore signed a petition requesting the removal of the system.

Similarly, Dube and Robey (1999) use a fragmented approach to study the improvement of software development processes at technical solution providers. They found that cultural values are constantly being renegotiated due to different approaches adopted between outsourcing partners and the organisation itself. They also proved that culture is not only shared between subgroups or only clearly exists between subgroups, but it is also inherently ambiguous.

2.16.5.4 Integration planning

Setting up a transitional structure is very critical in merger and acquisitions. It involves a temporary system which support and provide coordination during implementation of change (Marks & Mirvis, 2000). They provided the four bases of ideal transitional system as follows

Knowledge building - finding the best way of working together out of different set of different working arrangements between the two organisations.

Relationship building – arrange meeting between the employees of two firms so that they can understand different styles and culture and to build trust.

Transition management – senior management with experience of transition should share and exert particle experience to manage the process efficiently.

Communication management – regular exchange of information and ideas between the members of both firms.

Literature also focuses on maximising staff involvement in planning of transition process to identify problem areas early and ensuring bottom-up approach is adopted to get input from all levels. Despite the research has underlined the importance of management role during change process but its practical implications are due to be studied (Buchanan et al, 1999). IT/IS integration is an integral part of any financial M&A integration process therefore, doing appropriate due diligence including human capabilities of both firms and systems, aligning it with culture, policy and strategy of the firm are most important factors to consider so that any problem which may arise can be dealt before it affects the integration process of both firms.

Chapter 3 – Development of Conceptual Integrative Framework

Chapter Overview

Chapter 2 discussed the issues in literature related to the human factors affecting M&A integration process which can cause success or failure to M&A deal. This chapter focus on developing the Conceptual Integrative Framework.

3.1 Development of Framework

The framework proposed is supported by the findings of Hedman and Sarker (2015), Kovela and Skok (2015), Steigenberger (2016) and Toppenberg (2013) who reviewed the literature and given review of what and how it has been studied. Majority of the studies focused on analysis and explanation however none of them contained the theory for design and action or systematic approach have been developed in their studies to address integration issues of M&As. From findings of this study, integrative frameworks developed in the field of M&As are fragmented and a comprehensive framework is missing which include all the human factors affecting M&A in different integration phases. The framework is developed subject to induction of more ideas and concepts which will be revised upon application of this framework to mergers and acquisitions of two firms or departments therefore, bottom-up approach will be taken to improve the framework.

As mentioned in figure 3.1 and 3.2, employees are affected by number of factors. This framework included number or factors affecting employees at work and these factors must be considered during the process of integration as a result of M&A. Employees are shaped by their national, socio-cultural elements in which they have brought up, their communication style stem from their origin and based on the experience including personal and professional, training and development taken including any personality development and professional training, their leadership in a sense that their behaviour is followed up or build up by their parents or leaders from society and professional work who employee follow. Finally, their emotions, capabilities of dealing with emotions in stressful conditions and at work. This framework is developed based on the idea that everybody at work have different set of belief, culture, personality and have different styles of dealing with different situations. Therefore, these are called the personal factors which can affect the decision making of employee at work.

Figures 3.1 Conceptual Framework

Figure 3.2 Development of Conceptual Integrative Framework

Similarly considering organisational factors, each organisation has different actors which affects employees in number of different ways. Organisation culture can differ with the individual's own cultural values and most of the time employees must have to follow the norms and processes at work which might have been contradicting one's own practices. HRM processes followed by the employee might get change in the new merging firm which can cause stress and anxiety for the employees. When firms involve into M&A, HRM changes happen and issues can arise in the process of job grading, training, assess the performance, performance management, career development, salaries review and new employment contracts. These issues can badly affect the employees if merging firm don't deal with it appropriately and can cause emotional and job satisfaction issues for the employees at work which can affect the integration process and success of M&A deal. IT systems and process also can affect employees at work such as employees training of new or integrated system and feedback about using the new IT systems. If systems are too rigid and not functionable in order to perform the daily task by the employees, these can also affect the employees negatively. Change management is another important element which can affect employees as a result of M&As of new firms. Again, some humans are willing to make changes in their daily practices at work and for others it is not a pleasant experience which can cause stress, anxiety, and other work-related problems. These can be sorted by open communication, job rotation and motivations which can have positive impact on M&A integration process. Finally, leadership which is the most important factor at work which can affect employees the most. Leadership can become challenge for some employees and if leadership with appropriate leadership style adopted by management and supervisor, the whole M&A integration process which is overwhelming can become easy for employees. The organisational factors affecting employees during the process of M&A integration can become a challenging task for the management hence negatively affect the M&A deal. So therefore, management must consider these factors during post-M&A process.

3.2 Stages of Framework

The stages involved in the framework are as follows:

- 1) Assessing capabilities at each level
- 2) M&A context
- 3) Due diligence

- 4) Aligning business strategy
- 5) Selecting best integration strategy
- 6) Planning and implementation
- 7) Monitoring and evaluation

3.2.1 Assessing IT/IS, Processes, Controls, HRM, Leadership, Communications and Cultural Capabilities

At this level, higher management should be aware of different functions at the organisation of both firms before M&As. This can involve assessing the capabilities of governance system (processes, controls, communication system and leadership), HRM, cultural environment and IT/IS integration capabilities of firms. This is to ensure that structure, processes, cultural, IT/IS architectures of both firms integrating are suitable and not too fragmented or complicated to avoid risk of mergers and acquisitions failure. Failure to invest adequate resources in technology upgrades can lead to poor execution of the technology transition, causing frustration and, in the end, higher costs. Therefore, assessment before integration of both firms is important to ensure if both firms have suitable capabilities to integrate. Furthermore, not only higher leadership but IT managers should also involve in assessments of firm's IT/IS, cultural systems and processes capabilities at each stage of merger process, similarly integration managers should involve in every process of integrating processes such as HRM, culture integration, communications, and employee's engagement.

3.2.2 M&A Context

At this stage firms should know about the reasons and motives behind M&A to formulate integration strategy

- Business goals or strategy and expected synergies
- Type of M&A i.e., Horizontal, vertical, or takeover
- Business structures & integration i.e., functional, or operational
- Level of IT/IS integration i.e., Full, or partial
- Governance system (Leadership, processes, and controls)
- Culture, communication, HRM and People

- Employee's emotions
- Planning and risk assessment

3.2.3 Due Diligence

- Analyse IT/IS departments and structures of both firms including procedures and operations i.e., Centralized, or decentralized and standard or unique
- Analyse functions i.e., customers service and identifying how roles and tasks are distributed
- Analyse readiness for change and integration i.e., applications, IT infrastructure and cultural fit
- Compliance with regulatory authority
- Risk assessment and risk management
- Analyse IT/IS components integration
- Governance structure
- Cultural due diligence, acculturation, culture identity building of Employees with emotions and people

3.2.4 Aligning business strategy with Integration

The newly designed business strategy should be aligned with the desired business operations, processes, and procedures.

- Takeover or renewal of target firm's systems and processes
- Full or partial integration of systems with target firm
- Costs and benefits of using different systems
- Acculturation and firms' culture
- Organisational governance system
- HRM policies including training and development consider employees' emotions and stress management

3.2.5 Selecting best integration strategy

At this stage, firms should have full analysis of different integration options available and be able

to select best strategy which aligned with business objectives and expectations from integration. It might be possible that integration strategy is not aligned with overall business objectives of M&A however integration can still be successful.

It is argued that business managers (top leadership) should make decision at this stage instead of IT/IS personnel, HRM managers, however integration decisions should made by leadership following bottom-up approach by taking feedback from IT/IS managers, HRM managers and integration managers with business background.

3.2.6 Planning and implementation

At this stage, plans should be devised for the whole process of implementation of new strategy by including following factors

- Governance structure and its processes
- Cultural preservation and multiculturalism
- New IT/IS department structure & vendor management (Lange, 2015)
- Train users and Manage configuration, performance, capacity, and security (Kovela & Skok, 2015)
- Level of integration i.e., locations and deployment of resources over locations
- HRM, employees' emotions, satisfactions, and communications
- Organising change and advise of business transformation (Seddon, Reynolds & Willcocks 2010)

Once new business processes including new systems are connected and integrated between the firms, the old systems can then be abolished (Lange, 2015). However, employees from different cultures and background might have problems working with other therefore, careful assessment of culture fit needs to be done to avoid acculturation stress.

3.2.7 Monitoring and Evaluation

At this final stage when integration is completed. Monitoring and evaluation provide the feedback on integrated solution such as HRM and management information system, effectiveness & efficiency of IT/IS systems and compliance and reliability of information. Similarly, feedback

should assess, employees' satisfaction, emotions and cultural integration issues and based on the feedback, changes should be made to the strategy and evaluate again to assess its effectiveness.

3.3 Summary

The framework is developed through the concepts based on the available literature and improved based on the results of the meta synthesis analysis and PCA analysis of this study. It requires practical implications regarding the subject under consideration hence this framework not yet tested. Steps involved in framework will assist in encountering integration problems at different stages of M&A and not only help to reduce the risk of M&A Integration failure but also increase the efficiency of successful integration.

Chapter 4 - Research methodology

Chapter Overview

Previous two chapters have provided the details of the research including literature review and conceptual framework chapters. This chapter provides detailed explanations of the research methodology, techniques, purpose of the research and how this research is designed and implemented. Additionally, this chapter describes the steps used in conducting the study and addresses the issues in relation to research design, target population, sample size, sample collection, methodology and processes for data analysis. As far as research approach is concerned, it can be said that both inductive and deductive approaches (mixed) will be utilized for this research. It involves getting the results from qualitative primary data and studies using meta-synthesis and applies the results to construct the integrative framework (inductive approach). As per deductive research, relevant theories on integration within context of merger & acquisition are tested while making up entire research. Inductive approach will be taken to develop the conceptual integrative framework explained in chapter 2 for efficient integration strategy for merging firms. Entire study is developed based on primary and secondary qualitative data therefore, application of mixed approach will be most appropriate. This chapter is divided into two phases Qualitative Phase and Quantitative Phase which structure is outlined in Figure 4.1.

Figure 4.3 Organisational Structure of the Chapter

The Research Questions

Research questions are developed based on the literature review and hence divided into difference set of questions based on the sections of literature review. The questionnaire is extracted from asking employees questions about the understanding of organisational culture and how do they feel about the culture of their respective firms. In next section, employees are asked questions about the level of diversity within the organisation and how M&As affects the diversity as a result of merging both firms. Culture and diversity questions were developed after gaining the understanding of the section of culture in the literature review. Next sections are about the compensation, communication, and emotions where respondents are asked to response about their compensation, communication practices within firms, time of communication within the organisations and how these factors have affected the work practices of the respondents and its effects emotionally as a result of M&As. These questions developed based on the understanding from the sections of HRM, communication and emotions in the literature review. Next questions developed about the changing environment of firms and its effects on their work, changing processes, job roles and on their emotions as a result of M&As. These questions were developed based on the readings from the change management, resistance, and emotions sections in the literature review. Finally, respondents are asked to provide input on the effects of changing IT

systems and process and any training provided to them as a result of merging firms. These questions are developed from the IT and training sections of literature review. From each section of literature, questions have been generated to ask from the respondents so that the results generated from the analysis of this data can be used to validate the claims in the study and agree or disagree with the existing studies in the literature.

These factors are divided into two broad categories contextual and process related factors. However, lot of factors can become process and contextual at the same time such as communication is a process factor (based on the process) which helps firms in flow of information. This factor become contextual when employees' emotions are affected by the communications such as receiving different set of news from media and management and their effects on employees (based on the context). The concepts surrounded by humans in relation to their effects and influence on success or failure of mergers and acquisitions as subjective in nature therefore require in depth analysis keeping in mind both type of categories of contextual and processes related factors. The literature provides little or no direction in relation to these categories of these factors, and these are highlighted as propositions within the conceptual framework model developed in previous chapter 3. These factors of leadership, culture, communication, emotions, HRM, new IS/IT systems and processes at the organisational level, influence individuals at workplace and as a result overall success or failure in mergers and acquisitions. Therefore, the overall purpose of the research is to find the determinants which might affect human and inevitably employees of firms become change agents: How do humans affected by these factors of leadership, communication, culture, IT/IS and emotions at workplace. Furthermore, what is the nature and extent of these factors affecting the employees that influence an individual's capacity for the success or failure of firms involved in mergers or acquisitions.

After careful review of the literature within the areas of mergers and acquisitions surrounded by human factors, such as leadership, culture, communications, IT/IS systems and processes, Emotions and HRM issues. The conceptual framework followed by literature review chapter was developed to include interdisciplinary areas in M&As that have been extensively researched in the literature (referring to the previous chapters 2 and chapter 3).

Following are the questions which are based upon the overall purpose of the research and emerged from chapter 3 of the development of the conceptual framework.

- What is the nature of contextual and process-related factors causing failures or successes of mergers between the firms?
- What are the current and expected challenges and their effects on firms managing integration process during merger and acquisition period?
- How to evaluate the key determinants of systems and processes which will smoothen the process of mergers and acquisitions.
- What is the nature of comprehensive integrative framework involving mediating factors to determine the successful merger process?
- How developed integration framework will deal with the challenges during the process of merger and acquisition between the firms?
- What are the feasible recommendations for merging firms to maintain their operational proficiency during post-merger and acquisition period?

Based on the above objectives, this research is conducted and divided into two phases (qualitative phase and quantitative phase) as follows

PHASE ONE - QUALITATIVE PHASE

4.1.1 Phase One Overview

In phase 1, this study aims at to work out a systematic review by using the meta-analysis approach of M&A studies related research. The systematic review provides “deep insights through literature synthesis into fields and allied fields. The findings of systematic review are claimed to be rationalized, unbiased, rigorous, and transparent (Tranfield et al, 2003; Boell and Cecez-Kecmanovic, 2014). This study used standard systematic review guidelines of Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis (PRISMA) proposed by Moher et al, (2009) to improve the reporting quality of M&A studies.

4.1.2. Meta-Analyses

The process of meta- analyses is defined as” It is the statistical analysis of large body of literature from individual studies for achieving of fundamental purpose of integrating the qualitative and qualitative findings” (Barnett-Page and Thomas, 2009). It is a formal, epidemiological research

design followed to systematically examine the findings of past studies to derive compact conclusion about existing body of literature. Usually, but not necessarily, the research is depended on controlled and randomized trails. Output from the meta-analyses may involve more specific estimate of risk factor or effect of any policy shift or other outcomes, as compare to individual research participating to the pooled analysis. Major contributions involve the development of systematic review protocols that give systematic framework for electronic search of literature, methods, and extended and new analytic for examining the findings of meta-analyses. However, this study used standard systematic review guidelines of Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis (PRISMA).

4.1.3. Specification of method for qualitative synthesis

There are several ways for qualitative synthesis in meta-analysis and specification of method depends on research question, reviewer's purpose of review, and his philosophical position. An appropriate method has been identified after having an extensive appraisal of existing literature such as journal papers and range of different sources. It is prime responsibility of an author for adopting a reiterative aspect of method to pinpointing his data and information. Under the meta-analysis approach, the qualitative synthesis is an ongoing field of discussion and debate. Reason is behind that every author presents his own explanation of existing literature. Although many studies discuss various approaches for qualitative meta synthesis separately, but they are inter-related and overlapped. There are various reasons behind this. The qualitative synthesis is largely being employed to examine the issues of clinical and medical either integration or through interpretation of qualitative studies. Hence, there is no uniform approach which could be employed to qualitative synthesis. The vital qualitative synthesis methods are listed below:

- Thematic meta synthesis
- Qualitative cross-case meta synthesis
- Meta summary synthesis
- Meta study synthesis
- Meta interpretation approach
- Grounded theory synthesis
- Meta ethnography
- Critical interpretive synthesis

- This study used the Thematic Meta-Synthesis approach. It is an important synthesis method for examining the qualitative information. Recently, various studies have been used the qualitative synthesis findings from the thematic preceptive in systematic review.

4.1.4. Meta-synthesis

The method of meta-synthesis is also a systematic approach, beyond the scope of traditional literature review through which the results of different qualitative studies on a topic can be examined and presented. The main objective of meta-analysis is to make novel understandings from synthesis and comparison of results of various studies. This approach involves a detailed online search of qualitative research on M&A allowing us to extend beyond the primary or original scope of M&A qualitative studies by explaining analogies between the analytical themes following different keywords. A study Popay et al., (2006) proposed the following five different stages of meta-synthesis approach which are divided into primary in Figure 4.2 and Secondary in Figure 4.3.

4.1.4.1 Primary process of Meta-Synthesis

Figures 4.2 - Primary process of Meta-Synthesis

4.1.4.2 Secondary process of Meta-Synthesis

Figures 4.3 - Secondary Process of Meta-Synthesis

Many Studies found that thematic synthesis is very helpful tool when meta-synthesis including only qualitative studies about M&A (Vallido et al., 2010). A few studies deal with the concept of quantitative synthesis directly, hence the synthesis findings proved that all the relevant concept of individual M&A studies would not be examined in quantitative meta-synthesis (Meekums and Daniel, 2011).

4.1.5. Meta-Synthesis Review Protocols

The meta synthesis of M&A studies is directed by a review protocols confirming that the whole process is led strictly in keeping with guidelines of systematic review research. The meta-synthesis protocol involves a comprehensive description of all steps of systematic review process and the predefined decisions made during them, along with the sense of understanding and motivation behind them, similarly the main objectives of research question, electronic search process, criteria for inclusion and exclusion of identified studies, as well as quality synthesis of finally selected studies that fulfil the stated criteria (Averis and Pearson, 2003; Pearson, 2004; Holopainen et al., 2008). The systematic meta-synthesis process is guided by a precisely framed research question, which also guides and limits the selection of relevant articles obtained.

Research Question

- "How do mergers and acquisitions policies effect the quality of human such as IT/IS integration, employee satisfaction, training, HRM, communication, emotion, culture and leadership within an organisation"

Search Conditions

- Web Name: Pubmed, Google scholar Science Direct, J. store
- Year/Time Restrictions: 2000 to 2020
- Key Words: "merger", "acquisitions", "human capital", "cooperative section", "IT/IS Integration", "employee", "satisfaction", "training", "HRM", "communication", "emotion", "culture", "leadership"
- Kind of Research Added: Published Academic Research /Peer Reviewed/case studies
- Language: English

Articles Reviewed

- N=342 (292 excluded because they were not linked to research question or sub-population/interest)

Summarize

- n=50 (Finally used for Meta-Synthesis)

Figure 4.4 Meta-Synthesis Protocols

4.1.6. Data Collection and Eligibility Criteria

This meta-synthesis included studies that analyse the research question “how do mergers and acquisitions policies effect the quality of human such as IT/IS integration, employee satisfaction, training, HRM, communication, emotion, culture and leadership within an organisation”. The research papers were included if they fulfil the following eligibility criteria (1) the selected studies had to be focused only on merger and acquisitions (2) the identified studies estimated the empirical physiognomies i.e., M&A impacts on human capital; (3) the articles were written in English. The selected M&A research was briefly examined and scanned by the author with respect to dataset, measurement technique, empirical findings, and endogenous and exogenous factors.

4.1.7. Electronic Information Sources and Search Strategy

The online search was done by author on October 24, 2019 and on 29 October 2020 from three different databases such as Google Scholar, Science Direct and J-store. The selected papers should be published in ISI Web of Science register journals list. The online search was restricted to the year of publication from 2000 to 2020. This study used the following keywords and search strategy for the keywords appearing below in research paper title, abstract or full text research paper. Keywords are used as “merger”, “acquisitions”, “human capital”, “cooperative section”.

4.1.8. Selection of Case Studies and Data Extraction Process

Finally, the selected research papers were upload into EndNote software and 128 duplicate research studies were deleted by the author during the first stage of screening. Two independent reviewers selected articles for inclusion by following the two-step process. (1) Identified articles were screened based on research title and abstract. If there was conflict among the decision of independent reviewers, the article was sent into the second screening stage without negotiation. (2) the screening of full text paper, the second stage was also done by the author. This study identified the 342 full text studies among which 128 studies were excluded because they did not address inclusion criteria, 110 studies were discarded because they were duplicated. Remaining 104 research studies were reviewed in detail among which 54 research studies were discarded because they were just opinions, literature reviews and editorials. Total 50 selected papers were finally used for meta-synthesis.

4.1.9. Justification and Limitation of meta-synthesis

We know the rigor and depth of M&A research are generally found in economics and finance and then followed by law, accounting, and organisation studies. It is observed that M&A flow of studies in the form of number of publications, has increased in a fragmented way, therefore its aggregate impact is very difficult to discern (Barnett-Page and Thomas, 2009; Barbour and Barbour, 2003). The following limitation in M&A analysis has caused partial conclusion from extent of available research. Due to following reason, this study has embarked upon on qualitative synthesis of M&A studies. In some case studies, multiple effect models have been used, but we retained these relationships to single effect for our qualitative synthesis because they are based on different endogenous and exogenous variables.

Figure 4.5 PRISMA guidelines for included and excluded studies

The outline of cases selected in this study for meta-synthesis analysis are provided Appendix-E and summary of cases selected for meta-synthesis are provided Appendix-F with all required details, the time period of them expands from 2000 to 2020. Researcher explored the papers compiled from various sources and while searching for them I always kept in my mind that, these cases are illustrating every aspect related to the areas in question. The most important thing to mention is that these cases are satisfying our objectives very well & help us reaching our desired conclusion.

Figure 4.6 Visual Representation for No. of Included Studies

Figure 4.6 shows that the most cases are discussing about the HRM with 18% and culture compatibility with 16% of two firms merging. With six cases IT/IS integration, communications, and emotion each as the factor influencing the process of M&A comes third in our list of studies under consideration. Except these all (Employee Satisfaction, Training, & Leadership) factors have five or less included studies.

4.1.10. Data Extraction Process

Most relevant studies and data were obtained as follows: (1) M&A studies based on large scale study; (2) Empirical physiognomies i.e., M&A and research targets (3) Exclusion and inclusion criteria; (4) Studies were written in English; (5) Search was restricted to publication from 2000-2020; and (6) the datasets, methodology and results.

4.1.11. Quality and Reliability Assessment

In the last stage, the included research studies in meta-synthesis were independently evaluated for quality, validity, and reliability assessment by the author. To assess the quality, validity and reliability of selected studies, this study used the standard method proposed by Farrukh et al., (2020). The modified version of this tool permits for systematic quality valuation of evidence

from distinct sources which control the risk of bias. As compare to Farrukh et al., (2020), this study restricted its quality valuation to four major categories such as research target, data and design, methodology and results. We assigned a quality score of 1 to very poor, 2 to poor, 3 to good and 4 to very good. If any study is quality score is less 2 that study will be excluded from the meta synthesis.

4.1.12. Internal and external validity (Individual appraisal)

Internal validity of an individual appraisal refers to the proportion or degree to which changes in the endogenous factor of the paper can be examined for exogenous factors. These factors that may be perceived as threats to internal validity which are not the part of exogenous factors in M&A study, but they have a substantial impact on endogenous factor outcome. On the other hand, external validity refers to the extent to which the empirical findings of any specific study can be generalized. The following study used the following quality index to address the treats of internal and external validity and issue of biasness.

Table 4.9 Scoring the Methodological Rigor used by Farrukh et al., (2020)

Scoring	Poor -1	Good -2	Best-3	Excellent-4	Total
Abstract					
Introduction					
Literature Review					
Theoretical Framework					
Material and Methods					
Results & Conclusion					
Suggestions					

Mean value is equal or greater than 2 = Paper is included for meta-synthesis otherwise excluded

4.1.13 Inducing results into Integrative Framework

The next step involves getting the results from qualitative studies using meta-synthesis and applies the results to construct the integrative framework (inductive approach). Framework yet to be applied to a case of mergers and acquisitions of two firms to test the framework (deductive approach). In this study, researcher was not able to apply framework to any organisation. Instead,

this study developed integrative framework which involve resolving issues in relation to factors related to humans which can affect the success or failure of M&A.

Phase Two: Quantitative Phase

4.2 Phase Two Overview

This phase provides specific details of research participants, data analysis and findings procedure. This phase is about the quantitative component of the research which involved the development, administration, and analysis of a survey questionnaire. The findings from the qualitative research induced to quantitative research Creswell et al. (2003) which will help to make necessary changes to the quantitative phase of the study based on the findings and analysis of qualitative phase. The objective of quantitative phase in this research was to have better understandings the interrelationships and correlation between the factors affecting the human and integration process of mergers and acquisitions. The specific details of instrument development, case and participant selection, data collection and analysis have been detailed below. The Phase two structure is outlined in Figure 4.9.

Figure 4.7 Organisational Structure of Phase Two

4.2.1 Ethical Considerations

An ethics application was submitted to the University of West of Scotland before conducting the survey and the research project was granted ethical approval. All ethical issues mentioned are addressed which includes explaining purpose, promises and reciprocity, risk assessment, confidentiality, informed consent, data access and ownership, interviewer mental health, advice, and data collection (Patton,2002).

The aim of this study was explained to the participants and organisational contacts. English language was used as survey was sent to the different multinational companies all over the world. Respondents are offered to request a copy of the final report on this study after completion. Organisational contacts will be provided with the copies of this study after completion so that the results can be used to make informed decisions about M&A so that the success rate can be increased. It has also been promised with the organisation that in order to avoid breaching the confidentiality of respondents or organisational contacts, information would not be provided in such format which would compromise the issues of confidentiality. It was made clear to all individuals that they were free to withdraw at any stage of the process of taking survey and they would not be impacted by the decision of withdrawal in any way. It is also ensuring that the participants would have no impact and all respondents are open to participate to take the survey and there will be no implications in case they do not want to take or want to withdraw during any stage of taking survey.

Risk assessment was conducted in relation to firms and individuals involved in the study before commencing the research and it was considered that this research risk will remain at low level. Any issues in relation to the mental health such as stress and anxiety at work as a result of changes at workplace was not dealt with or shared with anyone as there was no physical contact to understand these issues of respondents in person due to confidentiality measures in place which prevents to disclose the identity of respondents to researcher. All participants were also ensured that the identification of individuals will not be disclosed during the analysis and reporting of findings of this research. Data collected from respondents was stored in a secure location it will be kept for at least two years.

Initially consent was taken from the main contacts at different firms and got access to email database and Informed consent was taken from respondents thereafter via separate email request

using Survey monkey and Mailchimp. Each respondent was sent a link to participate in survey with an Information Sheet (refer Appendix B) and Consent Form (refer Appendix A) using Mail Chimp and Survey Monkey. In return, participants were offered to provide copy of this thesis after completion. Completion of the survey questionnaire was the informed consent provided by participants and they were fully aware that that they could withdraw up to any stage during the survey completion.

Data access and ownership was also considered as an ethical issue. It has been communicated that any information gathered from respondents will not be shared with anyone if it reveals the identification and breach the privacy of individuals. Respondents were familiar with this method and were aware that the data would be used only for this study and retained for at least 2 years of completion of study. All participants were volunteers and none of them available for the interview. Finally, mental health issues of employees were not considered to be critical to discuss with organisational contacts to protect the privacy of participants.

4.2.1.1 Data Collection

The online questionnaire was dispensed by using Survey Monkey program. Now a days, many surveys have been assisted by information technology (Bates, 2001; Braithwaite et al.,2003), but the sustainable use of online questionnaire surveys is yet a critical problem. The pros and cons of online questionnaire surveys have been analysed in various contexts (Braithwaite et al.,2003). Although, the strong and reliable evidence is still lacking to many of questions and concerns that presently exist. A study of principal component analysis) gives a proper list of key pros and cons of online questionnaire surveys methods.

The main pros of online surveying method that were adopted on during this research involving the timeliness, convenience, low administration of cost, and the ease of follow up, data analysis and entry (Bates, 2001; Chatt and Dennis, 2003). The cons of online administrated surveys include problems related to skewed attributes of online users, similarly the respondents lack of interest, expertise, and online experience.

This study used the sample random sampling approach. All respondents were bound to follow this approach, and sampling was controlled by administering the online questionnaire to specific list determining all those in particular positions within the system. This study has collected the sample

of 146 random respondents through this online survey. Survey instrument sent to respondents for this research is provided in Appendix D.

4.2.2 Data Analysis

The findings from quantitative part were empirically estimated to deal with the specific research objectives and analyse the association among various factors of M&A. The advanced statistical package named as “SPSS Version 24” was used to build the M&A index. All the empirical results of quantitative part are given in next chapter, however structure and framework of specific methods employed, and their rationale are described in this section.

This study used the online Survey Monkey^s platform for collecting the cross-sectional data about M&A research questions. This online facility allows for all type of data to be collected online and directly download to MS Excel format. As a researcher, we know that some modifications and data cleaning within MS Excel spreadsheet was essential prior to perform any statistical analysis on SPSS (Chatt and Dennis, 2003; Crawford et al.,2001). After uploading the data in SPSS, the step preformed was to data cleaning and imputation of missing data or values in data sheet. Survey instrument used for data analysis is provided in Appendix C.

4.2.2.1 Normality & Descriptive Analysis

The second stage of empirical analysis involved drawing normality assumptions of the dataset through descriptive analysis in relation to all control and policy research questions. For those research questions with ordinal and nominal scales, percentage and frequency distribution table was estimated. For those research questions with interval scales unit, more rigorous statistical analysis was done such as mean, median, skewness and kurtosis calculations. The stage of normality and descriptive analysis allows for initial examination of quality of data and gives data operator with an opportunity to check the reliability of the data (Rachdawong and Christensen, 1997; Chatt and Dennis, 2003).

4.2.2.2 Testing for Factorability

A testing for factorability analysis is prerequisite test that allows to examine the data suitability for factor analysis. For this purpose, Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) and Bartlett’s Test was used. The KMO test examines the degree to which inter, or intra-correlations exist amongst the specified

dimension or factors. Hence, this test confirms the data suitability for factor analysis (Rachdawong and Christensen, 1997; Chatt and Dennis, 2003; Hu and Jing, 2013). The thresholds of the following test ranges from 0 to 1. It can be interpreted as less than 0.40 (unacceptable for factor analysis), equal or above 0.40 (miserable for factor analysis), equal or above 0.60 (mediocre for factor analysis), equal and above 0.70 (middling for factor analysis), equal and above 0.80 (meritorious for factor analysis). On the other side, Bartlett's test provides the probability. It gives information about degree of correlations some the modelled factors or variables. Both of these tests were used to confirm the cross-sectional data were suitable to be for factor analysis.

4.2.2.3 Validation of Factor Analysis

In this research, Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA) was employed. From the existing body of literature, a great debate has been evolved in recent times about the adaptation of Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA) and Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA). The application of CFA is usually recognized to be more suitable to estimate the specified form of hypothesis. On the other hand, EFA test is more exploratory in empirical point of view and more suitable for scale development (Rachdawong and Christensen, 1997; Pineau and Slotwiner, 2004; Hu and Jing, 2013). Therefore, EFA test was deemed more reliable and suitable for M&A analysis.

4.2.2.4 Principal Component Analysis

Mergers and Acquisitions (M&A) is estimated by several pragmatic and empirical indicators or parameters. M&A analysis show high variation on temporal and spatial basis and its quantitative monitoring findings in a large and complex data set encompassing of large set of indicators or parameters, which are usually difficult to figure out. Employment of various multivariate methods such as Principal Component Analysis (PCA) and Explanatory Factor analysis (EFA) provide a better opportunity to estimate such type of complex situations (Arslan, 2013)

M&A analysis normally require monitoring and analysis of various empirical parameters at the same time. Factor analysis or PCA can preferably reduce the dimensionality of both large as well as small multivariate data set while still accomplishing its fundamental structure to maximum scope possible. Thus, PCA has usually been employed while dealing with management and human resource data (Loska and Wiechula, 2003). This research showcases a significant variation in M&A analysis, i.e., indicators section and it employs the highly advance empirical method-

Principal Component Analysis (PCA) for this investigation. This study also demonstrates the importance of indicators reduction, the applied step that significantly restrict the estimation cost and time and make it more conducive for future studies (Loska and Wiechuła, 2003; Zeinalzadeh and Rezaei, 2017).

Normally, factor extraction technique employed in this research was principal components analysis (PCA). It is usually assumed that the specified factors or items are mutually correlated, because the PCA will help to formulate a new group of factors which are mutually uncorrelated (Zeinalzadeh and Rezaei, 2017). The study of Loska and Wiechuła, (2003) found that the issue of linearity, normality and homoscedasticity are not much significant yardstick in PCA. But the problem of multicollinearity is usually undesirable while using PCA. In the beginning, the PCA was performed determining factors with Eigenvalue (rule of thumb is Eigenvalue must be greater than 1) and diagram of scree was also checked (Zeinalzadeh and Rezaei, 2017).

4.2.2.5 Process of Factor Extraction

Most appropriate approach that should understand while the application of PCA is factor rotation approach. It refers to the process taken to rotation of axes for helping the explanation of empirical results (Zeinalzadeh and Rezaei, 2017). The process of decision making about rotation of axes depends on the degree which researcher believes that mutual correlation exists among various items or factors.

4.2.2.6 Cronbach's Alpha Test (Test for Factor Reliability)

The factors determined from PCA were then verified for reliability by using the Cronbach's Alpha test. It estimates internal reliability by measuring the inter or intra-items correlation within each of the newly determined factors. Only those factors were considered for final analysis which Cronbach's Alpha value was greater than 0.60 (Zeinalzadeh and Rezaei, 2017). It is observed that any items loading negatively onto a factor had to be recoded in order to conduct the Cronbach's alpha. This is necessary because all items within a factor must be unidirectional in order to conduct a Cronbach's alpha (Hu, and Jing, 2013). Principal components analysis (PCA) has been equally useful to apply on group or individual indicator or parameter with motive to capture maximum variance with minimum number of indicators or parameters. It is also demand individual parameters to have a unit equalization hence they have been normalized by following various

techniques such as Min-Max formulation and Z-score. The factors estimation from the large group of parameters or indicators having high correlation amongst themselves. Hence, the aggregation process is based on the “applied process” selected dimension of the given dataset and entirely independent from the original data (Hu, and Jing, 2013).

4.2.3 Steps of PCA Analysis

There is a four-step process involved in building the M&A index to rationalize and identify potential methodological discrepancies. The M&A index depends on well-established and comprehensive broad-spectrum approach presented in next section. The essential theoretical and structural demands for building index were systematically assessed and reported in the next section.

4.2.3.1 Process of Data Mining and Imputation.

Cross sectional data of 146 individuals is collected and carefully arranged for M&A index building in excel sheet. Only those indicators are involved whose more than 94% dataset was available in datasheet. To increase the robustness of the results, the missing values are substituted by a multiple imputation method proposed by Hu, and Jing, (2013).

4.2.3.2 Process of Data Normalization

Each index is min-max normalized ranged from 0 to 1. The higher value of indices characterizes the higher level of M&A effectiveness. Furthermore, the standardized indicators have a spreading range from minimum to maximum. Each index is linearly transformed between the scale 0 and 1. The following rescaling formula is used; $z' = (z - \min(z)) / (\max(z) - \min(z))$. Here the z expresses as the raw value of data, $\min(z)$ and $\max(z)$ indicate the limits for the worst and the best situation separately and after rescaling, z' represents the normalized value. The normalized data is used for index building process.

4.2.3.3 Process of Assigning Weights and Sensitivity Analysis

Each factor has equal importance in the M&A success outcomes; therefore, this study assigned the equal weight to each factor. This study adopted the weighting process, which is used by Strobl et al. (2020) and Bari et al., (2019). They argued that a priori decision to apply the method of the

equal weighting for aggregation process gives evidently unbiased choice of assigning weights. In order to avoid the biasness, the following study adopted the equal weighting system.

4.2.3.4 Process of Aggregation

Aggregation process is the last step in computing the M&A index which yields 0 to 1 score. A lot of approaches such as compensatory and non-compensatory are available to create balance between different dimensions. The aggregation process followed in the current study is proposed by Strobl et al. (2020) and Bari et al., (2019). Table 2 shows the theoretical threshold level of M&A index.

Table 4.2 Theoretical Threshold Level

Factor/Indices	Functional Type*	Upper Bound	Lower Bound
M&A Index	LB	0.98	0
Cultural Index	LB	0.97	0
Cultural Diversity Index	LB	0.86	0
Compensation Index	LB	0.81	0
Emotions Index	LB	0.89	0
Management Change Index	LB	0.91	0
IT System Index	LB	0.84	0

*LB = Lower is bad for Index

4.2.4 Interpretational Criteria

The M&A composite and sub-dimensional index scores range from 0 to 1. The advantages of constructing M&A index are as follow: (1) composite index provides the overview of general scenario, (2) sub-dimension indices allow to make comparison between dimensions, and (3) they reflect the significance of each dimension for M&A outcomes.

Table 4.3 Reading of index score

Index r (0-1)	< 0.20	0.20 -0.40	0.40-0.60	0.60-0.80	0.80>
Index	Very Low	Moderate	Good	Well	Very High

4.2.5 Mixed Method Approach

Mergers and Acquisitions (M&A) is estimated by several pragmatic and empirical indicators or parameters. M&A analysis show high variation on temporal and spatial basis and its quantitative monitoring findings in a large and complex data set encompassing of large set of indicators or parameters, which are usually difficult to figure out. Employment of various multivariate methods such as Principal Component Analysis (PCA) and Explanatory Factor analysis (EFA) provide a better opportunity to estimate such type of complex situations (Arslan, 2013). This study addresses the existing research gap in M&A analysis underlying the Mixed Method approach and observed the outcomes of M&A by involving both qualitative and quantitative aspects. Mixed Method approach refers to a research procedure or design for analysing, collecting, and “Mixing” both qualitative and quantitative method in a single study to estimate the research objectives. This method draws a potential strength of both qualitative and quantitative approach (Farrukh et al, 2020), permitting us to estimate the different aspects and unfold the diverse relationships among complex and broad research questions such as M&A. This research showcases a significant variation in M&A analysis, i.e., indicators section and it employs the highly advance empirical method- Principal Component Analysis (PCA) for this investigation. This study also demonstrates the importance of indicators reduction, the applied step that significantly restrict the estimation cost and time and make it more conducive for future studies (Loska and Wiechuła, 2003; Zeinalzadeh and Rezaei, 2017). Figure 4.7 gives the characteristics of this research design.

Figure 4.8 Concept of Mixed Method Approach

4.2.6 Multiple Regression Approach

This study used the Multiple Regression approach. It also known as multiple regression analysis, it uses different independent variables and one dependent variable in the data.

Figure 4.9 Framework of regression model

The multiple regression analysis shows the relationship between one dependent and several independent variables. The details of our study model are given above as follow.

Chapter 5 - Phase One Results

Chapter Overview

Chapter 4 outlined the data collection, research methodology and analysis procedures. This chapter consist of Phase One of the results which involved the results of Meta Synthesis using qualitative approach. This chapter provides specific details of secondary data analysis using Meta synthesis and findings.

The chapter structure is outlined in Figure 5.1.

Figure 5. 4 Organisational Structure of the Chapter 5

5.1 Results of Meta-Synthesis (Qualitative Approach)

The method of meta-synthesis is also a systematic approach, beyond the scope of traditional literature review through which the results of different qualitative studies on a topic can be examined and presented. The main objective of meta-analysis is to make novel understandings from synthesis and comparison of results of various studies. This approach involves a detailed online search of qualitative research on M&A allowing us to extend beyond the primary or original scope of qualitative studies by explaining analogies between the analytical themes following

different keywords. This meta-synthesis included studies that analyse the research question “how do mergers and acquisitions policies effect the quality of human such as communication, culture, emotion, HRM, IT/IS integration, employee satisfaction, training,”. Finally, the selected research papers were upload into EndNote software and 128 duplicate research studies were deleted by the author during the first stage of screening. Two independent reviewers selected articles for inclusion by following the two-step process. (1) Identified articles were screened based on research title and abstract. If there was conflict among the decision of independent reviewers, the article was sent into the second screening stage without negotiation. (2) the screening of full text paper, the second stage was also done by the author. This study identified the 342 full text studies among which 128 studies were excluded because they did not address inclusion criteria, 110 studies were discarded because they were duplicated. Remaining 104 research studies were reviewed in detail among which 54 research studies were discarded because they were just opinions, literature reviews and editorials. Total 50 selected papers were finally used for meta-synthesis which details provided in Appendix E and Appendix F.

5.2. Meta-Synthesis Results of Specified Factors

The study of Angwin et al., (2014) found that communication was a critical factor in M&A performance, but unexpectedly only few studies has estimated the relationship between various communication approaches and M&A process. This study is done to study the link between the content and process communication and M&A process such as employee commitment to merged organisation policy and M&A existence. They come up with the conclusion that the dynamics of communications practices in Nigerian M&A and responds the calls for developing M&A research beyond other countries. They confirm the significance of communication practices for the performance of pre- and post-M&A process. Another study of Zagelmeyar et al., (2016) investigated the impact of emotions and communication on M&A outcomes. They found that the process of M&A usually increased the stress, anxiety, and uncertainty among employees. They used the qualitative analysis for four global M&A cases and argued that management information and communication are very effective tool during all stages of M&A activities. They come up with results that these cognitive assessments of M&A process triggered negative and positive emotions. As the result they influence employee performance, behaviour, and attitudes and the success of M&A process.

Table 5.10 Tabulation of Meta-Synthesis of Communications

Reference	Design*	Sample Size- (Nature of Data) **	Location	Model***	Key Findings	Quality Index****
Communication						
Angwin et al., (2014)	I	77 (I)	Nigeria	DA	Pre & post both communications practices had significant impact on M&A success.	2.05
Zagelmeyer et al., (2016)	I	50 (I)	Globally	DA	Management Info & communication is an effective tool in M&A process.	2.25
Allata and Harbir, (2011)	I	475 (I)	Globally	RA	Both formal & informal communication is important for M&A success	3.15
Brahma and Srivastava, (2007)	I	155 (I)	India	RA	The process of integration does moderate communication and executive retention has positive impact on M&A performance.	2.98
Papadakis, (2005)	I	72 (I)	Greece	SR	Communication is influential factors in the successful implementation of an M&A.	3.5
Sciweiger, (1991)	I	500 (I)	Globally	RA	Communication has significant impact on M&A success.	2.75

*Design: (I= Qualitative Approach, II= Quantitative Approach), **Nature of Data: (I= Primary Data, II= Secondary Data), ***Model: (DA= Descriptive Analysis, RA= Regression Analysis, SR= Systematic Review, MA= Meta-Analysis, TA= Trend Analysis)

The study of Allata and Harbir, (2011) used the network data of employee's behaviour to examine the changes in employees' communications trends after the post-acquisition period (3 years). The empirical results of this study suggest that the process of new communication develop slowly and was not completely enduring even when a transformative process such as M&A occurs. They

conclude that both formal and informal communication is important for the success of M&A integration. Another study conducted by Brahma and Srivastava, (2007) and studied the five M&A process to understand the role employee stress, executive retention, and communication on M&A performance. They found that both executive retention and communication have a positive impact on M&A performance, whereas organisational employee stress has adverse impact on M&A performance. In this study they also studied whether the communication integration had any impact on M&A performance. This study suggests that the link between performance and employee stress was not moderated by communication integration. Similarly, the study of Papadakis, (2005) investigated what factors impacts a M&A successful implementation. This study used the different approach from traditional research and explored the rang of internal and external factors including communications. The empirical findings indicate that effective communication system is most influential factor in M&A successful implementation. Other the side the study of Sciweiger, (1991) examined the impact of program of realistic communication, realistic merger preview on the performance of employees. This study compares the role of organisational information and employee's communication and found that communication has positive impact on M&A success as compare to information.

Table 5.2 covers the studies based on culture and M&A relationships. Teerikangas and Very, (2006) has examined a critical question about how differences in culture have a short as well as long run impact on the performance of M&A. In this study, they reviewed a widely accepted myth about how culture effects negatively the performance of M&A. They explored the causes for this myth and contradictions and suggest some solutions. In the end, they come up with the findings that culture has long term dynamics on M&A performance either negative or positive. Another study of Hitt et al., (2012) has also been explored the dynamics of M&A. They found that acquiring firms only create little or no value. It is just because of the firm inability to make synergy, selecting inappropriate targets, paying high premium and ineffective process of integration. This study suggests that by carefully selection of targets and through adopting an effective process of acquisitions can create firm value and achieve synergy. This study also suggests some pathways of improvement such as relational target selection and new knowledge acquisitions. These pathways can enhance innovation and firm value as well as profitability over time.

Table 5.11 Tabulation of Meta-Synthesis for Culture

Reference	Design*	Sample Size- (Nature of Data) **	Location	Model***	Key Findings	Quality Index****
Culture						
Teerikangas and Very, (2006)	I	150 (I)	Globally	DA	Difference of Culture has direct influence on M&A success and failure.	2.5
Hitt et al., (2012)	I	1983–2008 (II)	Globally	SR	Culture has an effective role on M&A process.	2.28
Stahl and Voigt, (2007)	I	26 (I)	Globally	MA	The dynamics of cultural differences vary depending on dimensions of cultural differences and degree of relatedness.	3.1
Drori et al., (2011)	I	46 (I)	Israel	RA	Social factors/actors entering mergers process may enact a culture of equality.	3.5
Fang et al, (2004)	II	1997-99 (II)	Swedish, Norway	TA	Historical sentiments, feelings, and emotions, if not handled well, can cause fatal damage to cross-cultural business ventures.	3.12
Dhillon et al., (2016)	I	60 (I)	Europe	MA	Supportive culture is an opportunity for M&A success.	3.5
Halsall, (2008)	I	47 (I)	UK	MA	Cultural, economic, and political discourses have significant impact on M&A success	3.15
Weber and Camerer, (2003)	I	20 (I)	USA	MA	New culture has adverse impact on long term performance of M&A.	2.5

*Design: (I= Qualitative Approach, II= Quantitative Approach), **Nature of Data: (I= Primary Data, II= Secondary Data), ***Model: (DA= Descriptive Analysis, RA= Regression Analysis, SR= Systematic Review, MA= Meta-Analysis, TA= Trend Analysis)

Similarly, Stahl and Voigt, (2007) reviewed a large body of literature about the impact of culture on M&A performance and found that diversity in culture among merging firms can be a major obstacle to attain M&A integration benefits. On the other hand, they also explored an opposite

viewpoint that culture diversity among the merging firms can be an important source of gaining knowledge and value creation. In this study they present a model which qualitatively synthesizes the present understanding of impact of culture on M&A and gave a set of hypotheses regarding the pathway through which culture diversity impacts the performance of M&A. The synthesis results suggest that culture diversity affect synergy realization, sociocultural integration, and firm value in opposite way. On the same way Drori et al., (2011) explored the equality and justices as a dynamic construct linked with two important processes in M&A such as cultural construction and cultural clash. The study used the qualitative approach to examine the impact of culture and equality on M&A process. They found the answer to following question of why and how social agents came into mergers which may enact an equality of culture. They conclude that any change in strategic action which can transform the meaning of a “merger of equals” to more pragmatic, practical, and integrative cultural equality as per the needs and interests of merged organisation. They suggest that cultural equality is a crucial factor for the success of post-merger integration. Another study of Fang et al, (2004) examined the merger of IT firm by reviewing various factors such as culture and joint venture. They found that feelings and emotions and historical sentiments, if not addressed properly can cause major damage to cross- cultural business mergers. On the same way the study of Dhillon et al., (2016) examined the formal security polices, technical infrastructure changes and normative cultural clashes on the performance of M&A. They found that the factor like change in security culture and normative clash can make the firm more vulnerable after M&A integration. Halsall, (2008) examined the discourse of controversies of two international firms after M&A. These M&A controversies were evolved due to diversity of culture among various firms. This study reviews how economic, culture and political discourses relating to global integration were used strategically. Similarly, Weber and Camerer, (2003) explored M&A failure due to cultural diversity. They found that performance of merged firms is largely affected due to conflicting culture. Table 5.3 contains the meta synthesis of studies based on emotions and M&A relationships. The study of Cartwright and Cooper, (1991) studied the prospects of profitability and extension of market share and role of human aspect like emotions on the performance of M&A. In this study, they found that human aspect like emotions can affect the employee’s mental health and wellbeing. This study suggests that high degree of cultural diversity due to M&A can impact the employee’s emotions which had direct impact of their work performance. Another study of Goyal and Joshi, (2012) examined that M&A processes are

unavoidable event so as stress management. Whenever any changes in firm such as M&A take place employees are supposed to adopt and affect from them. In this study they found that if these changes are not managed properly ultimately, they may adversely change the emotions of employees. On the other they also pointed out some other factors which can affect the performance of employees such as job insecurity, uncertainty, cultural factor, and technology use.

Table 5.12 Tabulation of Meta-Synthesis for Emotions

Reference	Design*	Sample Size- (Nature of Data) **	Location	Model***	Key Findings	Quality Index****
Emotions						
Cartwright and Cooper, (1991)	II	300 (I)	UK	RA	M&A process increase stress and mental health of workers	3.12
Goyal and Joshi, (2012)	II	60 (I)	India	WAM	M&A was found as major psychological factors Such as uncertainty, insecurity, job changes and threat of job loss which create stress among employees	2.9
Tikkakoski et al., (2018)	I	139 (I)	Turkey	MA	Emotions play a vital role to trigger the M&A success.	3.2
Hassetta et al., (2018)	I	164 (I)	Global	MA	Both positive and negative emotions increased by individual, and company-level had significant impact on M&A process.	3.5
Kiefer et al., (2001)	I	50 (I)	Global	SR	Organisational changes, especially M&A process are very with change in emotive events	3.1
Fisher, (2000)	I	121 (I)	USA	RA	Positive and negative emotions both make unique contributions to M&A success.	3.2

Design: (I= Qualitative Approach, II= Quantitative Approach), **Nature of Data: (I= Primary Data, II= Secondary Data), *Model: (DA= Descriptive Analysis, RA= Regression Analysis, SR= Systematic Review, MA= Meta-Analysis, TA= Trend Analysis)*

A recent study of Tikkakoski et al., (2018) gave the insight about the complex relationship between emotions and pre and post M&A integration. In this study, they come up with view that M&A process is highly sensitive agreements. Due the involvement of strong emotion evoked. They conclude that misunderstanding about emotion may be the one of the core reasons of M&A failure. Another study of Hassetta et al., (2018) analysed the impact of post M&A situation on the top merger emotions and the factors and consequences which can trigger the emotions too. This study found that the event like M&A are very sensitive and emotional for key person and top managers. The study revealed that top managers experience a different range of positive and negative emotions triggered by M&A integrations. These positive and native emotions can influence the company performance in both in short as well as long term. Similarly, Kiefer et al., (2001) examined the organisational changes such as M&A are very much sensitive to human aspects like emotion and sentiments. In this study, they focused on cognitive aspects and emotions mainly as human aspect or factors for interference with implementing the changes of M&A. The results explored that emotions deeply affect the performance of managers. The study of Fisher, (2000) investigated the key factors which describe the job satisfaction especially in M&A. This study explored various hypothesized links among real time factors which influence the performance of job. The study found that both positive and negative emotions make a greater contribution to develop a satisfactory environment for employees.

Table 5.4 holds the meta synthesis of studies based on HRM and M&A relationships. Antila and Kakkonen, (2007) examined the causes behind the HR managers contribution in global M&A process by involving the various factors. In this study, they found the six set of factors that can influence the role of HR manager. They found that among the top management, the role of HR manager is very critical under M&A process. Aguilera et al., (2008) studied the links between three pillars of organisation and six factors of socialization in the context of M&A. This study proposed that post M&A integration will be more efficient and effective when socialization process is equipped with internalization of necessary actions. This study argued that HR domain is most prominent institution in any organisation. Murugesan and Venugopsl, (2018) observed that M&A integrations are largely being used by organisations to maintain and strengthens them

Table 5.13 Tabulation of Meta-Synthesis for HRM

Reference	Design*	Sample Size- (Nature of Data) **	Location	Model***	Key Findings	Quality Index****
HRM						
Antila and Kakkonen, (2007)	I	12 (I)	UK	SR	Most important contributing factors to HR managers' participation are HR managers' own capability and activity throughout the M&A process	3.4
Aguilera et al., (2008)	I	44 (I)	Global	MA	Most difficult task M&A process is to minimize the negative effects on employees.	3.1
Murugesan and Venugopsl, (2018)	I	20 (I)	Global	DA	Many mergers fail to achieve their objectives because HR professionals are not involved in M&A process.	3.02
Chang-Howe, (2019)	I	35 (I)	Global	SR	HRM has positive impact on M&A successes.	2.5
Weber, (2015)	I	40 (I)	Global	DA	The training and development during post-merger integration, to deal with the effects of culture clash situations in M&A, are pivotal for success.	3.8
Weber and Drori, (2011)	I	24 (I)	UK	DA	HR changing during the process of M&A that effects the organisational progress.	2.9
Krug and Aguilera, (2004)	I	71 (I)	Global	MA	Top HR team has direct role on the success of M&A process	3.1
King et al., (2014)	I	46 (I)	Global	SR	HRM had significant role on the performance of M&A integration.	2.78
Pawan et al., (2016)	I	N.A (I)	Global	SR	HR office played a key in the performance of post M&A process.	2.2

*Design: (I= Qualitative Approach, II= Quantitative Approach), **Nature of Data: (I= Primary Data, II= Secondary Data),

***Model: (DA= Descriptive Analysis, RA= Regression Analysis, SR= Systematic Review, MA= Meta-Analysis, TA= Trend Analysis)

marketplace and position. It is also observed that it relatively fast and much efficient tool to expend into new market by incorporating new IT systems. Although some failures can be observed as market and financial factors, a large number can be found to neglect HR activities and issues. This study stressed upon the need for organisations to comprehensively address the HR activities and issues in M&A process. Chang-Howe, (2019) purposed the perspective approach for post M&A integration process along with the special focus on HR integration. This study used the qualitative approach by using the systematic review approach. This study suggests that HR integration is as much as important the M&A integration for increasing the performance of any organisation. The study of Weber, (2005) highlighted the importance of HR training and development during post M&A process. In this study, they present the role of individual employee in corporate culture clash solution for the post M&A situation. The study come up with the results that dynamics of culture clash in M&A on acquired the management behaviour and attitude. This study suggests that these effects influence the performance of post M&A integration and turnover success. Therefore, training and development during post M&A integration is important to address the challenges of new market. Another study of Weber and Drori, (2011) presented a conceptual framework for examining the M&A performance through multilevel and multistage approach. The first HR challenge during M&A integration process is deal with to help describe the inconsistencies between empirical findings and effects of cultural diversity on M&A performance. This study proposed that the factors like organisational identification, culture clash and management attitude are the critical factors for determining the success of M&A agreements. The study of Pawan et al., (2016) observed that M&A integrations process are increasingly becoming a prominent choice for organisations attempting to attain and sustain relative and comparative advantage. In this study, they examined the three main reasons or major causes for the failure of M&A process. they analysed that HR functions played a significant role for addressing the causes of M&A failure.

Table 5.5 comprises the meta synthesis of studies based on information system and M&A relationships. Hsu and Chen, (2006) highlighted that how information system decision making process made at firm level which enabled the various pathways for different firms to work together along with M&A processes. This study also presented the problems with IT system integration as results of M&A. They come up with the conclusion that IS has significant role to strength the working environment after the M&A.

Table 14.5 Tabulation of Meta-Synthesis for IT and Systems

Reference	Design*	Sample Size- (Nature of Data) **	Location	Model***	Key Findings	Quality Index****
IT and Systems						
Budhwar et al., (2009)	I	N. A	India	TM	HR functions play an important role for addressing post M&A issues.	2.5
Hsu and Chen, (2006)	I	N. A	Global	DA	M&A activity has an impact on IS and conversely, so does IS on M&A activity.	2.9
Alaranta, (2005)	I	168 (I)	Finland	TM	Efficient and effective IS integration management, Efficient IS staff integration and IS ability to support the underlying motives of the merger.	2.2
Bhattacharya et al., (2010)	I	144 (I)	Australia	TM	IS used to integrate, optimize and information, can help firms achieve alliance innovation, process innovation and reshaped business strategy.	2.8
Jordan, (2019)	I	17 (I)	Global	SR	IS can assist business leaders in understanding the importance of organisational integration planning in the earliest phases of M&A transactions to improve M&A successes.	3.5
Tanriverdi and Uysal, (2011)	II	141 (I)	Austin	RA	CBITI has major role to transform the business under M&A agreements	3.2

*Design: (I= Qualitative Approach, II= Quantitative Approach), **Nature of Data: (I= Primary Data, II= Secondary Data),

***Model: (DA= Descriptive Analysis, RA= Regression Analysis, SR= Systematic Review, MA= Meta-Analysis, TA= Trend Analysis)

Another study of Alaranta, (2005) examined the importance of IS for M&A. This study investigated the meta synthesis of various definitions of post M&A and IS integration success through qualitative evaluation. Therefore, this study presented the four broad categories of success issues for M&A and IS integration. The empirical results proposed integrated software system, effective and efficient IS integration management, information quality and IS efficient staff integration are important factors the success of M&A process. Bhattacharya et al., (2010) reported and explored the IS potential to enable business transformations for achieving the success of

merger. In this study, they proposed the new model which emphasis upon the potential of IS to reshape and innovate the business plan and strategy, instead of mainly focusing of operational benefits of M&A. This new model deals with IS systems which was used to informant, optimize, and integrate the system that can be helpful for the firm to innovate and reshape the business according to the demand of M&A process. Finally, this study suggests that IS integration is important for achieving the success of M&A. Another study of Jordan, (2019) used the qualitative synthesis approach to study the firm integration strategies that use to examine the post M&A performance and business growth expectations. This study identified the following themes such as communications, firm planning, growth, performance, culture, management, and leadership. This study found that communication, firm planning, IS system and leadership have positive impact on the M&A performance. These factors are also helpful to stabilize the employment sector through creating the new opportunities for jobs and create positive economic activities for the economy. Tanriverdi and Uysal, (2011) has developed the set of ideas for explaining the relationship between the cross-business information technology integration (CBTI) and M&A outcomes. This study found that IT integration system and IT management processes had positive impact on M&A performance. In the long run, if a firm with high level of IS capabilities attain massively higher abnormal operation performance as well as they are also helpful to create higher value for the firm before and after the M&A.

Table 5.6 covers the meta synthesis of studies based on job satisfaction and M&A relationships. Adekola, (2011) found that there is need to empower human capital to enhance innovation and creativity through career planning by using HRM strategies, practices, and policies to create various mindsets, competencies, and skills with the ultimate objective to supply a range of innovative services and practices is appealing attentions. This study explored the relationship between career management and planning as career commitment and job satisfaction as its outcome. The empirical results suggest that the factors like career management, career planning, career development are significant factors for achieving job satisfaction. Similarly, job satisfaction is an important feature of attaining success of any M&A process. Another study of Kyeraa, (2016) studied the dynamics of M&A on employee satisfaction within banking industry. The following study used qualitative approach. This study found that nature of M&A had significant and positive impact on employee satisfaction. The empirical study finally and mainly suggests that post M&A

period, management culture and organisational goals had positive impact on the performance of M&A. The study of Gupta, (2012) observed the relationship between job satisfaction and M&A.

Table 5.15 Tabulation of Meta-Synthesis for Job Satisfaction

Reference	Design*	Sample Size- (Nature of Data) **	Location	Model***	Key Findings	Quality Index****
Job Satisfaction						
Adekola, (2011)	II	505 (I)	Nigeria	RA	Career planning and career management, and career development has significant on M&A process.	3.01
Kyeraa, (2016)	II	150 (I)	Europe	TA	M&A had a significant positive impact on job satisfaction.	2.8
Gupta, 2012	I	N. A	USA	TA	Success of M&A is an essential component for job satisfaction.	2.5
Gugler and Yurtoglu, (2004)	II	1987-1998 (II)	USA	RA	M&A has positive impact on labour demand	3.5
Maditinos et al., (2009)	II	122 (I)	UK	GARCH	M&A not only positively impact profitability but also job satisfaction.	2.6

*Design: (I= Qualitative Approach, II= Quantitative Approach), **Nature of Data: (I= Primary Data, II= Secondary Data),

***Model: (DA= Descriptive Analysis, RA= Regression Analysis, SR= Systematic Review, MA= Meta-Analysis, TA= Trend Analysis)

Now a days, M&A are the strategic growth process in the hand of modern companies not only to remain in competition but also enhanced the size of market and share and dominance at global level. This study claimed that M&A has become a strategic concept to grow rapidly for the large companies across the world. The booms in M&A recommends that firms are spending great amount of time and money to have such agreements. Another study of Gugler and Yurtoglu, (2004) systematically analysed the impact of M&A on the demand of labour in USA and Europe. This study did not find any negative impact of M&A on the labour demand in USA, but they found the adverse impact of M&A on labour demand in Europe during per and post-merger levels. Similarly, Maditinos et al., (2009) investigated the effects of M&A on two banks. This study is done in two sections. The first section investigates the impact of M&A in short run-in banking sector of USA. In the second section studies the long run impact of M&A on the two banks. The empirical findings show that job satisfaction is prerequisite for increasing the profitability of the banks in both short and long run in USA.

Table 5.16 Tabulation of Meta-Synthesis for Leadership

Reference	Design*	Sample Size- (Nature of Data) **	Location	Model***	Key Findings	Quality Index****
Leadership						
Gill, (2012)	I	N. A	Japan	TM	Leadership is key factor for the success of M&A	3.5
Mishra et al., 2018	II	2007-2010 (II)	India	TA	Leadership and culture are the real contributor for the M&A success	2.8
King et al., (2004)	I	93 (I)	Global	MS	Leadership is important factor after post M&A success or failure	2.75
Bari et al., (2019)	II	550 (I)	Pakistan-China	PLS-SEM	Productive deals of M&As would be helpful in underpinning the exclusive growth	3.1
Junni and Sarala, (2014)	I	69 (I)	Global	SR	M&A leadership influences post-M&A outcome	2.6

*Design: (I= Qualitative Approach, II= Quantitative Approach), **Nature of Data: (I= Primary Data, II= Secondary Data), ***Model: (DA= Descriptive Analysis, RA= Regression Analysis, SR= Systematic Review, MA= Meta-Analysis, TA= Trend Analysis)

Table 5.7 holds the meta synthesis of studies based on leadership and M&A relationships. The study of Gill, (2012) considered the combined and relative impact of leadership and organisational culture on the performance of M&A. It also examined the causes of success and failure factors of M&A process. The study found that the national culture directly or indirectly influenced the HRM practices and organisational culture. The empirical results suggest that leadership is a significant factor for achieving the success of M&A. Mishra et al., 2018 explored the impact of trust during post M&A integration in Indian IT sector. This study used the qualitative approach through reviewing the existing work focusing only on M&A studies. The prime intention behind this research is to understand the cultural disparity and leadership role in cultural alinement under the M&A integration. The following study found that trust and leadership played a significant role for attaining the success of M&A agreements, epically post M&A process. King et al., (2004) employed the meta-analytic approach to statically estimate the effect of various factors on post M&A performance. This study found the robust findings which indicating that most common

factors do not have any significant difference in pre and post M&A. On the other side the non-common factor like leadership and management skills have positive and significant impact on the performance of M&A. Another study of Bari et al., (2019) investigated the impact of knowledge, information, technology, culture, and leadership style on the performance of M&A. This study found that these factors may increase the success of M&A agreement. This study presented a conceptual framework for examining the M&A performance through multilevel and multistage approach. The first HR challenge during M&A integration process is deal with to help describe the inconsistencies between empirical findings and effects of cultural diversity on M&A performance. This study proposed that the factors like organisational identification, culture clash and management attitude are the critical factors for determining the success of M&A agreements. Another study of Junni and Sarala, (2014) examined the dynamics of M&A leadership by using the systematic review approach of leadership research. This study found that how M&A leadership effects the future outcome of M&A. They come up with the conclusion that leadership attributes have positive role on the success of M&A agreements.

Table 5.17 Tabulation of Meta-Synthesis for Training

Reference	Design*	Sample Size- (Nature of Data) **	Location	Model***	Key Findings	Quality Index****
Training						
Bansal, (2017)	I	N. A	Global	TM	Training has proven to be important in building employee commitment and mitigating the feelings of alienation.	3.1
Thakur et al., (2016)	II	117 (I)	Global	RA	Role of training in developing feelings of psychological empowerment, thriving, commitment and satisfaction with the merger.	2.5
Suifan, (2015)	II	500 (I)	Jordan	RA	HR practices examined (training, person-organisation fit, and rewards) were significantly and positively associated with M&A.	2.8
Grund and Titz, (2018)	I	N. A	Global	SR	Training is positively related to affective commitment of M&A	3.2

*Design: (I= Qualitative Approach, II= Quantitative Approach), **Nature of Data: (I= Primary Data, II= Secondary Data),

***Model: (DA= Descriptive Analysis, RA= Regression Analysis, SR= Systematic Review, MA= Meta-Analysis, TA= Trend Analysis)

Table 5.8 comprehends the meta synthesis of studies based on training and M&A relationships. Bansal, (2017) estimated the impact of training on cross culture M&A. The following study found that training has been proven as important factor for capacity building and increasing the employee's commitment in post M&A. The review of vast body of work revealed that there is significant link between employee training and post M&A performance. Thakur et al., (2016) studied the impact of training on employees' psychological outcomes during M&A in India. The following study estimated the role of various type of training on employees feeling and empowerment. They conclude that training of staff improves the feelings on employees which ultimate helps to attain success in M&A. Similarly, Grund and Titz, (2018) investigated the role of staff taring and effective commitment on the performance of M&A. overall results suggest that training and effective commitment had positive impact on the success of M&A. They found that the process of M&A usually increased the stress, anxiety, and uncertainty among employees. They used the qualitative analysis for four global M&A cases and argued that management information and communication are very effective tool during all stages of M&A activities. They come up with results that these cognitive assessments of M&A process triggered negative and positive emotions. As the result they influence employee performance, behaviour, and attitudes and the success of M&A process.

Chapter 6 - Phase Two Results

Chapter Overview

Chapter 5 outlined the analysis and findings of Phase One of the study. This chapter provides the specific details of Phase Two which involved quantitative approach using SPSS to perform Principal Component Analysis. The research participants, data analysis and findings of each human and composite index and their analysis provided. The reliability of data was tested through Cronbach Alpha and used the descriptive statistical measures such as frequency, mean, median, mode, measures of dispersion and measures of shape to assess the general theme of the data.

Finally, regression/ correlation analysis provided to evaluate the association among dependent and independent explanatory variables.

The chapter structure is outlined in Figure 6.1.

Figure 6. 5 Organisational Structure of the Chapter 6

6.1 Results of descriptive analysis

6.1.1 Overview of firms involved

The firms involved in the Phase Two were from different backgrounds and sectors. They are working in various sector such as services, manufacturing sectors etc. Details of sectors and countries are given in figure 6.2 and 6.3 respectively. Further details about the respondents and their origin are provided in table 6.1. It is important that all selected firms are involved in M&A process within or outside the country. Results of the M&A shows that various organisations inherited systems, processes, and many of which duplicated, or the information is overlapped, and different organisations have approached similar tasks in different ways or way of doing things and

process information differently from other firms. Every firm have its own systems, processes, culture, leadership, and communication styles before M&A and based on the M&A goals, these organisations merger or acquire. The aim of this could be to change the existing systems, processes, leadership and replace them new or merger them together and create mix of both styles. Other firms involved in M&A have goals in relation to replace the many previous systems and eliminate the replication and duplication of information and activities and based on that they merge or acquire other firms to achieve economies of scale. No matter what you going to change within the firm, it is always going to affect the humans who are working or maintaining these systems, processes, and functions of the organisations. Similarly, these are humans who help to keep the culture, leadership, values, communication styles and structures which run the organisations smoothly. Therefore, this phase involved in widespread involvement of humans which required to let go of old ways of doing things and adopt new ways, this gave a sufficiently large population of individuals for sampling purposes for the quantitative analysis in Phase Two.

Figure 6.2 Principal Industry of Organisation

Figure 6.3 Country of Origin

6.1.2 Response Rate and Data Preparation

This section contains response rate and data preparation process. Initially, the questionnaire was sent to 2490 people involved in the mergers and acquisitions at different phases and different levels within the organisations. These individuals worked within different departments of the organisations and implementation of the new system, in the form of an email invitation as well as personal messages through LinkedIn profile to participate which included a hyperlink to the online survey questionnaire. A total of 147 responses were received, out of which only 61 individuals fully completed the survey which means an overall response rate of 45.5%. Data was downloaded from Survey Monkey and extracted into an Excel file, and then imported into SPSS. The data was cleaned and reviewed for any errors and then reviewed for anomalies and omissions. Various respondents were identified which have not completed the survey. These were discarded from the final analysis, leaving a total of 61 total usable responses to be reported within this analysis. It was also noted during the cleaning of data, that 13 respondents gave the response in detail as in qualitative format instead of choosing the options from multiple choice questions. The data was

cleaned and reviewed for any errors and then reviewed for anomalies and omissions, and a further five respondents were identified as not having answered more than the demographics in the survey.

Table 6.1 Country of Origin

Answer Choices	% age	Responses
Afghanistan	0.66%	1
Algeria	0.66%	1
Australia	1.99%	3
Bangladesh	1.32%	2
Bhutan	0.66%	1
Canada	1.32%	2
Ecuador	0.66%	1
France	3.97%	6
Germany	5.96%	9
India	9.27%	14
Iraq	1.32%	2
Ireland	1.32%	2
Kazakhstan	1.32%	2
Lithuania	0.66%	1
Norway	1.32%	2
Pakistan	1.32%	2
Poland	0.66%	1
Singapore	0.66%	1
Spain	0.66%	1
Switzerland	1.32%	2
United Kingdom of Great Britain and Northern Ireland	31.13%	47
United States of America	31.79%	48

6.1.3 Demographics Analysis

Table 6.2 provides the descriptive statistics of all respondents. In summary, over 76% of respondents were male and over 50% respondents are fell within the age bracket of 25-44 years of age. Over 29% of respondents are working at executive level and 55% of employees having more than 2 years of experience of working with the company. Most importantly 47% of respondents are from bidding company and 41% including external consultants hired to help with M&A within different areas of firms. About 23% of respondents were working at to management and same percentage of people are working in the middle management and having 2 years of experience of working with the company.

Table 6.2 Results of demographic analysis

Gender	Questions	N	%	Valid %	Cumulative %
	Female		35	23.8	23.8
Male		112	76.2	76.2	100
Total		147	100	100	
Age	18 to 24	7	4.8	4.8	4.8
	25 to 34	40	27.2	27.2	32
	35 to 44	34	23.1	23.1	55.1
	45 to 54	40	27.2	27.2	82.3
	55 to 64	22	15	15	97.3
	65 to 74	4	2.7	2.7	100
	Total	147	100	100	
Current Job Level	Owner/Executive/C-Level	42	28.6	29	29
	Senior Management	34	23.1	23.4	52.4
	Middle Management	35	23.8	24.1	76.6
	Intermediate	19	12.9	13.1	89.7
	Entry Level	15	10.2	10.3	100
	Total	145	98.6	100	
	Missing System	2	1.4		
	Total	147	100		
Job Experience	Less than 6 months	21	14.3	14.4	14.4
	6 months - 1 year	20	13.6	13.7	28.1
	1 - 2 years	24	16.3	16.4	44.5
	More than 2 years	81	55.1	55.5	100
	Total	146	99.3	100	
	Missing System	1	0.7		
	Total	147	100		
Others	Other – External Consult	60	40.8	41.1	41.1
	Acquired (target firm)	17	11.6	11.6	52.7
	Acquiring (bidding firm)	69	46.9	47.3	100
	Total Respondents	146	99.3	100	
	Missing System	1	0.7		

Total	147	100
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6.2 Empirical Results of Model Variables

This section 6.2 is organized as follow: the sub section 6.2.1 presents the trend of M&A index and demonstrate important information about the magnitude and range of the series. Section 6.2.2 presents the empirical results of Cronbach Alfa approach. In the last the sub section 6.2.3 presents the results of regression analysis.

6.2.1 Trend and Magnitude of Mergers and Acquisitions (M&A) Series

The prime objective of this study was to build a numerical index series of merger and acquisition named as M&A index. For the following purpose, this study involved six key factor or dimensions which directly or indirectly influence the performance of M&A process. Results of PCA analysis unveil noteworthy information about M&A index after assigning diverse weights while the aggregation process of index. Figure 6.2 shows the radar diagram of M&A index series. It shows the progress and performance of M&A process.

Figure 6.4 Radar Diagram of Progress of M&A process

The following diagram also shows the influence of all the selected factors such as culture, culture diversity, communication, emotion, leadership and HRM on the performance of M&A outcome. Overall trend of radar diagram depicts that a company has made substantial progress after M&A process. On the other hand, the figure 6.3 shows that mean value of M&A index series was 0.37. The Max value of M&A index series was 0.98, Min value was zero and SD value was 0.36. M&A analysis normally require monitoring and analysis of various empirical parameters at the same time. This research showcases a significant variation in M&A analysis, i.e., indicators section and it employs the highly advance empirical method- Principal Component Analysis (PCA) for this investigation. This study also proved the importance of indicators reduction, the applied step that significantly restrict the estimation cost and time and make it more conducive for future studies (Loska and Wiechula, 2003; Zeinalzadeh and Rezaei, 2017). These pragmatic findings are affiliated with the findings of standing literature such as (Bari et al., 2019; Mishra et al., 2018; Junni and Sarala, 2014).

Figure 6.5 Trend of Modelled Series

M&A index series yields range between 0 to 1. M&A index provides the overview of M&A outcome. It also gives comparison of different factors and their importance for M&A progress.

6.2.2 Trend and Magnitude of Control Variables

The following section allow us to extend beyond the basic or original scope of quantitative analysis and examined the role of different control variables such as communication, culture, emotion, HRM, IT/IS integration, employee satisfaction, training on the performance of M&A outcome.

Figure 6.4 shows the radar diagram of culture index series. It shows the progress and role of culture while M&A process. The mean value of culture index series was 0.36. The Max value of culture index series was 0.97, Min value was zero and SD value was 0.32. Quantitative analysis normally requires monitoring and analysis of various empirical parameters at the same time. This study showcases a significant variation in culture index, i.e., indicators section and it employs the highly advance empirical method- Principal Component Analysis (PCA) for this investigation.

Figure 6.6 Radar Diagram of Progress of Culture Dimension

Figure 6.7 Radar Diagram of Progress of Culture Diversity Dimension

Figure 6.5 shows the radar diagram of cultural diversity index series. It shows the performance and role of cultural diversity while M&A process. The mean value of cultural diversity index series was 0.33. The Max value of cultural diversity index series was 0.86, Min value was zero and SD value was 0.32. Quantitative analysis normally requires monitoring and analysis of various empirical parameters at the same time. This study found a significant variation in cultural diversity among firms during pre- and post-merger process.

Figure 6.8 Radar Diagram of Progress of Compensation Dimension

Figure 6.6 shows the radar diagram of compensation index series. It shows the performance and role of compensation on M&A process and outcomes. The mean value of compensation index series was 0.30. The Max value of compensation index series was 0.81, Min value was zero and SD value was 0.29. Quantitative analysis normally requires monitoring and analysis of various empirical parameters at the same time. This study found a significant variation in cultural diversity among firms during pre- and post-merger process.

Figure 6.7 shows the radar diagram of emotion index series. It shows the dynamics of emotions dimension on M&A process and outcomes. The mean value of emotion index series was 0.30 The Max value of emotion index series was 0.89, Min value was zero and SD value was 0.35. Quantitative analysis normally requires monitoring and analysis of various empirical parameters at the same time. This study found a significant variation in emotion dimension of employees of firms during pre- and post-merger process.

Figure 6.9 Radar Diagram of Progress of Emotions Dimension

Figure 6.8 shows the radar diagram of Management Change index series. It shows the dynamics of management change on M&A process and outcomes. The mean value of management change series was 0.30 The Max value of management change index series was 0.89, Min value was zero and SD value was 0.35. This empirical analysis found a significant impact of management change on the performance of any firm during pre- and post-merger outcome. Similarly, Figure 6.9 shows the radar diagram of IT system index series. It shows the dynamics of IT system on M&A process and outcomes. The mean value of IT system index series was 0.26 The Max value of IT system index series was 0.84, Min value was zero and SD value was 0.31. Quantitative analysis normally requires monitoring and analysis of various empirical parameters at the same time. This study found a significant impact of IT system on pre- and post-merger process and outcome of any firm. The following information is helpful to stabilize the employment sector through creating the new opportunities for jobs and create positive economic activities for the economy.

Figure 6.10 Radar Diagram of Progress of Management Change Dimension

Figure 6.11 Radar Diagram of Progress of IT System Dimension

6.3 Results of Normality and Regression Analysis

6.3.1 Results of Cronbach Alfa Approach

All items are estimated through a well-structured online questionnaire survey by considering the study context and objectives. There are the following items are used to measures the performance of M&A process

6.3.1.1 Culture and M&A process

Question 8,9, 10 and 13 (4 items) are used to contract culture index. The culture index scale consisted of 5 points Likert scale approach at where “1” linked stands to “strongly disagree” and “5” linked stands to the response “strongly agree”. The Cronbach Alfa value is 0.89 (see Table 6.4).

Table 6.3 List of Questions about culture

Factors	Questions	Abbreviation
Culture	My company gives value to listening to the employees and consider feedback before making decision	Q8
	At my company we treat mistakes like learning opportunities, rather than personal failures.	Q9
	I am satisfied with the culture of my workplace.	Q10
	Both merging firms have suitable cultural fit?	Q13

6.3.1.2 Cultural Diversity and M&A process

Question 18,19, 20,21,22,23,24,25,26,27 and 28 (11 items) are used to contract cultural diversity index. The cultural diversity index scale consisted of 5 points Likert scale approach at where “1” linked stands to “strongly disagree” and “5” linked stands to the response “strongly agree”. The Cronbach Alfa value is 0.97 (see Table 6.4).

Table 6.4 Results of Cronbach's Alfa

Factors	Items	Cronbach's Alfa Stats
M&A	6	0.95
Culture	4	0.89
Cultural Diversity	11	0.97
Compensation	4	0.80
Communication	6	0.96
Emotions	9	0.94
Management Change	8	0.86
IT System	9	0.93

Table 6.5 List of Questions Included in Cultural Diversity

Factors	Questions	Abbreviation
Cultural Diversity	The leadership at this company encourages diversity.	Q18
	This company gives respect to individuals and value their differences.	Q19
	Employees who are different in background from others are treated fairly in our company.	Q20
	At this company, employees are not resentful of others because of their different race or ethnicity.	Q21
	I have personally experienced discrimination at work.	Q22
	Employees from different backgrounds are encouraged to apply for higher positions.	Q23
	This company provides an environment for the free and open expression of ideas opinions and beliefs.	Q24
	My supervisor/manager handles my personal issues satisfactorily and support me to improve at work.	Q24
	Goals and vision of company are clear to everyone in your team?	Q26
	Everyone seems engaging and committed to the organisation's goals.	Q27
	I can see career growth and development opportunities in this organisation.	Q28

6.3.1.3 Compensation and M&A process

Question 29,30,31and 32 (4 items) are used to contract compensation index. The compensation index scale consisted of 2-degree points ordinal scale approach at where “1” linked stands to “Yes” and “2” linked stands to the response “No”. The Cronbach Alfa value is 0.80.

Table 6.6 List of Questions included in Compensation

Factors	Questions	Abbreviation
Compensation	I have a good understanding of compensation policies and practices that affect me.	Q29
	The wellness benefits offered by my company have improved my physical and/or mental health.	Q30
	I am compensated (salary/wages) fairly	Q31
	I believed that there will be potential for career growth and increase in incentives and compensation after this M&A.	Q32

6.3.1.4 Communication and M&A process

Question 33,34,35,36,37,38 and 39 (6 items) are used to construct communication index. The communication index scale consisted of 5 points Likert scale approach at where “1” linked stands to “strongly disagree” and “5” linked stands to the response “strongly agree”. The Cronbach Alfa value is 0.96.

Table 6.7 List of Questions included in Communications

Factors	Questions	Abbreviation
Communication	My company way of communication with employees about mergers is very clear and formal?	Q33
	How well does your company facilitate communication among employees and management?	Q34
	Our company discuss important information with employees often about any changes as a result of M&A	Q34
	Employees have experienced psychologically issues as a result of communication between management and employees.	Q36
	Have you been informed effectively and clearly about changes in your job role during M&A?	Q37
	The communication from company about merger is not efficient and as a result i am not satisfied and feeling insecure at work.	Q38
	Receiving regular information and communication with management helps improve emotions at work	Q39

6.3.1.5 Emotion and M&A process

Question 45,46,47,48,49,50,51,52 and 53 (9 items) are used to construct emotion communication index. The emotion index scale consisted of 5 points Likert scale approach at where “1” linked

stands to “strongly disagree” and “5” linked stands to the response “strongly agree”. The Cronbach Alfa value is 0.94.

Table 6.8 List of Questions included in Emotions

Factors	Questions	Abbreviation
Emotions	My supervisor/manager handles my emotional issues and support me to improve at work	Q44
	Do you trust the management to take this company out of difficult times?	Q46
	During the process of mergers and acquisitions at your company, how bothered were you emotionally	Q47
	such as feeling anxious, depressed, irritable, or sad?	
	Do you think emotions of employees affect their performance at work?	Q48
	I am concerned about my future and inadequate working conditions after M&A.	Q49
	Emotional distress at work force employees to search for the better options.	Q50
	Emotions in my perception is the most important factor of performance enhancement of the employees.	Q51
	During M&A, how do you feel about your emotional balance?	Q52
	During M&A, Better communication has a positive impact on emotions	Q53

6.3.1.6 Management Change and M&A process

Question 55,56,57,58,59,60,61 and 63 (8 items) are used to construct management change index. The management change index scale consisted of 5 points Likert scale approach at where “1” linked stands to “strongly disagree” and “5” linked stands to the response “strongly agree”. The Cronbach Alfa value is 0.86.

Table 6.9 List of Questions Included in Management Change

Factors	Questions	Abbreviation
Management Change	How did management listen to employees' opinions when making decisions about making changes in processes as a result of M&A?	Q54
	Employees believe that our company will achieve its target as a result of this M&A	Q56
	My company believes that people have a certain amount of talent, and they can't do much to change it	Q57
	My company believes that people can always greatly improve their talents and abilities to enable change in company.	Q58
	Involvement of employees in making changes will boost fairness, commitment, and trust	Q49

	Other stake holders such as customers, consultants, and labour unions should be considered in decision making which will increase the chances of smooth integration between both merging partners and change process	Q60
	Employees in my organisation willingly accept change	Q61
	Employees believe that the company will achieve its target as a result of this M&A	Q63

6.3.1.7 IT System and M&A process

Question 71,72,73,74,75,76,77,78 and 79 (9 items) are used to construct IT system index. The IT system index scale consisted of 2-degree points ordinal scale approach at where “1” linked stands to “Yes” and “2” linked stands to the response “No”. The Cronbach Alfa value is 0.93.

Table 6.10 List of Questions in IT Systems

Factors	Questions	Abbreviation
IT System	I believe that this M&A will enhance my skills and capabilities in future?	Q71
	Were the learning objectives clearly defined before and throughout the length of the training	Q72
	Did you learn everything that was laid out in the learning objectives of IT and systems?	Q73
	Did you feel that this training adds value / Did you learn something new? Will it boost your confidence artwork?	Q74
	Did you feel you had the time and resources to appropriately complete this training?	Q75
	Is the training relevant to your career growth? Will you use these learned skillsets?	Q76
	Training to employees about new IT and systems was?	Q77

6.3.2 Results of Regression Analysis

This study aims at to estimate the relationship between control variables such as culture, cultural diversity, compensation, communication, emotion, management change and IT system on M&A performance. This section covers two main results: First part explains descriptive statistics and correlation matrix results. Second part explains the impact of control variables on M&A performance. Table 6.11 provides the results of descriptive statistics that summaries information about mean, maximum, minimum, standard deviation and total respondents. The empirical

findings show that culture and management change are exhibiting more volatility as compared to other control variables. Overall, descriptive statistics results suggest that all the data is normally distributed. Henceforth normality assumptions have been satisfied which improved the reliability of empirical results.

Table 6.11 Results of Descriptive Analysis

Factors	Mean	Std. Deviation	Min Value	Max Value	N
M&A Index	0.374	0.369	0	0.98	147
Culture	0.365	0.328	0	0.97	147
Cultural Diversity	0.332	0.323	0	0.86	147
Compensation	0.303	0.295	0	0.81	147
Emotions	0.302	0.357	0	0.89	147
Management Change	0.331	0.391	0	0.91	147
IT System	0.268	0.331	0	0.84	147

Table 6.12 shows the correlation matrix which showing the magnitude of correlation between modelled variables. Each value of the correlation matrix table shows the correlation coefficient between two variables of given model. Correlation matrix results suggest that culture and cultural diversity had high correlation which show the strong bounding between them. Similarly, all the modelled variables are exhibiting the strong and moderate bounding among them. These findings can be used as key diagnostic yardstick for more advanced analysis such as regression analysis.

Table 6.13 presents the empirical results of simple linear regression model. This study used the culture, cultural diversity, compensation, emotions, management change and IT system as independent variable and M&A index as dependent variable in the model.

6.3.2.1 Results of Culture and M&As outcome

Regression analysis finding show that culture has positive influence on the progress and performance of M&A outcome. Coefficient value of culture indicates that if 1 percent change occur in organisational culture leads to 0.18 percent positive cause on the performance of M&A outcomes. These findings are aligned with the study of Teerikangas and Very, (2006). They

examined a critical question about how differences in culture have a short as well as long run impact on the performance of M&A. In this study, they reviewed a widely accepted myth about how culture effects negatively the performance of M&A. They explored the causes for this myth and contradictions and suggest some solutions. In the end, they come up with the findings that culture has long term dynamics on M&A performance either negative or positive. Another study of Hitt et al., (2012) has also been explored the dynamics of M&A. They found that acquiring firms only create little or no value. It is just because of the firm inability to make synergy, selecting inappropriate targets, paying high premium and ineffective process of integration. Furthermore, Nummela (2005) provided versatility of integration of international firms from cultural perspective, case study on national and organisational cultures explored by Santti (2001) and mergers and acquisitions failure due to close cultures analysed by Fang, Fridh, and Schultzberg (2004). Additionally, Schoenberg, (2004) and Slangen (2006) focused on national cultural differences whereas Weber et al. (1996) and Weber & Camerer (2003) focused on organisational cultural differences. Very, Lubatkin, Calori, & Veiga (1997) focused acculturation process, cultural integration (Kavanagh & Ashkanasy, 2006), and cultural learning (Schweiger & Goulet, 2005). Finally, Studies by Riad, (2005) and Vaara & Tienari, (2003) provided in depth analysis by exploring cognitive challenges and stereotyping contributed to cultural dimension. Hence the existing literature are supporting our empirical findings.

Table 6.12 Results of Correlation Matrix

Correlations Matrix								
		Culture	Cul_Diversity	Compensation	Communication	Emotions	Management Change	IT System
Culture	Pearson Correlation	1	.837**	.778**	.753**	.691**	.711**	.679**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		0	0	0.000	0	0	0
	N	147	147	147	147	147	147	147
Cul_Diversity	Pearson Correlation	.837**	1	.893**	.803**	.729**	.748**	.747**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0		0	0.000	0	0	0
	N	147	147	147	147	147	147	147
Compensation	Pearson Correlation	.778**	.893**	1	.779**	.740**	.747**	.763**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0	0	0	0.000	0	0	0
	N	147	147	147	147	147	147	147
Communication	Pearson Correlation	.753**	.803**	.779**	1	.891**	.899**	.873**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
	N	147	147	147	147	147	147	147
Emotions	Pearson Correlation	.691**	.729**	.740**	.891**	1	.956**	.937**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0	0	0	0.000		0	0
	N	147	147	147	147	147	147	147
Management Change	Pearson Correlation	.711**	.748**	.747**	.899**	.956**	1	.935**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0	0	0	0.000	0		0
	N	147	147	147	147	147	147	147
IT System	Pearson Correlation	.679**	.747**	.763**	.873**	.937**	.935**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0	0	0	0.000	0	0	
	N	147	147	147	147	147	147	147

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 6.12 Results of Correlation Matrix

6.3.2.2 Results of Cultural diversity and M&As outcome

Regression analysis also show that cultural diversity has positive impact on the performance of M&A outcome. It has statically significant influence on M&A process. Regression analysis suggests that if 1 percent change or increase occur in cultural diversity of any pre or post M&A firm will cause the 0.18 percent change or positively cause in the performance of M&A outcome. On the same way Drori et al., (2011) explored the equality and justices as a dynamic construct linked with two important processes in M&A such as cultural construction and cultural clash. The study used the qualitative approach to examine the impact of culture and equality on M&A process.

They suggest that cultural equality is a crucial factor for the success of post-merger integration. Another study of Fang et al, (2004) examined the merger of IT firm by reviewing various factors such as culture and joint venture. They found that feelings and emotions and historical sentiments, it not addressed properly can cause major damage to cross- cultural business mergers. On the same way the study of Dhillon et al., (2016) examined the formal security polices, technical infrastructure changes and normative cultural clashes on the performance of M&A. They found that the factor like change in security culture and normative clash can make the firm more vulnerable after M&A integration. Halsall, (2008) examined the discourse of controversies of two international firms after M&A. These M&A controversies were evolved due to diversity of culture among various firms. This study reviews how economic, culture and political discourses relating to global integration were used strategically. Similarly, Weber and Camerer, (2003) explored M&A failure due to cultural diversity. They found that performance of merged firms is largely affected due to conflicting culture.

6.3.2.3 Results of Compensation and M&As outcome

Regression analysis results show that compensation for the firm employees have positive influence on the progress and performance of M&A outcome. Coefficient value of emotion factor indicates that if 1 percent change occur in organisational compensation policy leads to 0.17 percent positive cause on the performance of M&A outcomes. Pre-acquisition compensation reduce fears and concerns in M&As (Tanure & Gonzalez- Duarte, 2007). In the post-acquisition phase, communication and compensation motivate employees by supporting positive attitudinal and

behavioural outcomes (Chaudhuri & Tabrizi, 1999) and commitment (Angwin, Mellahi, Gomes, & Peter, 2016).

6.3.2.4 Results of Emotions and M&As outcome

Regression analysis results show that emotions employees also have positive influence on the progress and performance of M&A outcome. Coefficient value of employee's emotion indicates that if 1 percent change occur in organisational employees' emotions leads to 0.22 percent positive cause on the performance of M&A outcomes. Research in socio-economic context suggests that members in under-developed countries trigger positive emotions as a result of M&As. Members of target firm from under-developed economies perceived development in personal skills and career (increased valance) because of acquiring firm from developed country (Paustian-Underdahl et al., 2017). Additionally, emotions are different based on gender; women show sadness as low-activation emotions as compared to men which show anger as high-activating emotions (Strongman, 1996) therefore, industries with skewed gender emotions distributions such as female dominated nursing or male-dominated investment banking reflect these differences. Finally, occupational emotions form as a part of professional identity (Salmela, 2014) where conflict can arise when employees feel disgruntled because of M&A situation while performing their duties. Therefore, observing the embeddedness of emotional dynamics may require comparative research designs across several carefully selected countries and industries (Sarala, Vaara and Junni, 2017). Positive emotions have positive effects on M&A process, for example, positive emotions can increase motivation (Kusstatscher & Cooper, 2005), job satisfaction and commitment of members with firm (Kusstatscher, 2006) however, negative emotions lead towards fear, anger and frustration which decrease organisational commitment (Mottola, Bachman, Gartner, & Dovidio, 1997) and withdrawal (Kiefer, 2005) which can affect negatively on merger process can affect merger process negatively (Giessner, Viki, Otten, Terry, & Täuber, 2006). As a result, shifting the focus from actual problems to less constructive activities of emotion coping mechanisms. (Scheck & Kinicki, 2000).

Table 6.13 Results of Regression Analysis

Model	Coefficients	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T Stat	Sig.	Lower Bound	Upper Bound
		B	S. E	Beta				

(Constant)	237	0	187	1.399	0.164	0	0
Culture	0.18	0	0.158	402778.5	0	0.177	0.177
Cul_Diversity	0.18	0	0.161	299997.8	0	0.184	0.184
Compensation	0.17	0	0.133	273504.9	0	0.166	0.166
Emotions	0.22	0	0.209	269377.2	0	0.216	0.216
Management Change	0.24	0	0.253	325548	0	0.239	0.239
IT System	0.20	0	0.179	270202.9	0	0.2	0.221
a. Dependent Variable: M&A Index							

Additionally, emotions determine social identifications such as positive emotions improve organisational identity and enhance the relationships among themselves and with other firms (Kusstatscher, 2006). A recent study of Tikkakoski et al., (2018) gave same insight about the complex relationship between emotions and pre and post M&A integration. In this study, they come up with view that M&A process is highly sensitive agreements. Due the involvement of strong emotion evoked. They conclude that misunderstanding about emotion may be the one of the core reasons of M&A failure. Another study of Hassetta et al., (2018) analysed the impact of post M&A situation on the top merger emotions and the factors and consequences which can trigger the emotions too. This study found that the event like M&A are very sensitive and emotional for key person and top managers. The study revealed that top managers experience a different range of positive and negative emotions triggered by M&A integrations. These positive and native emotions can influence the company performance in both in short as well as long term. In contrast, negative emotions harm organisational identity (Ford & Harding, 2003), trust (Kiefer, 2005), cooperation (Sinkovics, Zagelmeyer, & Kusstatscher, 2011) and lead to social conflict (Saunders, Altinay, & Riordan, 2009).

6.3.2.5 Results of Management of Change and M&As outcome

Regression analysis results show that surprisingly the management change has also positive influence on the progress and performance of M&A outcome. Coefficient value of management change factor indicates that if 1 percent change occur in organisational management leads to 0.24

percent positive cause on the performance of M&A outcomes. Top management at target firm can play mitigating role in alleviating members concerns, resolving conflicts and avoid disruptions by target firm's employees during integration process (Colman & Lunnan, 2011). Therefore, management from target firm can act as change agents for acquiring firm in identifying and providing solutions proactively (Colman & Lunnan, 2011). Middle management such as integration managers, HR managers and line managers also play important role as change managers in their capacity (Shi, Markoczy, & Dess, 2009; Teerikangas, Very, & Pisano, 2011; Antila & Kakkonen, 2006; Antila & Kakkonen, 2006) and act as active agents and interpret, mediate, and broker information (Shi et al., 2009). They also involve in devising strategy and implantation process (Balogun & Johnson, 2004; Balogun & Johnson, 2005; Mantere, 2005; Mantere, 2008; Rouleau & Balogun, 2011; Rouleau, 2005). Subsequently, a shift from a "top-down" management style towards "involvement and commitment." which made middle managers as recipient and change agents and transforming their position to enablers and empowerees (Caldwell, 2003). Furthermore, integration managers can influence value creation and value leakage (Teerikangas et al., 2011) whereas HR managers advise and mentor line managers with the integration process (Antila & Kakkonen, 2006) during integration process. Employees also act as change agents which are not acknowledged in literature of change agency (Caldwell, 2003). Finally, other stake holders such as customers, investment bankers, lawyers, consultants, and labour unions are very important in M&As and should be considered in decision making. For example, labour union became driving force and opposed by management of American Airlines during integration with US Airways (Reed, 2013). Future studies should examine the impact of other stakeholders on processes, practices, and integration success mergers rather than on financial returns provided by Bodnaruk, Massa, & Simonov (2009) and Servaes & Zenner (2015).

6.3.2.6 Results of IT system and M&As outcome

Similarly, IT system also have positive influence on the progress and performance of M&A outcome. Coefficient value of IT system indicates that if 1 percent change occur in organisational IT system leads to 0.20 percent positive cause on the performance of M&A outcomes. Our results are similar with Hsu and Chen, (2006). It highlighted that how information system decision making process made at firm level which enabled the various pathways for different firms to work together along with M&A processes. They come up with the conclusion that IS has significant role to

strengthen the working environment after the M&A. According to O'Brien, J A. (2003), IS defined as collection of systems which help to control the performance of business processes in logical way whereas IT consists of components which enables IS to function. The only difference is that IT generally does not include business logic. Hence Proctor, K. Scott (2011) mentioned IT as "the study, design, development, application, implementation, support or management of computer-based information systems" Proctor, K. Scott (2011). IT and IS will be used in combination as IT/IS as this study considered both aspects of IT and IS and it might cause confusion if used separately. IT/IS integration refers to the connection of internal business activities, processes, systems, and functions together (Henningsson, 2008).

6.3.3 Results of Residuals Statistics

Table 6.14 shows the results of Residuals Statistics. It suggests that this study is exhibiting the best fitted and unbiased results. This study is a pioneer research based on quantitative approach which examine the impact of culture, cultural diversity, compensation, emotion, management change and IT system on M&A performance.

Table 6.14 Results of Residuals Statistics

Residuals Statistics					
	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Predicted Value	1.607	1	0.374	0.369	147
Residual	-1.706	2.386	0	9.017	147
Std. Predicted Value	-1.014	1.697	0	1	147
Std. Residual	-1.856	2.583	0	0.979	147
a. Dependent Variable: M&A Index					

The empirical results of this study not only support the existing literature but also support the existing studies empirical findings. This study results suggest some important implications and understandings for upcoming studies.

Chapter 7 – Discussion and Conclusion

Chapter Overview

Chapter 6 outlined the analysis and findings of Phase Two of the study. This chapter provides the discussion, conclusion, contribution to the research, limitation and finally the directions for the future research. The chapter structure is outlined in Figure 7.1.

Figure 7.1 Organisational structure of the chapter 7

7.1 Discussion

This study focuses on research gap on the “human side or capital” of mergers and acquisitions (M&As) outcomes. This study argues that there is a need for more deep and fine-grained understanding of human side or human capital which demands practice-oriented processes and

conceptualizing M&As. This research presented some novel avenues research for human side of M&A and involved some new factors such as culture, cultural diversity, communication, compensation, emotions, management change and IT systems.

Researchers and academia increasingly highlight that strategic and financial avenue give an incomplete picture of success factors and failure factors in M&A analysis (Graebner et al., 2017; King et al., 2004). Although, a limited number of studies were available which focused on human capital aspect of M&As (Cooper and Tarba, 2016; Hajro, 2015; Stahl et al., 2013). Existing body of research just focuses on the role of social processes, HRM practices and culture in mergers and acquisitions (M&As) as an ultimate strategy (Sarala et al., 2016). Similarly, another inter-related storyline has emerged as cultural differences or diversity and their possible impact on performance of ant pre- or post-M&A organisation (Sarala et al., 2012; Shahl and Voigt, 2008). The existing studies also have a strong prescriptive component about the adaptation of management “tools” in mergers and acquisitions (M&As) such as trainings and HRM practices. As a whole, this study observes the significance of these past literature in highlighting attention to the standing of the “softer elements” of mergers and acquisitions (M&As), as contrast to considering M&As arrangements as mainly financial transactions.

This study aimed at to examine the central themes that highlights significant dynamics of human capital on M&As outcomes. Thus, this study used the mixed method approach, which offers a broad view that emphasises on what human capital do in M&A organisations while taking outlook of both within and outside the firm or organisational boundaries. We argue that mixed method approach can improve our understanding of the human capital side of M&As by highlighting the attention to those un or underexplored factors such as cultural diversity, emotions, communications, managerial change, and IT systems. In the following perspective, this study elaborates on the given factors as fruitful for the success and failure of M&As.

7.1.1. Discussion Pathway 1: Culture and Cultural Diversity dynamics in M&As

National identity is usually measured by involving the cultural measures (location of organisation, geographic location) in M&As analysis (Shimizu et al, 2004). But, due to increase the inter or intra mobility of labour force brings situation where the culture or national identities of the hired labour force of the organisation are quite diverse (e.g., Stahl, Mendenhall, & Weber, 2005; Shimizu et

al., 2004). We know that a large number of workforces have multi-layered national and local culture such as Indian diaspora in across the globe with “bicultural identities” (Sarala et al. 2019; Kane and Levina, 2017; Chand and Tung, 2014; Stahl and Voight, 2008). Cultural research on mergers and acquisitions extended to identity and culture (Zaheer et al., 2003), employees understanding on integration process (Risberg, 2001), linking culture with knowledge transfer (Hasegawa, 2000) and with value creation (Blasko, Netter, and Sinkey, 2000). Another study of Napier, Schweiger, and Kosglow (1993) focused on research managing cultural diversity and its importance in foreign acquisitions and Olie (1994) (2005) concluded in case studies that different national cultures increased integration problems. Furthermore, Nummela (2005) provided versatility of integration of international firms from cultural perspective, case study on national and organisational cultures explored by Santti (2001) and mergers and acquisitions failure due to close cultures analysed by Fang, Fridh, and Schultzberg (2004). Mosaic culture framework which is given by (Zolfaghari et al., 2016) shows that workforce having diverse culture can be asset because they substitute effectively between cultural characteristics, depending on the social sitting. Thus, culture dimension has historic path dependencies. Recent experience of various countries, especially those countries that reflect prior dependencies, may describe why cultural diversity is challenging for the success of M&As. If the acquirer organisation is from a historically dominant nation, discourses associated to colonialism and imperialism are more probable to appear in the target. In contrast, if the acquirer organisation is from a conventionally submissive nation narratives in target explode uncertainties that a nation is being taken over (Schoenberg, 2006; Teerikangas & Very, 2006). The role of media is also very important in proliferate of culture in M&As (Tienari et al., 2003; Risberg et al., 2003; Riad and Vaara, 2011). Otherwise, media can weaken the culture through national narratives and that emphasizes dimensions like economic integration and globalization for M&As (Vaara and Tienari, 2002; Brock, 2005; Cartwright & Price, 2003). However, the existing studies have largely overlooked that cultural diversity with pre-M&A process can have significant and positive contribution. This study also supporting this argument that culture and culture diversity both have a significant impact on M&A outcomes. Both qualitative and quantitative findings suggest that culture dimension can provide an opportunity to re-understand the relationship with organisation during pre- and post-M&A integration process. It can develop new terms which directly and indirectly support the organisational business environment. In the end, we come up with conclusion that culture, and cultural diversity dimension

involve a complex interrelation and their interlink with the employee's personal shaping the professional life of employees therefore, cultural fit is the most important factor in the assessment of merger deal. It poses both opportunities and challenges during integration process and ultimately can effectively cause success or failure to the outcome of M&As deal between the two organisations.

7.1.2. Discussion Pathway 2: Emotional processes dynamics in M&As

Existing studies of M&As have evolved for attention to emotions dimension (Graebner et al., 2017). Emotions of the organisational members are influenced by cultural and social processes. It is therefore supported or hindered with various strategic intents (Brundin and Liu, 2015). Existing literature on emotions dimension along with M&As, it is very limited as compare to overall research on human capital in M&As process. A study of Graebner et al., (2017) called for attention to emotions in M&A studies. Influence of emotions are characterized by the effects of socio-cultural processes and therefore can support or cause failure to M&A process (Brundin & Liu, 2015). Emotions determines the attitudes and behaviours of members in the process of M&As. Positive emotions have positive effects on M&A process, for example, positive emotions can increase motivation (Kusstatscher & Cooper, 2005), job satisfaction and commitment of members with firm (Kusstatscher, 2006) however, negative emotions lead towards fear, anger and frustration which decrease organisational commitment (Mottola, Bachman, Gartner, & Dovidio, 1997) and withdrawal (Kiefer, 2005) which can affect negatively on merger process can affect merger process negatively (Giessner, Viki, Otten, Terry, & Täuber, 2006). Emotions are really an important factor of employee behaviours and attitudes in M&As. We found that positive emotions, better communications, job satisfaction can boost employee energy to do work, job satisfaction and motivation as well. On the other side, negative emotions may have adverse dynamics. For instance, the frustration, anger and worry adversely affect the employee performance (Giessner et al., 2006). Thus, this study found that emotions were an important socio-cultural mechanism which usually determine employee's satisfaction and actions through behaviours and attitude. Although, existing literature on emotions have been typically associated with positive attitude or behaviour with positive M&A outcomes and vice versa. Furthermore, the relationship between individual emotions (field of psychology) and collective emotions and emotional capabilities (cognitive and sociological process) requires further research in M&A literature (Sarala, Vaara and Junni, 2017).

Furthermore, managing emotions in M&A depend on the contextual factors such in cultural context, social beliefs system prevents individual from adding different meaning to their predefined activities and roles (Golsorkhi, Rouleau, Seidl, & Vaara, 2015; Lounsbury & Crumley, 2007). For example, in study of merger of banks in Brunei by Clarke and Salleh (2011), the emotions of manager influence M&A guided by their beliefs that they must endure the acquisition patiently and show gratitude. Similarly, emotional attending (ability to consider and care for emotions) can be different based on cultural context. Reus (2012) experienced reduced emotional attending in different international cultures conducted by US acquirers. Also, expression of emotions also differs in different cultural settings and affects the member of firms accordingly. Countries likely to expect suppression of emotions where status and power culture exist (Matsumoto, Yoo, & Nakagawa, 2008). However, US firms adjusted their emotional attending according to the cultural context such as increased level of emotional attending in high level of people-oriented culture (Reus, 2012). Research in socio-economic context suggests that members in under-developed countries trigger positive emotions as a result of M&As. Members of target firm from under-developed economies perceived development in personal skills and career (increased valance) because of acquiring firm from developed country (Paustian-Underdahl et al., 2017). This study suggest that the emotions of employees play a major role in the success or failure of mergers and emotions of employees are inter linked with the personal background, culture, professional backgrounds, and other areas which have effects on employees' emotions such as communications, compensation, and satisfaction with the job at work. Therefore, employees' emotional levels must be assessed during the process of mergers and acquisitions as it can cause challenges if employees feel negative or less optimistic about the merger outcome and ultimately can cause high employee turnover and risk of merging firms loosing key employees during integration process. As a result, this can effectively cause failure to the outcome of M&As deal.

7.1.3. Discussion Pathway 3: Management of Change dynamics in M&As

The management change dynamics emphasizes a broad prospective and definition of organisational actors who participate to planning and decision making like top or middle management. While the existing research typically conceptualize M&As process as top-down actions of the management. It is factual that during the pre-M&A stage, planning and decision making are often very limit to small group of employees due to confidential requirement. But the

post M&A process is entirely different due to it demands a broad-spectrum participation and engagement (Jarzabkowski and Wolf, 2015). Therefore, management from target firm can act as change agents for acquiring firm in identifying and providing solutions proactively (Colman & Lunnan, 2011). Middle management such as integration managers, HR managers and line managers also play important role as change managers in their capacity (Shi, Markoczy, & Dess, 2009; Teerikangas, Very, & Pisano, 2011; Antila & Kakkonen, 2006; Antila & Kakkonen, 2006) and act as active agents and interpret, mediate, and broker information (Shi et al., 2009). They also involve in devising strategy and implantation process (Balogun & Johnson, 2004; Balogun & Johnson, 2005; Mantere, 2005; Mantere, 2008; Rouleau & Balogun, 2011; Rouleau, 2005). Subsequently, a shift from a “top-down” management style towards “involvement and commitment.” which made middle managers as recipient and change agents and transforming their position to enablers and empowerees (Caldwell, 2003). Furthermore, integration managers can influence value creation and value leakage (Teerikangas et al., 2011) whereas HR managers advise and mentor line managers with the integration process (Antila & Kakkonen, 2006) during integration process. Employees also act as change agents which are not acknowledged in literature of change agency (Caldwell, 2003). A study of Gill, (2012) considered the combined and relative impact of management change and organisational culture on the performance of M&A. It also observed the causes of success and failure factors of M&A process. The existing literature suggests that organisation leadership and top management are the significant factors for achieving the success of M&A. The prime intention behind these studies was to understand the cultural disparity and leadership role in cultural alinement under the M&A integration. We also found that management change and leadership played a significant role for attaining the success of M&A agreements, epically post M&A integration process. King et al., (2004) employed the meta-analytic approach to statistically estimate the effect of various factors on post M&A performance. This study found the robust findings which indicating that not only most common factors have any significant difference in pre- and post-M&A integration. But also, on the other side the non-common factor like leadership and management skills have positive and significant impact on the performance of M&A. This study also suggests that the involvement of stakeholders including employees can smoothen the process of change management in the company in fact employees can act as change agent when a bottom-up approach is taken in decision making during the integration process of M&A. However, compensation, job security, power struggle, emotions such

as stress and anxiety unrealistic expectations and finally reduced cooperation by management can affect the process of change during M&A integration and ultimately it can cause failure to the M&As deal.

7.1.4. Discussion Pathway 4: HRM practices in M&As

Existing studies in M&As emphasizes the role of socio-material factors, that usually deals with moderating or mediating roles of material technologies and artefacts (Balohum et al, 2014). HRM help in assessing compensation differences between merging firms, manage retention agreements and ensure legal compliance in relation to equal opportunity and collective bargaining agreements (Mirvis and Marks, 1992). Similarly, emphasizing on socio-material factors such HRM tools and practices, are also important these aspects play a significant role on the integration process of the organisation. Various research studies have recognized HRM tools and practices which can directly or indirectly facilitate M&A process. During the pre-M&A stage, examining the target organisations culture, key employees and capabilities can be useful in developing M&A integrations plan (Harding and Rouse, 2007; Chaudhuri, 2005). Although some failures can be observed as market and financial factors, a large number can be found to neglect HR activities and issues. This study stressed upon the need for organisations to comprehensively address the HR activities and issues in M&A process. Chang-Howe, (2019) purposed the perspective approach for post M&A integration process along with the special focus on HR integration. This study used the qualitative approach by using the systematic review approach. This study suggests that HR integration is as much as important the M&A integration for increasing the performance of employees and reduce the turnover so that M&A between the organisations can be successful. This study suggests that human factors involved in HRM effects and influence the performance of post M&A integration success. Thus, job security, employees emotional and cultural issues, training and development during post M&A integration is important to address the challenges of new market. Another study of Weber and Drori, (2011) presented a conceptual framework for examining the M&A performance through multilevel and multistage approach. The first HR challenge during M&A integration process is deal with to help describe the inconsistencies between empirical findings and effects of cultural diversity on M&A performance. This study proposed that the factors like organisational identification, culture clash, communication, dealing

with the training, job satisfaction and emotions of employees, and finally management attitude are the critical factors for determining the success of M&A integration of two firms.

7.1.5. Discussion Pathway 5: New forms of compensation and communication in M&As

Employee's compensation and communication are most valuable HR tools in M&As integration. Pre-M&A effective communication can persuasively transform and convey the key plans and integration goals can be helpful to alleviate concerns and fear about M&As (Tanure and Gonzalez Duarte, 2007). During the post M&A stage, compensation, and communication both continue to play a significant role through supporting behavioural and attitudinal outcomes like motivation and job commitment (Angwin et al., 2005). These two factors also contribute to cultural and cultural diversity outcomes such as integration of culture, trust building and knowledge transfer (Stahl et al., 2011; Melkonian et al., 2011). In the post-acquisition phase, communication motivate employees by supporting positive attitudinal and behavioural outcomes (Chaudhuri & Tabrizi, 1999) and commitment (Angwin, Mellahi, Gomes, & Peter, 2016). Communication processes can be manipulated based on someone interests, background, experience, and attitudes when sending or taking information by deliberately or subconsciously using filters. Communication improves the perceptions of fairness as well as procedural and interactional justice among employees (Lotz & Donald, 2006) and acceptance for change thus, better commitment from employees (Klendauer and Deller, 2009). Relevant communication can manage employees' expectations which can interpret their psychological contract with firm (Hubbard and Purcell, 2001). Another study of Vaara and Monin (2010) focus on leadership aspects of communication for discursive legitimization of an M&A which can be used to yield particular behaviours from employees to support the process of cultural integration and development (Soderberg, 2012). Communication also contributes to socio-cultural outcomes such as cultural integration (Evans et al., 2011) and trust-building (Stahl, Larsson, Kremershof & Sitkin, 2011) and supports strategic outcomes such as knowledge transfer (Ranft & Lord, 2002) and merger survival (Angwin et al., 2016). The empirical results of this study suggest that the process of new communication develop slowly and was not completely enduring even when a transformative process such as M&A occurs. Both formal and informal communication is important for the success of M&A integration. Both executive retention and communication have a positive impact on M&A performance, whereas

organisational employee stress has adverse impact on M&A performance. This study also studied whether the communication integration had any impact on M&A performance. This study suggests that the link between performance and employee stress was not moderated by communication integration.

7.1.6. Discussion Pathway 5: IT system dynamics in M&As

IT system is an under-researched but significant area is the study of how IT system communication effects actors and business practices. Mainly the importance of new media revaluation such as social media demands to be further studied in M&As integration (Proctor, K. Scott ,2011; Henningson, 2008). IT system can involve the use of emails, mobile text, video conference and GPS induced picture and location (Jue et al., 2010; O'Brien, J A. 2003). We found that IT system can speed up the integration process of M&As through connecting employees. Similarly, Hsu and Chen, (2006) highlighted that how information system decision making process made at firm level which enabled the various pathways for different firms to work together along with M&A processes. They come up with the conclusion that IS has significant role to strength the working environment after the M&A. Another study of Alaranta, (2005) examined the importance of IS for M&A. They presented the four broad categories of success issues for M&A and IS integration. The empirical results proposed integrated software system, effective and efficient IS integration management, information quality and IS efficient staff integration are important factors the success of M&A process (Sarrazin, H. & West, A. 2011). Bhattacharya et al., (2010) reported and explored the IS potential to enable business transformations for achieving the success of merger. Finally, this study suggests that IS/IT integration is important for achieving the success of M&A. It should involve appropriate training about new systems, constant monitoring, and feedback from the employees about training should be taken in order to smoothen the process of integrating of IT/IS of both M&A firms. It should also be noted that the training provided must be aligned with their career and personal goals of employees so that the employees feel motivated to complete the training. These factors are also helpful to retain the skilled employees at the company as these employees are valuable assets of company which increases the IS capabilities of the firms. In the long run, if a firm with high level of IS capabilities attain massively higher abnormal operation performance as well as they are also helpful to create higher value for the firm before and after the M&A integrations. These IT emerging phenomena's directly challenge various traditional aspects

and assumptions in M&As process, involving those about the role of integration of culture and raise many new but interesting questions for research. For example, if any employee is used to working along with international team, will that weaken his culture and national identity and thereby reduced the role of cultural diversity in M&As? In the end, this study suggests that future research should examine that what kind of IT tools and practices are useful for managing the M&As integration who are physically or geographical dispersed from the office?

7.2 Conclusion

This study addresses the existing research gap in M&A analysis underlying the Mixed Method approach and observed the outcomes of M&A by involving both qualitative and quantitative aspects. In phase 1 (qualitative analysis), this study used systematic review approach by adopting the meta-analysis approach of M&A studies related research. The systematic review provided “deep insights through literature synthesis into fields and allied fields. The findings of systematic review are claimed to be rationalized, unbiased, rigorous, and transparent. This study used standard systematic review guidelines of Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis (PRISMA) to improve the reporting quality of M&A studies.

The main objective of meta-analysis is to make novel understandings from synthesis and comparison of results of various studies. This approach involves a detailed online search of qualitative research on M&A allowing us to extend beyond the primary or original scope of M&A qualitative studies by explaining analogies between the analytical themes following different keywords. This meta-synthesis included studies that analyse the research question “how do mergers and acquisitions policies effect the quality of human such as IT/IS integration, employee satisfaction, training, HRM, communication, emotion, culture and leadership within an organisation”. The research papers were included if they fulfil the following eligibility criteria (1) the selected studies had to be focused only on merger and acquisitions (2) the identified studies estimated the empirical physiognomies i.e., M&A impacts on human capital; (3) the articles were written in English. The selected M&A research was briefly examined and scanned by the author with respect to dataset, measurement technique, empirical findings, and endogenous and exogenous factors. The meta-synthesis focused on research gap on the “human side or capital” of mergers and acquisitions (M&As) outcomes. This study argued that there is a need for more deep and fine-grained understanding of human side or human capital which demands practice-oriented

processes and conceptualizing M&As. This research presented some novel avenues research for human side of M&A and involved some new factors such as culture, cultural diversity, communication, compensation, emotions, management change and IT systems. Existing body of research just focused on the role of social processes, HRM practices and culture in mergers and acquisitions (M&As) as an ultimate strategy. Similarly, another inter-related storyline has emerged as cultural differences or diversity and their possible impact on performance of pre- or post-M&A integration. The existing studies also had a strong prescriptive component about the adaptation of management “tools” in mergers and acquisitions (M&As) such as trainings and HRM practices. As a whole, this study observed the significance of these past literature in highlighting attention to the standing of the “softer elements” of mergers and acquisitions (M&As), as contrast to considering M&As arrangements as mainly financial transactions. We found that mixed method approach can improve our understanding of the human capital side of M&As by highlighting the attention to those underexplored factors such as cultural diversity, emotions, communications, managerial change, and IT systems. In the following perspective, this study elaborates on the given factors as fruitful for the success and failure of M&As.

In phase 2 (quantitative analysis), the second prime objective of this study was to build a numerical index series of merger and acquisition named as M&A index. For the following purpose, this study involved six key factor or dimensions which directly or indirectly influence the performance of M&A process. Results of PCA analysis unveil noteworthy information about M&A index. mean value of M&A index series was 0.37. The Max value of M&A index series was 0.98, Min value was zero and SD value was 0.36. M&A analysis normally require monitoring and analysis of various empirical parameters at the same time. This research showcases a significant variation in M&A analysis, i.e., indicators section and it employs the highly advance empirical method-Principal Component Analysis (PCA) for this investigation. The mean value of culture index series was 0.36. The Max value of culture index series was 0.97, Min value was zero and SD value was 0.32. The mean value of cultural diversity index series was 0.33. The Max value of cultural diversity index series was 0.86, Min value was zero and SD value was 0.32. Quantitative analysis normally requires monitoring and analysis of various empirical parameters at the same time. This study found a significant variation in cultural diversity among firms during post-merger integration process. The mean value of compensation index series was 0.30. The Max value of compensation index series was 0.81, Min value was zero and SD value was 0.29. The mean value of emotion

index series was 0.30 The Max value of emotion index series was 0.89, Min value was zero and SD value was 0.35. The mean value of management change series was 0.30 The Max value of management change index series was 0.89, Min value was zero and SD value was 0.35. This empirical analysis found a significant impact of management change on the performance of any firm during post-merger and acquisition outcome. The mean value of IT system index series was 0.26 The Max value of IT system index series was 0.84, Min value was zero and SD value was 0.31. Quantitative analysis normally requires monitoring and analysis of various empirical parameters at the same time. This study found a significant impact of IT system on post-merger and acquisition process and outcome of any firm. The following information is helpful to stabilize the employment sector through creating the new opportunities for jobs and create positive economic activities for the economy.

Finally, this study estimated the relationship between control variables such as culture, cultural diversity, compensation, communication, emotion, management change and IT system on M&A performance. The empirical findings showed that culture and management change are exhibiting more volatility as compare to other control variables. Overall, descriptive statistics results suggested that all the data is normally distributed. Henceforth normality assumptions have been satisfied which improved the reliability of empirical results. Correlation matrix results suggest that culture and cultural diversity had high correlation which show the strong bounding between them. Similarly, all the modelled variables are exhibiting the strong and moderate bounding among them. These findings can be used as key diagnostic yardstick for more advanced analysis such as regression analysis.

Regression analysis finding showed that culture has positive influence on the progress and performance of M&A outcome. This study examined a critical question about how differences in culture have a short as well as long run impact on the performance of M&A. We provided in depth analysis by exploring cognitive challenges and stereotyping contributed to cultural dimension. Similarly, the cultural diversity has also positive impact on the performance of M&A outcome. It has statically significant influence on M&A process. We found that performance of merged firms is largely affected due to conflicting culture.

Regression analysis results show that compensation for the firm employees have positive influence on the progress and performance of M&A outcome. Likewise, emotions employees also have

positive influence on the progress and performance of M&A outcome. Positive emotions have positive effects on M&A process, for example, positive emotions can increase motivation, job satisfaction and commitment of members with firm however, negative emotions lead towards fear, anger and frustration which decrease organisational commitment and withdrawal which can affect negatively on merger process can affect merger process negatively. In this study, it is viewed that post-M&A integration process is highly sensitive agreements. Due to the involvement of strong emotion evoked. It is also concluded that misunderstanding about the partner and negative emotions may be the core reasons of M&A failure. The study revealed that top managers experience a different range of positive and negative emotions triggered by M&A integrations. These positive and native emotions can influence the company performance in both in short as well as long term. In contrast, negative emotions harm organisational identity, cooperation, and lead to social conflicts.

Surprisingly, the management change has also positive influence on the progress and performance of M&A outcome. This could be because the top management at target firm can play mitigating role in alleviating members concerns, resolving conflicts and avoid disruptions by target firm's employees during integration process. Therefore, management from target firm can act as change agents for acquiring firm in identifying and providing solutions proactively. Middle management such as integration managers, HR managers and line managers also play important role as change managers in their capacity and act as active agents and interpret, mediate, and broker information. They should be involved in devising strategy of M&A integration process. Similarly, IT system also have positive influence on the progress and performance of M&A outcome. Our results are similar with existing studies. They highlighted that how information system decision making process made at firm level which enabled the various pathways for different firms to work together along with M&A processes. They come up with the conclusion that IS has significant role to strength the working environment after the M&A. In the end, residuals statistics. It suggests that this study is exhibiting the best fitted and unbiased results. This study is a pioneer research based on quantitative approach which examine the impact of culture, cultural diversity, compensation, emotion, management change and IT system on M&A performance. The empirical results of this study not only support the existing literature but also support the existing studies empirical findings. This study results suggest some important implications and understandings for upcoming studies.

7.3 Contributions of research

7.3.1 Academic Contribution

Our study has made following academic contributions to the literature of M&A.

- The debate to examine the role of M&A integration process started in early 1990s across the world and progress and performance was measured normally on pre- and post-M&A level. In some studies, the causes of M&A process are measured through the profitability dimension. But, to the best of my knowledge, no one has examined the role of human side partial as well as combined factors such as culture, cultural diversity, compensation, communication, emotions, management of change and IT systems on the M&A outcomes. There is evidence for call for multi-layered conceptualizations and identity roles in M&As (Sarala, R., Vaara, E. and Junni, P. 2019). This research provides both qualitative and quantitative evidence, which suggests how interdisciplinary factors affecting the performance of humans and how human behave differently in pre- and post-M&A process due to various factors affecting such as culture, leadership, emotions, communications, and emotions.
- This study also includes the emotions dynamics embedded in culture, communications, management of change and job satisfactions across various industries and countries using mix methodology approach underexplored area (Sarala, R., Vaara, E. and Junni, P. 2019).
- This study examined the culture and related human factors and their effects of the success and failure of integration process and M&A field across various industries all over the world. There is evidence for call for multi-disciplinary across various industries in international context in the field of M&As (Stahl et al., 2013).
- The novelty of this research can also be confirmed because none of existing studies considers all these factors joint by employing the mixed method approach inculcating meta-synthesis and PCA analysis.
- The role of other stakeholders and their effects on M&A (Maxon, 2014). This research also included the feedback of other stakeholder such as previous employees who left or lost their jobs because deal was unsuccessful between the merging firms and consultants and

contractors (M&A integration consultants) hired by merging firms to do the tasks in relation to the integration between the organisations.

- This study used largely putative theoretical and empirical understanding of M&A concept to review existing literature for meta synthesis the way in which M&A process is measured and identified the past and recent research priorities and gaps in M&A research. This study also examined the usefulness of various factors/dimensions for the success or failure of M&A integration and suggested possible adjustments to improve the outcome of M&A.
- In the field of HRM, its practices across industries and countries, its influence the flexibility and practices in M&As (Sarala et al., 2016). This research provides a theory-driven and comprehensive understanding of how various HRM practices can be applicable and how employees react and how HRM tools can be used to positively affect the M&A integration outcome.
- There was a huge research examining various factors in relation to M&A. Thus, the real problem was, therefore, not the absence of applied research on this area but rather, that available studies was scattered and single dimensional in focus. This study used a mixed method approach to study the complex and multifaceted nature of M&A process. To our best knowledge, this study was pioneer research to use a mixed method approach by involving both qualitative and qualitative prospective to explore the sustainable approach for M&A integration outcomes.
- The available research on M&A was narrow in its scope due to one or two factors. Thus, existing body of studies have not examined the role of multi factors on M&A outcome in sum. Therefore, the drawback is not availability of first-hand research on this issue but rather, the available studies are single dimensional in nature. In order to fill this gap, this research study employs the multidimensional approach by including the role of all the relevant factors together on the performance of M&A. It is marginal contribution in the existing literature of M&A.
- This research estimated all the novel paths to understand the dynamics of M&A integration. The beauty of this research was decomposing the role of various aspects such as culture, cultural diversity, compensation, communication, emotions, management change and IT systems on the performance of M&A. It explored the complex role of emotions and management change factors by swapping the focus of policy makers and scholars from

culture and compensation to some other significant factors. The empirical findings of this research opened up various new research dimensions and themes on M&A agreements.

- The research in the field of M&A involving social structure and culture such as processes, including social construction, affect participation (Shi et al., 2009), power differences and employee participation (Cartwright & Cooper, 1995) and participation of different actors within the merging organisation (Laine & Vaara, 2015; Mantere & Vaara, 2008) called for the comprehensive research including all socio-cultural factors affecting M&A integration process.
- Researchers also called for the research about resistance in M&As, its dynamics and management during the change process and how employees act as change agents (Chapman, Chua, & Mahama, 2015; Long, 2001). Circumstances under which employee cause hurdles or problems in the change process its rational and interrelationship among the factors affecting M&As (Long, 2001).

7.3.2 Practical Implications

The key implications are based on findings of mixed method approach. Particulars of policy implications are given bellow:

- Mixed method approach findings suggest that there are two possible implications of cultural and cultural diversity dimension in M&As outcomes. First, both qualitative and quantitative analysis suggests that culture and its diversity provide a pathway to change the practice and meaning of equality in pre- and post-M&A integration. It entailed reinforcing, appropriating, abandoning, and inventing norms and practices that ultimately facilitate a change from stated distributive equality to consolidative equality. Merging firms should negotiate and rebuild the model of what the future culture will look like consolidating if appropriate all the human factors related to the culture of both integrating firms in the process of pre- and post-M&A integration process. Similarly, culture works as a prime mechanism for developing an organisational identity. This organisational identity motivates the employee's commitment to sacrifice and change so that new M&A organisation has got potential to survive in the market. Second, empirical findings suggest that culture have the major implications on the employees which can affect the plan of actions during post-M&A integrations. If culture if both firms is too rigid and there is no

or less culture fit between the merging firms, it can badly affect the integration process and cause M&A failure. So therefore, management must understand the cultural mechanism of potential merging partners and investigate if there is cultural fit (integrated, differentiated, or fragmented) between the firms to avoid issue such as acculturative stress for employee.

- Mixed method approach suggests that any changes can occur during the process of integration of M&A, therefore, proactive actions suggested in this study to consider the human factors, must be taken to avoid the level of uncertainty which can cause stress and badly affects the performance of M&A. This study suggests that efficient communication process, dealing with employee's emotions and management support can reduce the uncertainty and stress issues of the employees which can positively affect the integration process and can cause M&A success. Poor planning, or actions taken at the time of integration or when the problem arises cannot guarantee controlling the situation as various inter-related and complex factors involved during the M&A integration process. In order to control this type of situation, financial institutions and companies in IT sector must follow and adopt proactive approach and devise policy measure to control this type of issue in advance as suggested in the framework.
- Time to communicate with employees about the merger is very important factor. Most of M&A involve complications and required confidentiality so therefore, it should be assessed how the information is going to affect the employees and what is the nature of the processes are in place for communications. Releasing any confidential information to employees about the M&A deal can affect employees and deal negatively. Normally the deal is communicated to employees after it has been signed which can take time and cause uncertainty. It can sometime delayed depend upon the due diligence process of merging partners. However, when the deal is done, employees should be communicated immediately and throughout the entire process.
- The M&A deals are very secretive, only a few people know, in the beginning, on both sides of the deal. There is a preliminary time when both agree (depending on the deal, merger of equals, hostile, etc) to allow the acquiring company to look at all the targets data which includes every contract, liability, financial, patents etc. Directors of each side are abundant in most M&A deals that is why certain persons need to know early. Therefore, communication must be handled very carefully following M&A deal.

- Sometimes deals can fall apart as a result of disclosing information. Management should also have the risk assessment in place. In case the deal fell apart or not completed, management should assess the costs of failed M&A deal which could be a percentage of the total deal. Most of the time if deal fails, employees affected the most and there must be a plan in place to protect the employees.
- This study findings suggests that there is dire need to develop an advance tools of job cognitions, job evaluation, job affect to understand the technical relationship of these clearly observe and commonly used indicators of job satisfaction during post-M&A integration process. These human factors can enhance the understanding for employers of mechanisms by which job factors directly or indirectly influence employees' emotions, attitudes, stress, health, and work quality. This will then be able to help management to change the policy and take appropriate actions before it can badly affect the M&A integration process.
- The findings of the study support the theory of M&A being emotionally sensitive for employees, both negative and positive emotions directly reflect their impact on M&As outcomes. Thus, it is suggested that a constant feedback from the employees and receiving their input should be considered to understand the nature of "soft factors" which should be addressed carefully during the M&A integration process.
- This study suggest that the executives must converse with as many employees at every level to understand the heartbeat of the employees. Sometimes employees can expose themselves to the management while showing the emotions. The most important factor this study suggests dealing with the emotional issues is creating a team culture, recommending interdisciplinary and interprofessional teams are important. Separately as a singular team they can provide continuity to the company. Teams follow a pattern, forming, storming, norming, and performing. Usually at the end of a project a team will be doing their best work for the merger. Teams individually can perform better and deal with the emotional issues with the team which can positively affect M&A integration.
- This study has suggested some implications for management of change. We observed that different people are likely to adopt or experience the impact of change as a result of M&A integration differently and it became the caused to develops the different emotional experience for them. For others, compensation and power struggle has become a worrying

factor during change as a result of M&A integration process. Hence, management should communicate openly about the management change process openly and constantly update the employees about the benefits of the M&As with the new firms to motivate them and so that employees can perform better which can cause success of M&A integration.

- This study also suggests that management should also consider the views of other stakeholders including customers, consultants, and labour unions in relation to the proposed merger of both firms. This will allow management to input an outside perspective which can be important in decision making process which can help management in dealing with the issues in relation to the other stakeholders proactively. This will also increase the chances the smooth integration between both merging partners and management of change process.
- This study also suggest that the management should perform the due diligence at pre-M&A stage about the target firm to assess the IT/IS systems. This will allow the merging or acquiring firm to better understand the targets, systems, applications, the technology, and the processes. Based on this information management can decided whether firms have the capacity and resources (needs training to develop or understand the target firm's systems) to involve in M&A with the target firm or whether it can acquire/merger with the target firm system, or it needs completely new and integrated system to add any value after M&A integration.
- Management must consider if IT and systems' goals are fully aligned with the strategic goals of merging firms as IT systems are the backbone of any merging firms. Having appropriate resources and planning in place so that the new or integrated systems after M&A integrations are achieving the goals in providing and enabling services to the final customers. Failure to integrate both merging firms IT/IS will cause integration problems which can fail the M&A integration process.

7.4 Research Limitations

As with any study, this research has limitations which must be considered when interpreting the results. This research is based on mixed method approach both qualitative approach and

quantitative approach. So, it is appropriate to separate the study limitations into qualitative limitations and quantitative limitations. Both limitations are presented below:

7.4.1 Qualitative part limitation

- Data limitation is first limitation of meta synthesis as not all available literature is covered. Due to time limitation, there was simply not able to cover all the available resources.
- Second data limitation is that all relevant research articles are selected on the base of level of generalizability, not distinction is made whether it concerned with large, medium, or small firm.
- Third limitation of qualitative part is lack of available data. Unfortunately, no scientific database about M&A is available yet.
- Fourth limitation is about self-reporting data. As emotions and communication factor data is grouped into categories by the researcher, this considered as self-reporting data.
- Conceptual Framework developed in the study is not tested on any particular case of integration of M&A.

7.4.2 Quantitative part limitations

- First limitation of study is time constraints. The time available to examine the research question is constraint by due date of research submission.
- Second limitation is about data constraints. Unfortunately, no secondary database is available yet about M&As.
- Usually during the survey, some employees were reluctant to give information due to privacy concerns.
- Like the above, no employee was willing to give interviews due to confidentiality issues in relation to the M&A deal.
- Most of employees left or lost their jobs as a result of unsuccessful M&A deal, therefore, very few respondents found who were willing to participate.

- Although study aimed to collect data across several industries and countries however, most of the respondents are from UK and USA and from financial and IT and Telecommunication sectors.
- The study collected cross sectional data in post-M&A period as opposed to observation of actual behaviour or time series data which could involve interviews in pre- and post-M&A period which could extend the analysis and be able to identify this anomaly if individuals' perceptions do not match their behaviour.

7.5 Directions for Future Research

- The study suggests that upcoming research should explore the valuable and fruitful perspective of HRM dimension that the area of M&A studies has to enrich and offer further important insights into process. M&A process is good opportunity to account and study for the steps of M&A integration taken within this conceptual framework. Similarly, the applied research on post M&A process is also required to observe the factors and indicators which determine ultimate success of a M&A process. Hence, such type of research will have a continuous and significant impact on business world and academic community as well.
- Number of respondents across different countries compare to UK and USA are very small therefore in future studies, increased size of sample size across many countries can bring more insight from other countries. Similarly, most respondents are from financial and telecommunication and IT sectors. Having more respondents from different sectors can bring more insight in M&A field.
- This study opens various avenues for further research. Mixed method approach findings suggest that communication and compensation approaches in M&A process, and upcoming research could explore the reasons why various compensation and communication processes and tools are deployed. This research also identified the various outcomes of different dimensions such as culture, cultural diversity, communication, compensation, emotions, management change and IT systems and further research could understand the efficiency and usefulness of these dimensions for M&A outcomes.
- Although, data limitations are a real issue in M&A research, however, this research findings suggest that much work still needs to be done to examine these complex

relationships at different firm levels such as large vs small, large vs medium or both. Similarly, a proper research on M&A in SME's can be new particle contribution in the literature of M&A.

- Framework developed in this study has not been tested on any M&A integrations so therefore, it can be tested for future studies in the field of financial and telecommunications sectors.
- Primary data collected in the research was in relation to the different industries across countries however future research can have focused only on to one case of M&A integration in particular field or country to study the individual case of M&A integration between two firms which may also have an impact on M&A.

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Appendix A. Consent Form

Title of Project: **'Human integration issues during post mergers and acquisitions:
A mix methodology approach in the study of successful mergers of humans'**

Name of Researcher: **Mehmood Jamshed**

1. I confirm that I have read and understand the participant information sheet for the above study. I have had the opportunity to consider the information, ask questions and have had these answered satisfactorily.
2. I understand that my participation is voluntary and that I am free to withdraw at any time without giving any reason, without my legal rights being affected.
3. I understand that any information recorded in the investigation will remain confidential and no information that identifies me will be made publicly available.
4. I consent to use of the data in research, publications, sharing and archiving as explained in the participant information sheet.

Name of Participant

Date

Signature

Consent form date of issue

Appendix B. Information Sheet

Participant Information Sheet

Project Title: Human integration issues during post mergers and acquisitions:

A mix methodology approach in the study of successful mergers of humans.

You are invited to participate in a research study being conducted by [Mehmood Jamshed doctorate research student at University of West of Scotland] under the Supervision of Dr Rose Leburn.

Project Summary: Research's aim is to provide the recommendations on the factors that affect the humans during post mergers and acquisitions period which can cause failure to integration between the firms. This research will investigate the factors involves merging culture, leadership, communication, emotions, IT/IS, HRM issues such as employees' satisfactions, turnover of key people, post-merger performance drops, and morale problems. Finally, study will develop conceptual integrative framework which will achieve the mergers and acquisitions goals incorporating the human factors affecting mergers of two firms.

How is the study being paid for?

Private funding

What will I be asked to do?

You will be asked to answer the questions listed on questionnaires.

How much of my time will I need to give?

10-15 minutes

What benefits will I, and/or the broader community, receive for participating?

You will be received with a copy of research findings after finalising the research

Will the study involve any risk or discomfort for me? If so, what will be done to rectify it?

No

How do you intend to publish or disseminate the results?

It is anticipated that the results of this research project will be published and/or presented in a variety of forums. In any publication and/or presentation, information will be provided in such a way that the participant cannot be identified, except with your permission. Information will be securely locked in safe and on encrypted files on computer which will be password protected.

Can I withdraw from the study?

Participation is entirely voluntary, and you are not obliged to be involved. If you do participate you can withdraw at any time without giving reason.

Can I tell other people about the study?

Yes, you can tell other people about the study by providing them my email address

██

They can contact Investigator (Mehmood Jamshed) directly to discuss their participation in the research project and obtain a copy of the information sheet.

What if I require further information?

Please contact [Mehmood Jamshed] should you wish to discuss the research further before deciding whether or not to participate

What if I have a complaint?

If you have any complaints or reservations about the ethical conduct of this research, you may contact the University of West of Scotland University Ethics Committee (UEC) through school of business & enterprise on Tel +44 141 848 3351 or email businessandenterpriseethics@uws.ac.uk

Any issues you raise will be treated in confidence and investigated fully, and you will be informed of the outcome.

If you agree to participate in this study, you may be asked to sign the Participant Consent Form. The information sheet is for you to keep and the consent form is retained by the researcher/s.

This study has been approved by the University of West of Scotland Business & Enterprise School Research Ethics Committee. Ethical approval application reference 7837, Ethical Approval, submission reference 7061.

Appendix C. Survey Instrument Used for Analysis

Factors	Questions	Abbreviation
Culture	My company gives value to listening to the employees and consider feedback before making decision	Q8
	At my company we treat mistakes like learning opportunities, rather than personal failures.	Q9
	I am satisfied with the culture of my workplace.	Q10
	Both merging firms have suitable cultural fit?	Q13
Cultural Diversity	The leadership at this company encourages diversity.	Q18
	This company gives respect to individuals and value their differences.	Q19
	Employees who are different in background from others are treated fairly in our company.	Q20
	At this company, employees are not resentful of others because of their different race or ethnicity.	Q21
	I have personally experienced discrimination at work.	Q22
	Employees from different backgrounds are encouraged to apply for higher positions.	Q23
	This company provides an environment for the free and open expression of ideas opinions and beliefs.	Q24
	My supervisor/manager handles my personal issues satisfactorily and support me to improve at work.	Q25
	Goals and vision of company are clear to everyone in your team?	Q26
	Everyone seems engaging and committed to the organisation's goals.	Q27
I can see career growth and development opportunities in this organisation.	Q28	
Compensation	I have a good understanding of compensation policies and practices that affect me.	Q29
	The wellness benefits offered by my company have improved my physical and/or mental health.	Q30
	I am compensated (salary/wages) fairly	Q31

	I believed that there will be potential for career growth and increase in incentives and compensation after this M&A.	Q32
Communication	My company way of communication with employees about mergers is very clear and formal?	Q33
	How well does your company facilitate communication among employees and management?	Q34
	Our company discuss important information with employees often about any changes as a result of M&A	Q35
	Employees have experienced psychologically issues as a result of communication between management and employees.	Q36
	Have you been informed effectively and clearly about changes in your job role during M&A?	Q37
	The communication from company about merger is not efficient and as a result i am not satisfied and feeling insecure at work.	Q38
	Receiving regular information and communication with management helps improve emotions at work	Q39
Emotions	My supervisor/manager handles my emotional issues and support me to improve at work	Q45
	Do you trust the management to take this company out of difficult times?	Q46
	During the process of mergers and acquisitions at your company, how bothered were you emotionally such as feeling anxious, depressed, irritable, or sad?	Q47
	Do you think emotions of employees affect their performance at work?	Q48
	I am concerned about my future and inadequate working conditions after M&A.	Q49
	Emotional distress at work force employees to search for the better options.	Q50
	Emotions in my perception is the most important factor of performance enhancement of the employees.	Q51
	During M&A, how do you feel about your emotional balance?	Q52
During M&A, Better communication has a positive impact on emotions	Q53	
Management Change	How did management listen to employees' opinions when making decisions about making changes in processes as a result of M&A?	Q55
	Employees believe that our company will achieve its target as a result of this M&A	Q56
	My company believes that people have a certain amount of talent, and they can't do much to change it	Q57
	My company believes that people can always greatly improve their talents and abilities to enable change in company.	Q58

	Involvement of employees in making changes will boost fairness, commitment, and trust	Q59
	Other stake holders such as customers, consultants, and labour unions should be considered in decision making which will increase the chances of smooth integration between both merging partners and change process	Q60
	Employees in my organisation willingly accept change	Q61
	Employees believe that the company will achieve its target as a result of this M&A	Q63
IT System	I believe that this M&A will enhance my skills and capabilities in future?	Q71
	Were the learning objectives clearly defined before and throughout the length of the training	Q72
	Did you learn everything that was laid out in the learning objectives of IT and systems?	Q73
	Did you feel that this training adds value / Did you learn something new? Will it boost your confidence artwork?	Q74
	Did you feel you had the time and resources to appropriately complete this training?	Q75
	Is the training relevant to your career growth? Will you use these learned skillsets?	Q76
	Training to employees about new IT and systems was?	Q77

Appendix D. Survey Instrument sent to respondents

Final M&A (Mergers and acquisitions) Survey People

Q1. What is your gender?

Female	Answer Choices
Male	

Q2. What is your age?

18 to 24	Answer Choices
25 to 34	

35 to 44
45 to 54
55 to 64
65 to 74
75 or older

Q3. Which of the following best describes your current job level?

Answer Choices

Owner/Executive/C-Level
Senior Management
Middle Management
Intermediate
Entry Level

Q4. Which company you from?

Answer Choices

Acquired (target firm)
Acquiring (bidding firm)
Other (please specify)

Q5. How long have you worked for the company?

Answer Choices

Less than 6 months
6 months - 1 year
1 - 2 years
More than 2 years

Q6. Which of the following best describes the principal industry of your organisation?

Answer Choices

Advertising & Marketing
Agriculture
Airlines & Aerospace (including Defence)
Automotive

Business Support & Logistics
Construction, Machinery, and Homes
Education
Entertainment & Leisure
Finance & Financial Services
Food & Beverages
Government
Healthcare & Pharmaceuticals
Insurance
Manufacturing
Non-profit
Retail & Consumer Durables
Real Estate
Telecommunications, Technology, Internet & Electronics
Transportation & Delivery
Utilities, Energy, and Extraction
I am currently not employed

Q7. In what country do you live?

Answer Choices

Afghanistan
Albania
Algeria
Andorra
Angola
Anguilla
Antigua and Barbuda
Argentina
Armenia
Australia
Austria
Azerbaijan
Bahamas
Bahrain
Bangladesh
Barbados
Belarus
Belgium
Belize
Benin
Bhutan

Bolivia (Pluractional State of)
Bosnia and Herzegovina
Botswana
Brazil
British Virgin Island
Brunei Darussalam
Bulgaria
Burkina Faso
Burundi
Cabo Verde
Cambodia
Cameroon
Canada
Cayman Islands
Central African Republic
Chad
Chile
China
Colombia
Comoros
Congo
Costa Rica
Côte D'Ivoire
Croatia
Cuba
Cyprus
Czech Republic
Democratic People's Republic of Korea
Democratic Republic of the Congo
Denmark
Djibouti
Dominica
Dominican Republic
Ecuador
Egypt
El Salvador
Equatorial Guinea
Eritrea
Estonia
Ethiopia
Fiji
Finland
France

Gabon
Gambia
Georgia
Germany
Ghana
Greece
Grenada
Guatemala
Guinea
Guinea Bissau
Guyana
Haiti
Holy See
Honduras
Hungary
Iceland
India
Indonesia
Iran (Islamic Republic of)
Iraq
Ireland
Israel
Italy
Jamaica
Japan
Jordan
Kazakhstan
Kenya
Kiribati
Kuwait
Kyrgyzstan
Lao People's Democratic Republic
Latvia
Lebanon
Lesotho
Liberia
Libya
Liechtenstein
Lithuania
Luxembourg
Madagascar
Malawi
Malaysia

Maldives
Mali
Malta
Marshall Islands
Mauritania
Mauritius
Mexico
Micronesia (Federated States of)
Monaco
Mongolia
Montenegro
Montserrat
Morocco
Mozambique
Myanmar
Namibia
Nauru
Nepal
Netherlands
New Zealand
Nicaragua
Niger
Nigeria
Norway
Oman
Pakistan
Palau
Panama
Papua New Guinea
Paraguay
Peru
Philippines
Poland
Portugal
Qatar
Republic of Korea
Republic of Moldova
Romania
Russian Federation
Rwanda
Saint Kitts and Nevis
Saint Lucia
Saint Vincent and the Grenadines

Samoa
San Marino
Sao Tome and Principe
Saudi Arabia
Senegal
Serbia
Seychelles
Sierra Leone
Singapore
Slovakia
Slovenia
Solomon Islands
Somalia
South Africa
South Sudan
Spain
Sri Lanka
State of Palestine
Sudan
Suriname
Swaziland
Sweden
Switzerland
Syrian Arab Republic
Tajikistan
Thailand
The former Yugoslav Republic of Macedonia
Timor-Leste
Togo
Tonga
Trinidad and Tobago
Tunisia
Turkey
Turkmenistan
Turks and Caicos
Tuvalu
Uganda
Ukraine
United Arab Emirates
United Kingdom of Great Britain and Northern Ireland
United Republic of Tanzania
United States of America
Uruguay

Uzbekistan
Vanuatu
Venezuela (Bolivarian Republic of)
Vietnam
Yemen
Zambia
Zimbabwe

Q8. My company gives value to listening to the employees and consider feedback before making decisions.

Answer Choices

Strongly agree
Agree
Neither agree nor disagree
Disagree
Strongly disagree

Q9. At my company we treat mistakes like learning opportunities, rather than personal failures.

Answer Choices

Strongly agree
Agree
Neither agree nor disagree
Disagree
Strongly disagree

Q10. I am satisfied with the culture of my workplace.

Answer Choices

Strongly Disagree
Disagree
Neutral/Neither agree nor disagree
Agree
Strongly Agree

Q11. I like/dislike the following cultural elements of my company.

Answer Choices

- Stories - the past and present events and people talked about inside and outside the company
- Rituals and routines - the daily behaviour and actions of people that signal acceptable behaviour
- Symbols - the visual representations of the company including logos, office decor and formal or informal dress codes
- Organisational structure - includes organisation chart, and the unwritten lines of power and influence that indicate whose contributions are most valued
- Control systems - the ways that the organisation is controlled including financial systems, quality systems, and rewards
- Power structures - Power in the company may lie, for example, with one or two executives, with a group of executives or a department, or it may be more evenly distributed in a 'flat' organisational structure. These people have the greatest amount of influence on decisions, operations, and strategic direction.
- Other (please specify)

Q12. How valuable is the culture of partner firm to you or your company?

Answer Choices

Extremely valuable
Very valuable
Somewhat valuable
Not so valuable
Not at all valuable

Q13. Both merging firms have suitable cultural fit?

Answer Choices

Strongly agree
Agree
Neither agree nor disagree
Disagree
Strongly disagree

Q14. I like/dislike merging partner because of following cultural elements

Answer Choices

- Stories - the past and present events and people talked about inside and outside the company
- Rituals and routines - the daily behaviour and actions of people that signal acceptable behaviour
- Symbols - the visual representations of the company including logos, office decor and formal or informal dress codes
- Organisational structure - includes organisation chart, and the unwritten lines of power and influence that indicate whose contributions are most valued
- Control systems - the ways that the organisation is controlled including financial systems, quality systems, and rewards
- Power structures - Power in the company may lie, for example, with one or two executives, with a group of executives or a department, or it may be more evenly distributed in a 'flat' organisational structure. These people have the greatest amount of influence on decisions, operations, and strategic direction.
- Other (please specify)

Q15. Cultural elements of both merging partners are

Answer Choices

All cultural elements in both firms are similar (integrated)

Most of cultural elements in both firms are similar

Some of cultural elements in both firms are similar (differentiated)

A few of the cultural elements in both firms are similar

None of the cultural elements in both firms are similar (fragmented)

Other (please specify)

Q16. Which company culture you would like to preserve after M&A?

Answer Choices

Acquiring firm or bidding firm

Target firm or acquired firm

Mix of both

Completely new culture

Other (please specify)

Q17. Is there any additional information that you would like us to know about culture of both merging companies?

Answer write here

Q18. The leadership at this company encourages diversity

Answer Choices

- Strongly agree
- Agree
- Neither agree nor disagree
- Disagree
- Strongly disagree

Q19. This company gives respect to individuals and value their differences

Answer Choices

- Strongly agree
- Agree
- Neither agree nor disagree
- Disagree
- Strongly disagree

Q20. Employees who are different in background from others are treated fairly in our company

Answer Choices

- Strongly agree
- Agree
- Neither agree nor disagree
- Disagree
- Strongly disagree

Q21. At this company, employees are not resentful of others because of their different race or ethnicity

Answer Choices

- Strongly agree
- Agree
- Neither agree nor disagree
- Disagree
- Strongly disagree

Q22. I have personally experienced discrimination at work

Answer Choices

Strongly agree
Agree
Neither agree nor disagree
Disagree
Strongly disagree

Q23. Employees from different backgrounds are encouraged to apply for higher positions

Answer Choices

Strongly agree
Agree
Neither agree nor disagree
Disagree
Strongly disagree

Q24. This company provides an environment for the free and open expression of ideas opinions and beliefs

Answer Choices

Strongly agree
Agree
Neither agree nor disagree
Disagree
Strongly disagree

Q25. My supervisor/manager handles my personal issues satisfactorily and support me to improve at work

Answer Choices

Strongly agree
Agree
Neither agree nor disagree
Disagree
Strongly disagree

Q26. Goals and vision of company are clear to everyone in your team?

Answer Choices

Strongly agree
Agree
Neither agree nor disagree
Disagree
Strongly disagree

Q27. Everyone seems engaging and committed to the organisation's goals

Answer Choices

Strongly agree
Agree
Neither agree nor disagree
Disagree
Strongly disagree

Q28. I can see career growth and development opportunities in this organisation

Answer Choices

Strongly agree
Agree
Neither agree nor disagree
Disagree
Strongly disagree

Q29. I have a good understanding of compensation policies and practices that affect me.

Answer Choices

Yes
No

Q30. The wellness benefits offered by my company have improved my physical and/or mental health

Answer Choices

Yes
No

Q31. I am compensated (salary/wages) fairly.

Answer Choices

Yes
No

Q32. I believed that there will be potential for career growth and increase in incentives and compensation after this M&A.

Answer Choices

Strongly agree
Agree
Neither agree nor disagree
Disagree
Strongly disagree

Q33. My company way of communication with employees about mergers is very clear and formal?

Answer Choices

Strongly agree
Agree
Neither agree nor disagree
Disagree
Strongly disagree

Q34. How well does your company facilitate communication among employees and management?

Answer Choices

Extremely well
Very well

Somewhat well
Not so well
Not at all well

Q35. Our company discuss important information with employees often about any changes as a result of M&A.

Answer Choices

Strongly agree
Agree
Neither agree nor disagree
Disagree
Strongly disagree

Q36. Employees have experienced psychologically issues as a result of communication between management and employees.

Answer Choices

Strongly agree
Agree
Neither agree nor disagree
Disagree
Strongly disagree

Q37. Have you been informed effectively and clearly about changes in your job role during M&A?

Answer Choices

Strongly agree
Agree
Neither agree nor disagree
Disagree
Strongly disagree

Q38. The communication from company about merger is not efficient and as a result i am not satisfied and feeling insecure at work.

Answer Choices

Strongly agree
Agree
Neither agree nor disagree
Disagree
Strongly disagree

Q39. Receiving regular information and communication with management helps improve emotions at work.

Answer Choices

Yes
No

Q40. When is the best time to communicate with employees?

Answer Choices

During the merger is the best time to discuss about the idea.
Before the merger activity took place, is the right time to discuss.
No, it's the matter of concern for the higher officials only.
It's an important thing to discuss with the staff as they are the sole reason of the workability.
Other (please specify)

Q41. How do you think that communication has an impact on employees?

Answer Choices

Better communication gives time to switch or to continue with the plan of the company's merger plan.
Better communication fills the gap between the owners and employees.
I think it does not affect employees at all.
Employees feel more connected (emotionally) if the communication process is effective.
Other (please specify)

Q42. Do you have experience of working with companies involved in merging and acquisitions?

Answer Choices

Yes

No

Other (please specify)

Q43. How do you think your company have tackled the issues of communication and engagement with its employees during M&A?

Answer Choices

Merger is a tough decision to take and off course we tackle the communication and engagement process with high priority.

Merger is a tough decision to take and we tried to tackle the communication and engagement process, but many loopholes remains.

It's a smooth process and we didn't face any issues of communication and engagement in the process.

It's a smooth process as we tackle the communication and engagement process with high priority.

Other (please specify)

Q44. Is there any additional information that you would like us to know about communication strategy of your company during M&A?

Answer write here

Q45. My supervisor/manager handles my emotional issues and support me to improve at work

Answer Choices

Strongly agree

Agree

Neither agree nor disagree

Disagree

Strongly disagree

Q46. Do you trust the management to take this company out of difficult times?

Answer Choices

Always

Usually

Sometimes

Rarely
Never

Q47. During the process of mergers and acquisitions at your company, how bothered were you emotionally such as feeling anxious, depressed, irritable, or sad?

Answer Choices

Extremely bothered
Very bothered
Somewhat bothered
Not so bothered
Not at all bothered

Q48. Do you think emotions of employees affect their performance at work?

Answer Choices

Strongly agree
Agree
Somewhat agree
Neither agree nor disagree
Somewhat disagree
Disagree
Strongly disagree
Other (please specify)

Q49. I am concerned about my future and inadequate working conditions after M&A.

Answer Choices

Strongly agree
Agree
Neither agree nor disagree
Disagree
Strongly disagree

Q50. Emotional distress at work force employees to search for the better options.

Answer Choices

Strongly agree
Agree
Neither agree nor disagree
Disagree
Strongly disagree

Q51. Emotions in my perception is the most important factor of performance enhancement of the employees.

Answer Choices

Strongly agree
Agree
Neither agree nor disagree
Disagree
Strongly disagree

Q52. During M&A, how do you feel about your emotional balance?

Answer Choices

Much better
Better
About the same
Worse
Much worse

Q53. During M&A, Better communication has a positive impact on emotions

Answer Choices

Strongly agree
Agree
Neither agree nor disagree
Disagree
Strongly disagree

Q54. Is there any additional information that you would like us to know about dealing with employees' emotions of your company?

Answer write here

Q55. How did management listen to employees' opinions when making decisions about making changes in processes as a result of M&A?

Answer Choices

Always
Usually
Sometimes
Rarely
Never

Q56. Employees believe that our company will achieve its target as a result of this M&A

Answer Choices

Strongly agree
Agree
Neither agree nor disagree
Disagree
Strongly disagree

Q57. My company believes that people have a certain amount of talent, and they can't do much to change it.

Answer Choices

Strongly agree
Agree
Neither agree nor disagree
Disagree
Strongly disagree

Q58. My company believes that people can always greatly improve their talents and abilities to enable change in company.

Answer Choices

Strongly agree
Agree
Neither agree nor disagree
Disagree
Strongly disagree

Q59. Involvement of employees in making changes will boost fairness, commitment, and trust.

Answer Choices

Strongly agree
Agree
Neither agree nor disagree
Disagree
Strongly disagree

Q60. Other stake holders such as customers, consultants, and labour unions should be considered in decision making which will increase the chances of smooth integration between both merging partners and change process.

Answer Choices

Strongly agree
Agree
Neither agree nor disagree
Disagree
Strongly disagree

Q61. Employees in my organisation willingly accept change.

Answer Choices

Strongly Disagree
Disagree
Neutral/Neither agree nor disagree
Agree
Strongly Agree

Q62. Employees will resist the change due to following

Answer Choices

- Compensation / job security
- Power struggle
- Emotions such as stress and anxiety
- Unrealistic expectations
- Reduced cooperation by management
- Other (please specify)

Q63. Employees believe that the company will achieve its target as a result of this M&A

Answer Choices

- Strongly agree
- Agree
- Neither agree nor disagree
- Disagree
- Strongly disagree

Q64. What have been the obstacles, if any, you've encountered when trying to attain your goals? (Select all that apply.)

Answer Choices

- Out of office (vacation/sick)
- Too much work
- Not enough support
- Insufficient supplies or equipment
- Workplace distractions
- Personal distractions
- I have not encountered any obstacles
- Other (please specify)

Q65. Merging firms will have following IT and systems structure in place as a result of M&A.

Answer Choices

- Acquiring firm will fully absorb the target firm including its systems, operation, IT and processes.

Acquiring firm will only acquire the functions which relates to core competencies or structures that create competitive advantage from target firm.

Acquiring firm will not integrate any of its IT and systems or operations and remains fully intact within the merged entity.

Other (please specify)

Q66. IT and systems goals are fully aligned with the strategic goals of merging firms.

Answer Choices

Strongly agree

Agree

Neither agree nor disagree

Disagree

Strongly disagree

Q67. IT and information systems of both merging partners are

Answer Choices

All IT and systems in both firms are similar (integration IT/IS)

Most of software and IT in both firms are similar

Some of the systems and IT in both firms are similar (differentiated IT/IS)

A few of the systems and IT in both firms are similar

None of the systems and IT systems in both firms are similar (fragmented IT/IS)

Q68. Do you think IT and systems department of your company have the personnel and resources they need to achieve their goals?

Answer Choices

Yes

No

Q69. Do you believe that employees responsible for managing IT systems are trained in managing such systems?

Answer Choices

Yes

No

Q70. Do you think that the decisions made about IT and software projects were sound and good?

Answer Choices

Yes
No

Q71. I believe that this M&A will enhance my skills and capabilities in future?

Answer Choices

Yes
No

Q72. Were the learning objectives clearly defined before and throughout the length of the training?

Answer Choices

Yes
No

Q73. Did you learn everything that was laid out in the learning objectives of IT and systems?

Answer Choices

Yes
No

Q74. Did you feel that this training adds value / Did you learn something new? Will it boost your confidence at work?

Answer Choices

Yes
No

Q75. Did you feel you had the time and resources to appropriately complete this training?

Answer Choices

Yes
No

Q76. Is the training relevant to your career growth? Will you use these learned skillsets?

Answer Choices

Yes
No

Q77. Training to employees about new IT and systems was

Answer Choices

Extremely helpful
Very helpful
Somewhat helpful
Not so helpful
Not at all helpful / no training provided
Other (please specify)

Q78. How did you feel about getting training during M&A?

Answer Choices

Very satisfied
Satisfied
Neither satisfied nor dissatisfied
Dissatisfied
Very dissatisfied

Q79. Were you able to provide feedback about the IT and systems' training?

Answer Choices

Yes

Appendix E. Outline Tabulation of the Selected Studies for Meta-Synthesis

S/N	Authors	Year	Cases	Factor
1	Angwin et al., (2014)	2014	Multiple papers	Communication
2	Zagelmeyar et al., (2016)	2016	Single paper	Communication
3	Allata and Harbir, (2011)	2011	Single paper	Communication
4	Brahma and Srivastava, (2007)	2007	Single paper	Communication
5	Papadakis, (2005)	2005	Single paper	Communication
6	Sciweiger, (1991)	1991	Single paper	Communication
7	Teerikangas and Very, (2006)	2006	Single paper	Culture
8	Hitt et al., (2012)	2012	Multiple papers	Culture
9	Stahl and Voigt, (2007)	2007	Multiple papers	Culture
10	Drori et al., (2011)	2011	Single paper	Culture
11	Fang et al, (2004)	2004	Single paper	Culture
12	Dhillon et al., (2016)	2016	Multiple papers	Culture
13	Halsall, (2008)	2008	Multiple papers	Culture
14	Weber and Camerer, (2003)	2003	Multiple papers	Culture
15	Cartwright and Cooper, (1993)	1993	Single paper	Emotions
16	Goyal and Joshi, (2012)	2012	Single paper	Emotions
17	Tikkakoski et al., (2018)	2018	Multiple papers	Emotions
18	Hassetta et al., (2018)	2018	Multiple papers	Emotions
19	Kiefer et al., (2001)	2001	Multiple papers	Emotions

20	Fisher, (2000)	2000	Multiple papers	Emotions
21	Antila and Kakkonen, (2007)	2007	Multiple papers	HRM
22	Aguilera et al., (2008)	2018	Multiple papers	HRM
23	Murugesan and Venugopsl, (2018)	2018	Single paper	HRM
24	Chang-Howe, (2019)	2019	Single paper	HRM
25	Weber, (2015)	2015	Single paper	HRM
26	Weber and Drori, (2011)	2011	Single paper	HRM
27	Krug and Aguilera, (2004)	2004	Multiple papers	HRM
28	King et al., (2014)	2014	Single paper	HRM
29	Pawan et al., (2016)	2016	Single paper	HRM
30	Budhwar et al., (2009)	2009	Single paper	HRM
31	Hsu and Chen, (2006)	2006	Multiple papers	IS
32	Alaranta, (2005)	2005	Multiple papers	IS
33	Bhattacharya et al., (2010)	2010	Single paper	IS
34	Jordan, (2019)	2019	Single paper	IS
35	Tanriverdi and Uysal, (2011)	2011	Multiple papers	IS
36	Adekola, (2011)	2011	Single paper	Job Satisfaction
38	Kyeraa, (2016)	2016	Single paper	Job Satisfaction
39	Gupta, 2012	2012	Multiple papers	Job Satisfaction
40	Gugler and Yurtoglu, (2004)	2004	Single paper	Job Satisfaction
41	Maditinos et al., (2009)	2009	Single paper	Job Satisfaction
42	Gill, (2012)	2012	Multiple papers	Leadership
43	Mishra et al., 2018	2018	Multiple papers	Leadership
44	King et al., (2004)	2004	Single paper	Leadership
45	Bari et al., (2019)	2019	Multiple papers	Leadership

46	Junni and Sarala, (2014)	2014	Single paper	Leadership
47	Bansal, (2017)	2017	Single paper	Training
48	Thakur et al., (2016)	2016	Multiple papers	Training
49	Suifan, (2015)	2015	Single paper	Training
50	Grund and Titz, (2018)	2018	Multiple papers	Training

Appendix F. Summarisation details of Selected Studies for Meta-Synthesis

S/N	Title of selected Studies	Authors	Publication Source	Year
1	How communication approaches impact mergers and acquisitions outcomes	Angwin et al., (2014)	Review paper	2014
2	Exploring the link between management communication and emotions in mergers and acquisitions	Zagelmeyar et al., (2016)	Research paper	2016
3	Evolving communication patterns in response to an acquisition event	Allata and Harbir, (2011)	Research paper	2011
4	Communication, Executive Retention, and Employee Stress as Predictors of Acquisition Performance: An Empirical Evidence	Brahma and Srivastava, (2007)	Research paper	2007
5	The role of broader context and the communication program in merger and acquisition implementation success	Papadakis, (2005)	Research paper	2005
6	Communication with employees following a merger: A longitudinal field experiment	Sciweiger, (1991)	Research paper	1991
7	The Culture–Performance Relationship in M&A: From Yes/No to How	Teerikangas and Very, (2006)	Research paper	2006

8	Creating Value Through Mergers and Acquisitions: Challenges and Opportunities	Hitt et al., (2012)	Review paper	2012
9	Do Cultural Differences Matter in Mergers and Acquisitions? A Tentative Model and Examination	Stahl and Voigt, (2007)	Review paper	2007
10	Cultural clashes in a “merger of equals”: the case Of high-tech start-ups	Drori et al., (2011)	Review paper	2011
11	Why did the Telia–Telenor merger fail?	Fang et al, (2004)	Research paper	2004
12	Interpreting information security culture: An organisational transformation case study	Dhillon et al., (2016)	Review paper	2016
13	Intercultural Mergers and Acquisitions as ‘Legitimacy Crises’ of Models of Capitalism: A UK–German Case Study	Halsall, (2008)	Review paper	2008
14	Cultural Conflict and Merger Failure: An Experimental Approach	Weber and Camerer, (2003)	Review paper	2003
15	The psychological impact of merger and acquisition on the individual: A study of building society managers	Cartwright and Cooper, (1993)	Research paper	1993
16	Impact of Merger on Stress Level of Employees (A Case Study of Erstwhile Bank of Rajasthan Ltd.)	Goyal and Joshi, (2012)	Research paper	2012
17	Emotions related to mergers and acquisitions	Tikkakoski et al., (2018)	Review paper	2018
18	The Emotions of Top Managers and Key Persons in Cross-Border M&As: Evidence from a longitudinal case study	Hassetta et al., (2018)	Review paper	2018
19	Understanding the Emotional Experience of Organisational Change: Evidence from a Merger	Kiefer et al., (2001)	Review paper	2001
20	Mood and emotions while working: missing pieces of job satisfaction?	Fisher, (2000)	Review paper	2000
21	Factors affecting the role of HR managers in international mergers and acquisitions	Antila and Kakkonen, (2007)	Review paper	2007
22	Institutions and Organisational Socialization: Integrating Employees in Cross-Border Mergers and Acquisitions	Aguilera et al., (2008)	Review paper	2008

23	Role of human resource management in Mergers and acquisitions	Murugesan and Venugopsl, (2018)	Research paper	2018
24	The challenge of HR integration: a review of the M&A HR integration literature	Chang-Howe, (2019)	Research paper	2019
25	Development and Training at Mergers and Acquisitions	Weber, (2015)	Research paper	2015
26	Integrating Organisational and Human Behaviour Perspectives on Mergers and Acquisitions	Weber and Drori, (2011)	Research paper	2011
27	Meta-analyses of post-acquisition performance: Indications of unidentified moderators	Krug and Aguilera, (2004)	Review paper	2004
28	Barriers to effective HRM”	King et al., (2014)	Research paper	2014
29	The Role of HR in Cross-Border Mergers and Acquisitions: The Case of Indian Pharmaceutical Firms	Pawan et al., (2016)	Research paper	2016
30	HRM in context: The applicability of HRM models in India	Budhwar et al., (2001)	Research paper	2001
31	The Impact of Mergers and Acquisitions on Information Systems: A Case of a Software Industry Acquisition	Hsu and Chen, (2006)	Review paper	2006
32	Evaluating Success in Post-Merger IS Integration: A Case Study	Alaranta, (2005)	Research paper	2005
33	Enabling Strategic Transformations with Enterprise Systems: Beyond Operational Efficiency	Bhattacharya et al., (2010)	Research paper	2010
34	Mergers and Acquisitions: Organisational Integration Strategies	Jordan, (2019)	Review paper	2019
35	Cross-Business Information Technology Integration and Acquirer Value Creation in Corporate Mergers and Acquisitions	Tanriverdi and Uysal, (2011)	Research paper	2011
36	Career planning and career management as correlates for career development and job satisfaction A case study of Nigerian bank employees	Adekola, (2011)	Research paper	2011
37	The impact of acquisition on employee’s satisfaction	Kyeraa, (2016)	Research paper	2016

38	Mergers and acquisitions (m&a): the strategic concepts for the nuptials of corporate sector.	Gupta, 2012	Review paper	2012
39	The effects of mergers on company employment in the USA and Europe	Gugler and Yurtoglu, (2004)	Research paper	2004
40	The Effect of Mergers and Acquisitions on the Performance of Companies – The Greek Case of Ioniki-Laiki Bank and Pisteos Bank	Maditinos et al., (2009)	Research paper	2009
41	The role of leadership in Successful international Mergers and acquisitions: Why Renault Nissan succeeded And Daimler Chrysler Mitsubishi Failed	Gill, (2012)	Review paper	2012
42	The impact of trust on leadership during mergers and acquisitions: case studies from the Indian telecom sector	Mishra et al., 2018	Research paper	2018
43	Meta-analyses of Post-acquisition Performance: Indications of Unidentified Moderators	King et al., (2004)	Research paper	2004
44	Soft Issues During Cross-Border Mergers and Acquisitions and Industry Performance, China–Pakistan Economic Corridor Based View	Bari et al., (2019)	Research paper	2019
45	The Role of Leadership in Mergers and Acquisitions: A Review of Recent Empirical Studies	Junni and Sarala, (2014)	Research paper	2014
47	Training during transitions: The context of a developing Economy	Bansal, (2017)	Review paper	2017
48	The role of thriving and Training in merger success: An integrative learning Perspective	Thakur et al., (2016)	Research paper	2016
49	The Effect of Human Resources Practices on Organisational Commitment: A Jordanian Study	Suifan, (2015)	Review paper	2015
50	Further Training and Affective Commitment	Grund and Titz, (2018)	Research paper	2018

